

BEST PRACTICE AND SITUATION ANALYSIS

WP5

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GLOSSARY

Table 1 - List of terms

Term	Definition
VL best practice	The best practice selected for this JA is the “Reverse Diabetes2 Now experience”. It is an evidence-based and reimbursed Dutch lifestyle treatment and training programme for type 2 diabetes, developed and promoted by the Dutch non-profit organisation Voeding Leeft.
C4D practice	Developed and implemented practice based on in-depth understanding of the VL best practice on one hand, and based on understanding of each C4D practice contexts including key stakeholders on the other per each pilot country in JA C4D.
C4D team	Is the core team of C4D JA in collaborative learning and knowledge generation which eliminates bottlenecks during the implementation of C4D practice, provides strategic vision and supports implementation process through the focus of the system, sustainability, scalability of the practice.
Multidisciplinary team	Multidisciplinary team runs the C4D practice with the patients, provides feedback and reflections, and shares experiences on real life practice. Participates in continuous monitoring and assessment of implementation practice and in collaborative learning and knowledge generation within this JA.
Implementing countries	12 EU countries (Bulgaria, Belgium, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain), implementing C4D practice.
SCIROCCO Tool	The Scirocco self-assessment tool is used to identify the maturity of the health and social care systems for the adoption and scaling up of integrated care or best practice solutions.
CFIR construct	The Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research is a determinants framework designed to describe barriers and facilitators to implementation outcomes.
JA CHRODIS+ and JADECARE	Joint Actions funded by the EU Health Programme whose experiences and methodological approaches are being used in C4D: JA CHRODIS+ - Implementing good practices for chronic diseases JADECARE – Capacity building in Europe for digitally enabled integrated care
SWOT	SWOT is a technique for assessing four aspects: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. SWOT Analysis is a tool that can help analyze what your

Term	Definition
	organization does best now, and to devise a successful strategy for the future.
Study visit	In Work Package 5 of JA C4D study visit was performed at VL practice to support and evaluate the implementation of VL best practice to C4D pilot countries. The study visit was conducted by experts which consisted of the WP5 Task 5.1 leader; NIJZ and coordinators of the project as observers.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Table 2 - List of acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Description
CARE4DIABETES / C4D	Reducing the burden of non-communicable diseases by providing a multi-disciplinary lifestyle treatment intervention for type 2 diabetes
WP5	Work Package 5: Preparatory actions (Joint Action Care 4 Diabetes)
D	Deliverable
JA	Joint Action
VL	Voeding Leeft
RD2N	Reverse Diabetes 2 Now
GP	General Practitioner
MoH	Ministry of Health
HCP	Healthcare professional
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
T2D	Type 2 diabetes

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

CARE4DIABETES (C4D) Joint Action supports 30 competent authorities from 12 Member States in reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes through effective lifestyle treatment programs, developed by learning process based on NGO Voeding Leeft (VL best practice) experiences.

The **purpose** is to support preparatory actions within C4D by providing a comprehensive analysis of core aspects of the VL best practice to be considered by pilot local teams while designing, implementing, monitoring and evaluating their C4D practice, and to review the contexts and key stakeholders to engage within C4D pilot countries.

The **objective** of this deliverable is (1) to timely present main recommendations to support development and implementation of C4D practices based on in-depth understanding of the VL best practice, and (2) to provide baseline understanding of each C4D practice contexts including key stakeholders. This deliverable addresses cross-sectional elements that will be reflected upon on communication and dissemination activities (D2.3); country implementation plans (D5.2), train-the-trainers actions (D6.1), sustainability oriented actions (D4.1) and the reports on the Phase I and Phase II activities (D6.2 and D7.1).

The **intended audience** are members from C4D teams from implementing countries, and other members from competent authorities and associated entities. In addition, main learnings are important to institutions, associations and other stakeholders outside the consortium of this Joint Action, interested in designing and implementing sustainable educational programmes for diabetes or other (chronic) diseases, or contemplate to apply the principle of good practice transfer in improving health and healthcare.

State-of-the-art **methodological** frameworks and approaches were used to analyse implementation process (Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research CFIR), context characteristics (SCIROCCO Maturity Model), and to provide situation analysis of national/regional and local context (SWOT) including stakeholders' analysis.

Main **results** from in-depth analysis of VL best practice, relevant for the **implementation** process, are: (1) Intervention characteristics: VL best practice was internally developed with strong support of a wide variety of outside stakeholders, was unique to the Dutch context, and addressed the multidimensional nature of type 2 diabetes management; (2) Outer setting: Patient needs and views are continuously considered and the practice has adapted to meet the needs, VL is continuously engaged with stakeholders, and practice is aligned with national policies and funding frameworks; (3) Inner setting: The organizational structure supports continuous information flow between VL teams, frontline professionals and participants of

the program, goals are clearly communicated, acted upon, and aligned with the staff, continuous learning and improvement are encouraged; (4) Characteristics of individuals: self-reflection in achieving implementation goals is valued and supported; passionate commitment of individuals to the goals of the organization exists and there is a perception that they have an impact on practice development; (5) Process: clear protocols exist, including the training; continuous efforts to identify and empower champions within and outside of the VL to overcome indifference or resistance, and there is continuous quantitative and qualitative feedback about progress and experience.

Key characteristics of the **context** that support successful future implementation within C4D are readiness to change, evaluation (to support evidence-based investment) and capacity building (“learning system”).

Main successes of VL best practice are: (1) Establishment of a comprehensive program type 2 diabetes; (2) Inclusion of the program into the Dutch basic insurance; (3) Development of an online based program with comparable outcomes to the face-to-face version and increased accessibility to the program; (4) Continuous focus on engagement and networking; (5) Translation and adaptation of the program into settings outside Netherlands.

Main challenges are: (1) Resistances at various levels of healthcare system; (2) Hesitation on part of the private insurers to fund the program; (3) as a reaction to COVID-19 pandemic development of an online-based program but is appropriate only for low complexity patients; (4) Access to people with lower socio-economic; (5) Patients and healthcare professionals awareness of the program’s existence.

Situation analysis of contexts within C4D implementing countries shows, that all of them have C4D teams with roles assigned and with an agreement on shared purpose and common goal, and in 10 out of 12 have defined a multidisciplinary team. All of C4D teams identified positive and negative characteristics both at the national/regional and at local level. Despite the variability of health systems among the 12 countries, main challenges are largely the same (such as role of digitalisation, increasing number of patients, decreasing number of healthcare professionals). 151 main stakeholders were identified by C4D teams, and their level of involvement is defined.

To conclude, the contexts within C4D pilot countries might differ a lot from the VL best practice context. Nevertheless, some general lessons learnt can be taken: (1) Continuous education of staff is key, but especially important at the beginning. Recommended staff to be included at the very start of practice development are a nurse & dietitian; (2) Proceed step-by-step, go forward when you understand your needs and existent resources. Remain

adjustable, flexible and open to opportunity; (3) Showcase a strong 'business case' as good story sells. Have that in mind when getting funding after the project ends, and (4) Keep good relationships with stakeholders; showcase results continuously.

1. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

CARE4DIABETES (C4D) Joint Action supports 30 competent authorities from 12 Member States as C4D pilot countries to improve and foster health by reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and related risk factors, both at societal and personal level, through effective lifestyle treatment programs of patients. Partners from C4D consortium will transfer and implement a Dutch evidence-based best practice “Reverse Diabetes 2 Now”, a lifestyle treatment program for type 2 diabetes, developed by the non-governmental organisation Voeding Leefstijl (VL best practice). The practice addresses several components of the promotion of lifestyle changes that can bring improved quality of life in people with type 2 diabetes and healthier blood glucose levels with potential lower medication consumption. The expected outcomes of this JA are to increase patients’ health and quality of life, reduce healthcare associated costs, and promote capacity building of health systems towards more innovative and integrated type 2 diabetes interventions based on patients' lifestyle changes.

The **purpose** of this document is to support C4D pilots’ countries implementation with insights into VL best practice development of objectives, core content, context characteristics and implementation processes; to facilitate their assessment of the relevant national or regional (depending on the structures of the healthcare systems) context as well as the specifics of the local setting where C4D pilot practice will be implemented; and to support early identification of the main stakeholders, and their analysis, that reflects their (planned) level of involvement.

In-depth understanding of the best practice on one hand and C4D pilot countries’ contexts on the other are crucial for understanding the essence of VL best practice model and adopt, adapt or abandon certain elements, or add essential elements needed as a response to each C4D pilot countries’ specificities in terms of socio-cultural, geographical, linguistic aspects and healthcare practices.

The **objective** of the document is to present a comprehensive description of core aspects of VL best practice to be considered by C4D pilot local teams, along with a summary of the national/regional/local situational analysis including main stakeholders' involvement, per each C4D pilot country.

The **intended audience** of this document are primarily C4D pilot local teams, and other members from C4D competent authorities and associated entities. In addition, main learnings are important to institutions, associations and other stakeholders outside the consortium of this Joint action, interested in designing and implementing sustainable educational programmes for diabetes or other (chronic) diseases, or contemplate to apply the principle of good practice transfer in improving health and healthcare.

This document however **does not include** details regarding the online portal, recruitment strategy, materials dedicated to train-the-trainers and materials available to support the patients during the intervention, details on monitoring and reporting of the intervention, communication and dissemination activities, and general principles including essential elements to achieve sustainability of the implemented practice. These are covered by other activities of C4D.

2. METHODOLOGY

Methodological approaches used are scientifically proven and adjusted to the type of data to be collected. Detailed description of methodology, including rationale, preparatory work, and all templates used are presented in Annex I. Methodological guidance document for in-depth review of VL best practice and in Annex II. Methodological guidance document for situation analysis of national/local contexts including main stakeholders.

2.1. In-depth review of VL best practice

The methodology covers several perspectives of VL best practice:

- Description of the objectives of VL best practice and how they were developed
- Description of the core features of VL best practice
- Description of the implementation process (CFIR¹ elements)
- Description of context characteristics minimum maturity requirements for VL practice implementation) using SCIROCCO² approach
 - Description of elements of sustainability that supported/are still supporting VL practice (this part is related to work on sustainability within Work Package 4 and will not be mentioned in detail).

For each of the perspectives of VL best practice, a dedicated methodological document was developed by NIJZ in collaboration and in agreement with VL. Experiences and methodological approaches used in JA CHRODIS+ and JADECARE informed the design of guides for conducting CFIR-based focus group for implementation process and interviews on elements of sustainability. All information collection approaches are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 - Approaches to collect information for in-depth review of VL best practice

Content	Approach used
Description of the objectives and core features of VL best practice	Core features of VL best practice - word template
Description of the implementation process of VL best practice (CFIR elements)	Guide for CFIR based focus group on implementation process

¹ <https://cfirguide.org/>

² <https://www.scirocco-project.eu/maturitymodel/>

	Guide for individual in-depth interview (partly)
Description of elements of sustainability, that supported/are still supporting VL practice	Guide for individual in-depth interview on elements of sustainability of VL best practice <i>(this part is related to work on sustainability within Work Package 4 and will not be mentioned in detail)</i>
Description of context characteristics with minimum maturity requirements	Guide to complete online individual assessment of good practice using SCIROCCO Tool Guide to conduct SCIROCCO Consensus-building workshop

In short, to collect descriptions and basic data to inform further analytical steps, available resources were studied; for missing data, a collaboratively designed word template was used to complete the data. To explore relevant characteristics of the implementation process against CFIR domains (Intervention characteristics, Outer setting, Inner setting, Characteristics of individuals and Process) a focus group was conveyed, the prompting questions being informed by the data from objectives and core features descriptions and preliminary studies on context characteristics. In addition, semi-structured interviews included some questions related to implementation in general, and provided the second source of data. To assess the relative relevance of context dimensions for successful implementation against SCIROCCO dimensions, please see Table 4 (for the full description please see Annex I), individual assessment via online tool was collected after briefing with VL practice core team, finalised by group workshop to achieve a consensus. Individual SCIROCCO assessment using an online SCIROCCO Tool were conducted in January 2023 with participation of 9 respondents, representatives of VL: 1.) EC, Data and Care Relations Director, Project Manager; 2.) BK, Program director; 3.) LS, operational manager; 4.) NZ, Head of medical team; 5.) DB, Regional manager of care relations; 6.) NW, Research Coordinator; 7.) MH, nurse medical team; 8.) MB, program coordinator; 9.) MV, program coordinator.

Table 4 - 12 Scirocco dimensions with short descriptions

Name of dimension	Short description
1. Readiness to change	Re-design requires change across many levels; this process is disruptive and may be viewed negatively by workers, press and public. Clear communication is needed, including a justification, a strategic plan, and a vision of better care.
2. Structure & Governance	Ideally, it needs multi-year programmes with efficient change management, funding and communications, alignment of purpose across diverse organisations

	and professions, and the willingness to collaborate and put the interest of the overall care system above individual incentives.
3. Digital infrastructure	Data-sharing across diverse care teams might be needed, to enable continuous collaboration, and the measurement and management of outcomes.
4. Process coordination	Care coordination of complex processes demands new pathways and services to improve the quality and efficiency of care and avoid unnecessary variation.
5. Funding	Changing systems requires initial investment and funding and on-going financial support until the new services are fully operational.
6. Removal of Inhibitors	Include legal issues with data governance, resistance to change from individuals or professional bodies, cultural barriers to the use of technology, perverse financial incentives, and lack of skills.
7. Population approach	Population health goes beyond this and uses methods to understand where future health risk will come from. It offers ways to act ahead of time, to predict and anticipate, so that citizens can maintain their health for longer and be less dependent on care services as they age.
8. Citizen empowerment	Providing services and tools that enable convenience, offer choice, and encourage self-service and engagement in health management, considering the need to address the risk of health and social inequalities.
9. Evaluation methods	This dimension supports the concept of evidence-based investment, where the impact of each change is evaluated, e.g., by health economists working in universities or in special agencies. Health technology assessment (HTA) is an important method and can be used to justify the cost of scaling up the practices.
10. Breadth of Ambition	The broader the ambition, the more numerous and diverse the stakeholders who have to be engaged. Similarly, integration may include all levels of the system or may be limited to clinical information sharing.
11. Innovation Management	Innovations need to be recognised, assessed and, where possible, scaled up to provide benefit across the system. Managing the innovation process is needed to get the best results for the systems of care and ensuring that good ideas are encouraged and rewarded.
12. Capacity building	Capacity building is the process by which individual and organisations obtain, improve and retain the skills and knowledge needed to do their jobs competently. New roles will need to be created and new skills developed. The systems of care need to become “learning systems” that are constantly striving to improve quality, cost and access, with the capacity to become more adaptable and resilient.

To analyse qualitative data acquired during focus group and interviews, thematic analysis method was used. The sessions were recorded with the consent of the participants, and transcribed. In the next step of thematic analysis, transcription was coded by the researchers, and grouped according to themes. Themes were predetermined – based on the topic, we were using implementation research framework CFIR, but were conscious that if this framework might not sufficiently cover the data, new/additional themes can arise during the process of

analysis itself (e.g., Grounded theory approach). Before analysed information is reported and publicly disseminated, there was at least one round of revision by people who participated in the research activities.

For more details, please consult Annex I. Methodological guidance document for in-depth review of VL best practice.

2.2. Situation analysis of national/local contexts including main stakeholders

Methodological guidance document for situation analysis of national/regional and local contexts including main stakeholders' identification was highly influenced by preliminary analysis of information from in-depth review of VL best practice on one hand and on the other hand tried to leverage the complexity of methodology, timeline and the capacities of C4D pilot local teams.

The analysis was performed at country level and took 4 steps:

- (I) defining C4D pilot local team, (preliminary) multidisciplinary team and their roles;
- (II) defining shared purpose and the common scope of the C4D pilot practice,
- (III) identifying supporting and inhibiting characteristics of the context at national/regional level and at C4D pilot level as well as defining main stakeholders and their level of involvement, and
- (IV) assessment of the identified characteristics as Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats for the C4D pilot practice implementation with re-definition of the shared purpose and the common scope of the C4D pilot practice based on those insights, if needed.

For more details, please consult Annex II. Methodological guidance document for situation analysis of national/local contexts including main stakeholders.

3. RESULTS

All results were collected and analyzed in the methodological framework explained in the previous chapter. In the first section (3.1.) detailed results of the in-depth review of VL best practice consisting of description of the objectives, core features, implementation process and context characteristics are presented. The second section (3.2.) presents the situation analysis of national/regional and local contexts including main stakeholders for each C4D pilot country. For further information, consult Annex III Situation analysis of national/regional and local contexts including main stakeholders, per C4D pilot country.

3.1. In-depth review of VL best practice

In- depth review of VL best practice consists of:

- Description of the objectives of VL best practice and how they were developed
- Description of the core features of VL best practice

Description of the implementation process of VL best practice (CFIR elements)³

- Description of context characteristics minimum maturity requirements for VL practice implementation) using SCIROCCO approach⁴

The detailed description of the methodology and the rationale can be found at Annex I.

3.1.1. Objectives of the VL best practice

VL best practice is an intensive lifestyle program for type 2 diabetes, with an objective to achieve healthier blood glucose levels with potential lower medication consumption, and improvement of physical and mental health related quality of life.

The rationale for and the process leading VL towards the objectives is described in Box 1.

³ <https://cfirguide.org/>

⁴ <https://www.scirocco-project.eu/maturitymodel/>

Box 1. How it all started?

MB, founder of Voeding Lefst, studied business economics and then worked for more than 15 years in various commercial management positions in the food industry for publicly listed multinationals. During that time, his interest gradually shifted from the outside of the product, the packaging and the advertising, to the inside of the product: what does it actually contain and what does that do to my and our health? The last company in the food industry he worked for was a candy company. He became more and more aware of the impact sugar has on our bodies and he began asking himself questions about his job and purpose in life. MB decided to take a year off to go traveling. During his travels he experienced the impact of better nutrition and a healthier lifestyle on his body, his energy levels and his mind. After his year traveling, he realized he had to do something else and started working in a company selling organic food. In the following two years, he discovered that there are few incentives within most societies to support people to have the best possible quality of life and he realized that nutrition and lifestyle can play an enormous role in this. In addition, better nutrition and healthier lifestyles combined with lifestyle as medicine could play an important role in ensuring that health care does not become unaffordable in the long term. That is why in 2011 MB founded Voeding Lefst together with a general practitioner and a medical physiologist. Soon after Voeding Lefst was founded MB and his two co-founders came in contact with HP, an experienced endocrinologist from the Leiden University Medical Center who was seeing many patients with diabetes, and CH, a dietician and NG, a nurse who were working with patients to reverse their type 2 diabetes using nutrition and lifestyle. An important aspect is the behaviour change, so RR as a coach joined the team. Together they started to work on the program Reverse Diabetes2 Now with the first pilots taking place in 2014. Diabetes was chosen based on the experiences of those involved and because it is a disease where lifestyle has a clear and measurable impact. It is also a disease where the patient, through blood glucose measurements can get direct feedback on the effect of nutrition and lifestyle changes which helps develop their ability to manage their disease themselves. Patients also see fast improvements which increase motivation to work further on their lifestyle.

The broader purpose, underlying the objectives of the VL best practice, is outlined by VL purpose-vision-mission-goal statements:

Purpose: VL makes society more vital with the power of nutrition and lifestyle.

Vision: VL makes lifestyle change accessible to everyone.

Mission: VL enables people to experience the impact of lifestyle on body and mind.

The goal of VL is to develop and implement lifestyle programs for people with chronic diseases in order to improve patient health outcomes, quality of life and reduce health care costs.

3.1.2. Core features of VL best practice

Essential core features, such as patient selection and flow during enrolment, human and other resources (inside and outside VL, i.e. stakeholders), description of the intervention, general monitoring and evaluation, expected results and long-term outcomes, its effectiveness, efficiency, evidence base, equity and coverage, and funding mechanisms. From their narrative we captured first suggestions on main barriers and facilitators and on approach, how to solve problems, that are summarised in Chapter 3.1.5. Results of more in-depth analyses are presented in Chapters 3.1.3. and 3.1.4.

The core features of the VL best practice, as they were collected within the work of Task 5.1 of C4D are as follows.

Patient selection criteria and flow during enrolment

Inclusion criteria:

- having prediabetes or type 2 diabetes;
- being under the age of 80 (between 70-80 years in consultation);
- being overweight (BMI>25) and/or having an increased waist size (female>80cm, male>94cm)
- being motivated* for a lifestyle change
- having access to an email address and the internet

Exclusion criteria:

- being over 80 years old;
- having type 1 diabetes;
- having severe COPD GOLD stage III or stage IV;
- having had a gastric bypass;
- having kidney failure (eGFR/MDRD <30);

- having heart failure
- having an eating disorder;
- having mental health issues
- being pregnant;
- being vegan (vegetarian is okay)

*In the registration form people are asked the following questions about their motivation, please see Box 2.

Box 2. Questions to assess motivation

(1) Could you describe your motivation for applying for Reverse Diabetes 2 Now?
(2) To what extent do you agree with the following statements on a scale of 1 - 5? (1 = not motivated and 5 = very motivated):
I am motivated to reverse my type 2 diabetes by means of lifestyle adjustments.
I am willing to make adjustments to my current diet.
I am willing to make exercise a part of my daily life.
I am willing to make relaxation a part of my daily life.
(3) How do you rate the factors below in your current lifestyle on a scale of 1 - 10? (1= bad and 10 very good):
Current diet;
Daily exercise;
Quality of sleep;
Quality of relaxation.

Patient flow during enrolment is shown in Figure 1. In summary, data of the potential participant is collected in the registration form, which is evaluated by the VL "inclusion team". The process is supported by the administrator.

Fig. 1. Patient flow during enrolment

Human resources

Core program team at VL, that runs the intervention of VL best practice, includes several disciplines, please see Table 5. (More detailed descriptions of their competencies were developed within C4D task, related to train-the-trainers, and are not covered here.) Within VL, several other teams and structures support core program team, such as management team, training team, and scientific council, please see Table 6. Stakeholders involved are identified in Table 7.

Table 5 - Multidisciplinary core program team at VL, their competencies and roles/tasks.

Team member's profession	Core competencies (relevant for VL practice)	Role/tasks
General Practitioner (GP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GP: a registered GP according to national standards - Proactive: is able to oversee the situation and act on what is best for the participant. - Results-oriented: has a clear goal in terms of supervision of the medical team. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medical supervision in the inclusion process. Advises medical team in complex cases; - Provides additional medical advice to the program team (nurse) if necessary, during the program and process to reduce medication

Team member's profession	Core competencies (relevant for VL practice)	Role/tasks
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexible: supports the participant and his/her main doctor, listens to what motivates the participant and is able to adjust advice accordingly. - Team player: can work well independently and with the team. Consults, listens and puts the results of the team and group first. 	
Nutritionist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrition: a registered dietician of nutrition according to relevant national standards - Proactive: is able to oversee the situation and act on what is best for the participant. - Results-oriented: has a clear goal in the supervision of the participant, works with the nurse on an optimal reduction of medication. - Flexible: supports the participant and his/her main doctor, listens to what motivates the participant and is able to adjust. - Communication: strong verbal communication skills, can use motivational communication to teach new behaviours and can work well with groups. - Independent: works independently and can also advise individuals and the group from a distance. Works in close cooperation with the team and in particular the nurse. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supports participants in changing eating and lifestyle habits - Presents physiological explanation of the metabolic disturbance of type 2 diabetes (insulin resistance) and the relationship with nutrition, exercise, sleep and stress (relief). - Keeps track of the medical and lifestyle records of the participants' progress.
Coach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bold: able to manage the group with confidence and easily makes decisions. - Observation: is able to review the group from a distance, has a good overview of the situation and acts on what is best for the participant and group. - Sensitive: recognizes the feelings and needs of others and can relate to others and act accordingly. -Communication: strong verbal communication skills, can use motivational communication to teach new behaviours and can work well with groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a safe setting for the individual and the group - Activate and monitor group dynamics - Guidance in awareness and behavioural change. To activate and integrate sustainable behaviour. - Guidance the program team throughout the process.

Team member's profession	Core competencies (relevant for VL practice)	Role/tasks
Nurse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proactive: is able to oversee the situation and act on what is best for the participant. - Results-oriented: has a clear goal in the supervision of the participant, you work on an optimal reduction of medication. - Flexible: supports the participant and his/her main doctor, listens to what motives the participant and is able to adjust. - Team player: can work well independently and with the team. Consults, listens and puts the team result and the result of the group first. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safe process guidance for individual participants - Individual and group guidance on reduction of medication and reversing type 2 diabetes - Manage patient record and registration - Contact with the lead practitioner of the participant
Program Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proactive: is able to oversee the situation and act on what is best for the participant. - Organisational ability: able to organise events and is efficient in time management for optimal planning and organisation. Is well structured. - Team player: can work well independently and with the team. Consults, listens and puts the team result and the result of the group first. - Communication: strong verbal communication skills, can use motivational communication to teach new behaviours and can work well with groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Practical organisation of program (days) and online community. - Administration of participants and progress - Coordinating team - Quality assurance of program

Table 6 - Other teams and structures supporting VL core program team within VL organisation

VL teams	Team members' profession	Core competencies (relevant for VL practice)	Role/tasks
VL management team	Business management	- HR, program management, marketing, finance and IT	- Manage all aspects of the organisation responsible for implementing the program including HR, program management, marketing, finance and IT
VL training team	Includes VL management, doctor, coach, nutritionist, dietician and program coordinators	- Communication: strong verbal communication skills, can use motivational communication to teach	- Provide interactive training sessions on all the relevant aspects of the

		new behaviours and can work well with groups.	Reverse Diabetes 2 program
Scientific council	Scientists	- Research: ability to review program results in the broader context of lifestyle research	- Advising in decision making

Table 7 - Stakeholders of VL, related to VL best practice.

Name of the stakeholder	Profession (if applicable)	Core competencies (relevant for VL practice)	Role/tasks
Diabetes Patient organisation		- Support diabetes patients with information	- Promote the program among its members
Diabetes foundation		- Raise funds for research into diabetes type 1 and type 2 - Provide information on diabetes type 1 and type 2	- Share information on the program
Louis Bolk Research Institute	Researches	- Evaluate program results and publish papers on program results	- Share program results

Other resources

In addition to human resources, several other areas of resources need to be in place, such as financing (direct payment, insurance coverage), facilities and hard copies of the materials for patients (for face-to-face program), or a platform with digital resources (for digital program).

General outline of the VL best practice intervention

VL best practice as an intensive lifestyle program for type 2 diabetes consists of a 6-months intensive care programme (Phase I), followed by 18-months after-care (Phase II), please see Figure 2. During the 6 contact days within Phase I, presentations and workshops (e.g. cooking workshop, exercise workshop, coach sessions around the four pillars of the programme: nutrition, exercise, relaxation and sleep) are delivered to the participants. Phase I and Phase II are also supported by the platform 'Mijn Voeding Leeft', that has 24/7 access and supports sharing experiences and keeping track of the goals, provides additional background

information, inspiration, recipes and agendas for the meetings, and allows the participants to ask questions to the VL team. The goal of Phase II is to support patients to sustain the lifestyle change that were achieved in Phase I. Participants can participate in optional activities in order to improve their reversal process or to get additional support if they have a setback. The activities include presentations to refresh participants' knowledge, Q&A sessions, coach sessions and inspiring in-depth webinars about the four pillars of the programme (nutrition, exercise, relaxation and sleep). The participants have access to the online community during the aftercare phase. Phase II consists of monthly sessions about pathophysiology, coaching and behaviour change, to repeat the basic principles and refresh knowledge, and of a webinar about specific themes for diabetes type 2. Phase II is supported by a continuous online community via the platform.

Fig. 2. VL best practice general outline

Monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring starts already during the participant selection, based on the flowchart (please see Figure 1) and the registration form to check the inclusion and exclusion criteria. During the program, several lines of monitoring and evaluation are in place.

Patient information and progress are stored in a Customer Relationship Management System (a Patient Information System), such as height, weight, waist circumference, blood glucose profiles and laboratory values (Hba1c, fasting blood glucose, lipid profile).

Several questionnaires and forms are used to collect and monitor the progress of the patients:

- Lifestyle status is assessed using a questionnaire that also allows to monitor the progress of the participants at start, 3, 6, 12, 18 and 24 months.

- A special form is used to collect the measurements and to follow the medication use during the programme.

-A quality of life survey is delivered to the participants at the start and at the end of the Phase I to assess the changes in subjective quality of life score.

Feedback from participants and from the core VL team is collected regularly. The participants provide feedback via a survey after each of the 6 contact days within Phase 1 and after the completion of Phase I. In Phase II, a survey is provided after each optional activity to the ones participating. Members of core VL team together give feedback internally after each contact day. Program coordinators take care of the feedback loop for further development.

A self-evaluation tool was developed by VL to increase visibility of VL best practice in 2021. It is a web based tool for “self-test”, with an aim to attract potential participants to show the potential outcomes after participating at VL program in terms of medication reduction and blood glucose control. The tool is based on the results of previous participants collected during the program.

English versions and examples all the forms and questionnaires are introduced to C4D consortium during train-the-training task of C4D.

Expected results and long-term outcomes

Expected results are supported by the scientific literature, please see Chapter 5 on References and Resources. In summary, the results are:

- Significant decreases in weight, BMI, waist circumference, fasting glucose, HbA1c and triglycerides;
- Significant improvement in quality of life;
- Significantly lower experienced fatigue and sleep problems;
- Significant increases in light and moderate physical activity; intensive physical activity increase possible in the long term.

Achieved results and long-term outcomes

Effectiveness Extent to which the objectives of the intervention were achieved.

Results after 6 months (i.e. after intensive period of the intervention):

- 74 patients with type 2 diabetes (56% female) aged 57.4 ± 8.0 years with mean BMI 31.2 ± 4.2 kg/m² and mean waist circumference 105.4 ± 10.2 cm were included in the study.
- Compared with baseline, mean HbA1c levels at 6 months were 5 mmol/mol lower (SD=10, $p < 0.001$) and the number of participants with HbA1c levels ≤ 53 mmol/mol after intervention had increased (from 36% (n=26/72) to 60% (n=43/72)).
- At baseline, 90% of participants were taking at least one type of glucose lowering medication.

At 6 months, 49% (n=35/72) of the participants had reduced their medication or eliminated it completely (13%).

- Secondary outcomes were significantly lower fasting glucose levels (-1.2 ± 2.6 mmol/L), body weight (-4.9 ± 5.1 kg), BMI (-1.70 ± 1.69 kg/m²) and waist circumference (-9.4 ± 5.0 cm).

Plasma lipids remained unchanged except for a decrease in triglyceride levels. Furthermore, self-reported quality of life was significantly higher while experienced fatigue and sleep problems were significantly lower.

This pilot study showed that a 6-month multicomponent group-based program in a routine care setting could improve glycaemic control and reduced the use of glucose lowering medication in motivated T2D diabetics. These were the studies' main objectives. Other unforeseen outcomes, as experienced fatigue and sleep problems were significantly lower. Not reported in the study, but in participant experience stories VL noticed and heard a lot of other, non-foreseen, health benefits. For example, less burden of psoriasis and a favourable effect on renal function. About additional benefits as were seen in patients, and reported by patients can be accessed at the website of the VL best practice <https://reverseddiabetes2now.com>.

Results after 24 months (the end of the intervention):

- 234 participants provided information on glucose lowering medication and HbA1c ('responders'). 67% of the responders used less glucose lowering medications, and 28% ceased all of them. Notably, 71% of insulin users at baseline (n=47 of 66 insulin users) were off insulin at 24 months.

- Mean HbA1c levels were similar at 24 months compared with baseline (55.6 ± 12.8 vs. 56.3 ± 10.5 mmol/mol, $p=0.43$), but more responders had HbA1c levels ≤ 53 mmol/mol at 24 months (53% vs 45% at baseline).
- Furthermore, triglyceride levels (-0.34 ± 1.02 mmol/L, $p=0.004$), body weight (-7.0 ± 6.8 kg, $p<0.001$), waist circumference (-7.9 ± 8.2 cm, $p<0.001$), body mass index (-2.4 ± 2.3 kg/m², $p<0.001$) and total cholesterol/high-density lipoprotein (HDL) ratio (-0.22 ± 1.24 , $p=0.044$) were lower, while HDL ($+0.17 \pm 0.53$ mmol/L, $p<0.001$) and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels ($+0.18 \pm 1.06$ mmol/L, $p=0.040$) were slightly higher.
- No differences were observed in fasting glucose or total cholesterol levels. Quality of life and self-reported health significantly improved.

This study indicates that VL best practice shows robust, durable real-life benefits of the lifestyle group intervention. Still after up to 24 months of follow-up, positive effects remain, particularly in terms of medication use, body weight and quality of life in type 2 diabetes patients.

Efficiency Extent to which (monetary and non-monetary) inputs were used to achieve desired outcomes.

The cost-effectiveness of treatments for type 2 diabetes is often calculated based on diabetes models such as the United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS) Outcomes model. A 2016 review looked at the consistency between improved blood glucose and health outcomes across models using 76 studies⁵. Based on this, the author has put together a model to calculate QALYs based on changes in HbA1c, BMI, blood pressure and total cholesterol. The model gives an indication of the possible benefit of an intervention based on QALYs. Using this model for the Reverse Diabetes2Now results shows a QALY gain between 0.5 and 0.7 at 12 months and 0.6 and 0.7 at 24 months. The results show that the QALY gains of the treatment are significant. Assuming a reference value of € 20,000 per QALY, cost-effective treatment is achieved if the costs of the treatment are lower than € 12,000 to € 14,000. In a scaled-up version, the costs for the treatment are between € 1,000 and € 2,500. The treatment is then very cost-effective. Figure 3 shows the QALY gain for the total group and for subgroups after 12 and 24-months.

⁵ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27873225/>

Fig. 3. VL best practice and QALY gain

Evidence-base The strength and validity of evidence used to develop or evaluate the intervention.

Before the start of the first pilot program in 2014, evidence had been gathered about the potential effects of lifestyle interventions⁶.

Several lifestyle intervention studies showed promising effects in diabetes type 2 patients. For example, the DiRECT study and the VirtaHealth trial demonstrated a 46%–64% remission rate of diabetes type 2 after 2 years. However, both DiRECT (very low-calorie meal replacement) and Virta (nutritional ketosis) interventions require radical changes of food consumption. Still, several other RCT studies in the period from 2002 till 2014 showed that other lifestyle intervention could also improve glycaemic control, evaluating more modest changes in one or two lifestyle components, yielded long-term (9 months to 4 years) benefits in type 2 diabetes. Secondly, an intensive lifestyle intervention was associated with higher odds of partial remission of type 2 diabetes compared with diabetes support and education. Thirdly, compared with diabetes counselling and education, participants who participated in an

⁶ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11832527/>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15220230/>

<https://bmcpimcare.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1471-2296-12-95>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23288372/>

intensive lifestyle intervention had fewer hospitalisations, medications and lower healthcare costs over 10 years.

Equity Extent to which the intervention reduced inequalities in society.

Equity in the sense of level of impact of VL best practice across socioeconomic strata

People in lower socioeconomic groups are more likely to be overweight and be exposed to other important behavioural risk factors. Greater efforts, and an extensive lifestyle program as Reverse Diabetes2 Now targeting modifiable behavioural risk factors, also among disadvantaged groups (with low socioeconomic status) can play an important role in promoting healthier lifestyles, offering individuals better choices, and reducing health inequalities.

Educational status of people who followed the program was:

- 27% of participants are lower educated
- 29% of participants are middle educated
- 42% of participants are higher educated

Percentage of people who were able to lower or cease their glucose medication at 24 months was the highest in the subgroup with a low education status (49% lowered medication and 30% ceased medication). In that way, the reduction of inequalities is at some level reduced in society between low and high educated people and its impact on healthcare costs overall and personal.

Equity in access and utilization of health care (program use)

Inequalities in access to health care (in this case: the lifestyle program) exist across different socio-demographic groups, including sex, age, geographic area and socio-economic status. For this, financial and non-financial reasons exist. Regarding financial reasons, biggest part of program is financed by health insurance coverage by most of the health insurers; and the contribution depends on the income of the patient. For example, in the Rotterdam project the municipality reimbursed the program for people with low-income. Non-financial reasons are tackled by inclusive campaigns, and online program made it possible to overcome a geographic barrier. Namely, as a respond to COVID pandemics, an online program was developed which makes it possible for people from across the Netherlands to participate, and the need to travel to a location is no longer a barrier.

Coverage Extent to which the intervention reached the whole target population.

The program has so far reached 3,700 participants. In the Netherlands there are around 1 million people with diabetes type 2 (6% of the Dutch population). About 0,4% of the population with diabetes type 2 has followed the Reverse Diabetes2 Now program. More than 600 healthcare professionals have attended training about diabetes reversal and the program. The group reached directly is small but the education program for healthcare providers has played an important role increasing acceptance of the role of diabetes in reversing type 2 diabetes. This is seen through the increase in patient referrals from healthcare professionals that have taken part in the education program.

VL has also written a handbook on the process to reduce medication on diabetes patients together with a well-known diabetes education institute in the Netherlands and the Doctors and Lifestyle organisation, an organisation for healthcare professionals interested in lifestyle that was co-founded by VL and operates as an independent organisation.

Funding mechanisms

A chronological summary of funding mechanism for VL best practice is reported here:

- 2014: 10 participants - The program was initially funded with a grant from the Dutch government and got funding for making a documentary - available on YouTube, access [here](#).
- VGZ (health care insurance), a Dutch insurer funded a pilot program for 70 people and in recent years additional insurers have reimbursed the program.
- VL gained an award followed by a financial support plan
 - 2017: 450 participants
 - 2018: 600 participants
 - 2019: 750 participants
- In those three years VL contacted other health care insurances to gain funding for the program.
- From 1 January 2023 the version of the program for pre-diabetes and patients using metformin is included in the standard Dutch insurance program. From 1 January 2024 the program is also available for patients on sulfonylurea-derivatives and insulin within the standard Dutch insurance program.

3. 1. 3. Characteristics of implementation process

The results are informed by outcomes of CFIR-informed focus group and in semi-structured interviews. Data is grouped and shown using predetermined implementation research framework CFIR in Tables 8 to 12 showing key constructs per each domain including justification. Most relevant key constructs per domain were chosen based on the previous understanding of VL best practice. Analysis regarding individual characteristics of sustainability will be reported elsewhere.

3. 1. 3. 1. Intervention characteristics (CFIR domain 1)

Voeding Leeft was established 12 years ago with a clear vision to advocate for a lifestyle as medicine approach in the management of type 2 diabetes, to support its uptake at the level of general practitioners and to make it easily accessible to patients with type 2 diabetes in the Netherlands by embedding the program into Dutch basic insurance package. The VL best practice was developed based on strong scientific data suggesting positive results of lifestyle interventions in type 2 diabetes management⁷ and extensive experience of several health and nutrition experts working in the field. A significant characteristic of the practice implementation process was its gradual development, starting in 2014 with establishment of a multidisciplinary team (practitioner, nurse, dietitian and a coach) and a first group of 10 type 2 diabetes⁸ patients (costs covered by patients themselves) involved in the program. Focusing on nutrition, the program already showcased positive results in the participants' self-management of type 2 diabetes and reduction in medication use⁹. This was an encouraging moment for the practice developers, especially when observing a shift in program participants' lives and mindsets: *"People were getting their life back and they were behind the wheel themselves again. The wheel of life!"* In the next step, practice was scaled up with support of the government to 75 patient participants divided into four groups while monitoring and evaluation mechanisms were put in place to measure the effectiveness of the program. Simultaneously, VL as an organisation was being established and new dietitians and nurses were included in the training program. Due to its success, the VL practice was awarded a three-year (2015-17) contract from the Dutch innovation budget and the provided funding

⁷ <https://nutrition.bmj.com/content/early/2020/08/17/bmjnph-2020-000081>

⁸ T2D was chosen as an appropriate field of application due to extensive research data available at the time.

⁹ <https://nutrition.bmj.com/content/2/1/43>

enabled the participation of approximately 1900 new patients during this time. An important intervention characteristic is to provide diabetes education to participants in groups as it increases peer support, motivation, mutual responsibility/commitment, and potential for behaviour change.

Table 8 - Characteristics of the intervention, key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Intervention source	VL practice was internally developed, but outside support (networks of physicians and funding organisations/health authorities) was needed to scale up the practice and increase accessibility for patients.
Evidence Strength & Quality	Quality and validity of evidence supports the belief that the practice has desired outcomes.
Relative advantage	VL best practice is the only practice in the Netherlands that introduces lifestyle intervention in the field of type 2 diabetes education.
Adapatability	VL practice operates successfully in different local settings with specific contextual features (including outside Netherlands: India, Hong Kong). Its focus is on adaptability, both contextual (different settings) and situational (e.g. adaptations due to COVID-19 pandemics).
Trialability	The practice was first tested on a small scale in the organization, and is able to reverse/change course (implementation) if warranted.
Complexity	The intervention addresses the complex and multidimensional nature of type 2 diabetes management and lifestyle changes by focusing on nutrition, exercise, sleep and stress reduction. Program includes a multidisciplinary team and is available in both face-to-face and online format.
Cost	Initially, costs of the first (pilot) program were covered by participants, in the next step through Dutch innovation budget, between 2017 and 2022 with contracts directly with a number of Dutch insurers, and since January 1 st 2023 the program is covered for low complexity patients through basic insurance package. From 1st Jan 2024 the process with Dutch health authorities will be complete to expand the coverage to high complexity patients.

3. 1. 3. 2. Outer setting (CFIR domain 2)

Continuous networking with stakeholders outside of the organisation is a crucial aspect of practice development and implementation, including its expansion to new settings and its increase in accessibility to the program for the patients. From the very beginning, VL practice representatives have been involved in networking activities with variety of stakeholders' groups, such as Healthcare Groups (of physicians)¹⁰, nurses, scientists, specialists, patient federations, government and health insurers to increase awareness about the program and lifestyle medicine approach in diabetes education. As observed, there is an overall proclivity towards resistance against systemic change, however, in each organisation there are champions, the "points of light" as referred to by respondents that supported and are still supporting the practice implementation and its expansion. Specially important when communicating with the outside stakeholders is to showcase the data reflecting the positive clinical outcomes of the intervention and to 'use' the first patients as ambassadors or pioneers "to tell the story to their own doctor". Additional driver for involvement of health professionals (nurses specifically) is the obtainment of accreditation points, if they participate in the VL training program. A two hour online training where health professionals are informed about; the program, in depth physiology and how to support the patient during and after participation. Overall, there is a shift in perception about lifestyle medicine in Dutch healthcare, gaining a wider recognition in the last five years which helped to build trust into the program. Significant efforts were put into communication with health authorities to acquire funding. The goal was to embed the practice into the Dutch healthcare system through basic insurance package which would provide coverage to both low and high complexity patients¹¹. This has been a long still ongoing process (5 years) involving complex procedures and interactions with decision-making organisations to check practice eligibility in terms of scientific rigour, appropriateness, costs etc. It is important to note that economics of implementing lifestyle interventions is complex and may be location specific. While national health authorities and institutes are more interested in the program effectiveness, the insurers' focus is more on reducing costs of disease management (e.g. reducing or postponing insulin use) but are less interested in long-term costs (due to dialysis, blindness, amputation and reduced quality of life).

¹⁰ In the Netherlands, Healthcare Groups represent the bodies of general practitioners operating at primary level and include 50 practices on average. These groups are important stakeholders when seeking support for implementation of health-related interventions.

¹¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9106317/>

Table 9 - Outer setting: key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Patient Needs & Resources	Patient needs are considered through motivational interviews and continuous discussion during the program. Online program was developed during COVID-19 pandemics to increase accessibility.
Cosmopolitanism	Organisation is well connected to outside stakeholders, including Healthcare Groups (of physicians), nurses, scientists, specialists, patient federations, government and health insurers. Experience with pilots in Hong Kong and India suggests that the practice is translatable to settings outside the Dutch healthcare system.
External Policy & Incentives	Program is included in the Dutch basic insurance package for low complexity patients. Program was developed and is monitored in collaboration with the advisory board.

3. 1. 3. 3. Inner setting (CFIR domain 3)

Within VL best practice, significant characteristics are its multidisciplinary nature, involving people from various professional backgrounds to cover comprehensive lifestyle interventions and manage the broad scope of the program, and its focus on culture, networking, communication, and patient-centeredness. The organisational structure consists of VL management team, VL training team, Scientific council and Core program team at VL that manage various aspects of the program. Internal communication has been recognized as one of the most important success factors of the implementation. There is continuous exchange of information and experiences between the front-line professionals, program coordinators, scientists and management with a focus to adapt and evolve the program according to the emergent needs. Investing in capacity building of people's knowledge has been at the forefront of the intervention, specifically through Train-the trainers program and iterative process of communication with the frontline professionals. In terms of communicating with the patient participants, respondents have emphasized the importance of creating the safe environment where people can speak about their problems, express their beliefs and give honest opinions about the program which became an important aspect of the evaluation and monitoring process of the program.

Table 10 - Inner setting: key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Networks & Communications	The organization has a well established communication process between VL management team, VL training team, Scientific council and Core program team, including networks with frontline professionals and participants of the program.
Culture	The organization fosters culture of collaboration, learning, and patient-centered care.
Implementation Climate	There is significant support for the practice implementation across the organization and frontline professionals involved in the program.
Compatibility	There is a high degree of tangible fit between meaning and values attached to the intervention with the norms and values of involved individuals managing the practice. The practice isn't disruptive to the workflow of the organization.
Goals & Feedback	Goals are clearly communicated, acted upon, and aligned with the staff.
Learning Climate	Continuous learning and improvement are encouraged within the intervention team (see domain V Process).
Leadership Engagement	Leadership plays a role in supporting and promoting the intervention.
Access to Knowledge & Information	Knowledge and information are continuously available and shared with the teams.

3. 1. 3. 4. Characteristics of individuals (CFIR domain 4)

There is a strong recognition and shared perspective of the practice members about the relevancy of the lifestyle medicine philosophy in diabetes management and about importance of wider systemic change in general. This shared belief is achieved through continuous communication, train-the-trainers program as a transformative process for the staff working at the frontline and strong data that suggests the effectiveness of the program in terms of clinical outcomes and participants' overall satisfaction. An important factor is also the fact that the intervention was internally developed and not imposed from the outside, which increases a sense of shared ownership. Team members also believe that they have an impact on practice development, by sharing their experiences and provide suggestions for improvements. Communication is clear and accessible to stakeholders involved, open-mindedness and innovation thinking are respected and valued. Intervisions are provided to the team members

(online and on location), including webinars and VL Caffee to enable exchange of ideas and facilitate self-reflection. Members of the practice exhibit a high degree of passion about the lifestyle medicine approach in diabetes management and organisational goals and value self-reflective, patient, honest communication between people involved.

Table 11 - Characteristics of individuals: key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Knowledge & Beliefs about the Intervention	There is an overall recognition of the importance of lifestyle medicine philosophy in diabetes management and education among individuals from VL.
Self-efficacy	Self-reflection in achieving implementation goals are valued and supported through several processes (online and face-to-face interventions, 'VL Cafe' (Meet-ups), webinars and trainings) among individuals from VL.
Individual Identification with Organization	Individuals from VL exhibit a strong and passionate commitment to the goals of the organization and believe they have an impact on practice development.

3. 1. 3. 5. Process (CFIR domain 5)

Clear protocols are established for providing training course to the frontline professionals (nurses, dietitians, coaches) that work with the participants. Professionals that attend the training course acquire the accreditation points from the Dutch health authorities which is a strong incentive for their involvement. The program for type 2 diabetes patients itself follows a structured process, including an intensive 6-month program and a post-program support. The content for each phase of the program is standardised. There are differences in the program implementation based on the participants involved (low vs high complexity type 2 diabetes patients) and its format (online vs. face-to-face). Participants are included in the program with the support of their GPs who are also their medical supervisors. A comprehensive evaluation and monitoring approach are in place to facilitate self-reflection of VL practice members, obtain relevant clinical data and survey results from the health professionals, follow everyday experiences of patients, develop learnings and make improvements to the program. VL also developed a scoring system to measure if the positive changes in blood glucose levels (periodically, after 3, 6, 12, 18 and 24 months) have been achieved. Health professionals share these results individually with the participant and discuss possible adjustments in disease management. There is a strong focus on communication with GP networks, nurses, insurers and national health authorities. Patient engagement is also key,

participating in regular assessments and feedback. Periodically, VL team meets with a group of patient participants to converse about and analyse their experiences with the program (e.g. experiences with using the online platform and attending the program, their motivation after the program, suggestions for future improvements etc.). Patients also have the opportunity to pose questions and engage in discussions at the online platform of the practice or face-to-face. VL practice members emphasize the importance of enabling the participants to be in control of their own processes in lifestyle change also when interacting with their physicians and nurses. A significant emphasis is put on practice adaptability and flexibility. For example, the online version of the program has been developed due to COVID-19 pandemics while still maintaining the program's focus on group dynamics and interactions under the changed conditions. There is also a strong emphasis on increasing accessibility of the program to the type 2 diabetes patients across Netherlands. Therefore, VL has been involved in the extensive process of including the program into the Dutch basic insurance package. Since beginning of 2023, this has been achieved for low complexity patients with prospects of expanding the access also to high complexity patients in 2024. Accessibility is being achieved also by introducing the practice into different urban and rural settings across Netherlands and through the possibility of attending the program online (with no specific technical requirements needed apart from participants owning a computer and having access to internet).

Table 12 - Process: key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Planning	There are clear protocols in place to implement the practice, including the provision of training to the frontline professionals. Organisational planning approach is practical and flexible.
Engaging	Attracting and involving appropriate individuals in the implementation is very important, including networks of health professionals, staff, national health authorities, patient participants. Within the program, patient participants and frontline professionals are continuously engaged through various mechanisms.
Formally Appointed Internal Implementation Leaders	Roles within the organization and in terms of program implementation are clearly defined.
Champions	There are continuous efforts to identify and empower champions ("points of light") within and outside of the organization to overcome indifference or resistance that the intervention may provoke at different levels of operation.

Reflecting & Evaluating	Continuous quantitative and qualitative feedback about the progress and quality of implementation of VL practice is in place, accompanied with regular personal and team debriefing about progress and experience.
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3. 1. 4. Context characteristics including minimum maturity requirements

The results are arising from the SCIROCCO Maturity Model approach that was closely followed, for details please see Annex I.

Results include individual spider diagrams that showcase individual perceptions about the importance of each of the 12 dimensions when it comes to future successful implementation and a joint diagram that shows the frequency of scores provided per each dimension of the context. The individual SCIROCCO assessments of the importance of SCIROCCO maturity dimensions of the context are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Individual SCIROCCO assessments of the importance of SCIROCCO maturity dimensions, spider diagrams

The 8 spider diagrams provide the quick detection of different perceptions among respondents, consisting multi-disciplinary team, and at the same time representing the variety of (professional) backgrounds. Diversity in individual scoring can be attributed to the differences in how individuals experience the implementation process based on their unique positions and roles within the practice and also to the differences in understanding the scope and true meaning of each specific dimension. Detailed collection of individual scores and justifications from all Individual SCIROCCO assessments are presented as tables in Attachment II of Annex I. The individual results provided the basis for conducting the consensus-building workshop with the participants to reach the agreement.

To facilitate the understanding of commonalities and differences among individual assessments of each SCIROCCO dimension, including the frequency of scoring per dimension, the individual scores were included in a joint spider diagram, presented in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Individual SCIROCCO assessments shown in a joint spider diagram

The scores and justifications from the individual assessments were used as a basis for the SCIROCCO consensus-building workshop convened on February 3rd 2023 with same respondents that participated in the individual assessments. One additional representative of VL (NW, Research Coordinator) participated in the workshop. Each dimension was discussed within the group against individual assessment results.

At the areas where the consensus has not been reached, consensus-building process was needed to review the outcomes of the individual assessments and reach the agreement, including suggestions for the future improvements. It is of importance, that during the consensus process there was a tension among what is needed as a minimum to start, or when setting standards for the program, or what is perceived as optimal for potential future implementer. The final result of assessment of the context is based on consensus-scoring of SCIROCCO dimensions, showing the relative importance of maturity requirements, is shown as spider diagram, please see Fig 6. Respondents also defined three key maturity requirements of the context needed for successful translation of the VL best practice to new settings, presented in Table 13.

Fig. 6. Consensus-based scoring on SCIROCCO maturity requirements, spider diagram

Key contextual SCIROCCO dimensions for successful VL implementation are readiness to change, evaluation methods and continuous capacity building, please see Table 13 for details.

Table 13 - Key contextual SCIROCCO dimensions for successful VL best practice implementation including justification

KEY CONTEXTUAL REQUIREMENTS
Readiness to change
Justifications: There was a common agreement that being open for change is key when implementing new programs such as VL best practice that addresses the problem of type 2 diabetes in healthcare in the face of increasing costs and

uprising number of patients. The switch in health care has already been made with increasing attention for prevention. What one of the participants of the workshop pointed out was that there has to be a lot of patience and understanding that this is a slow, long run process, that maybe doesn't show results quickly, but with a strong team and cooperation with stakeholders, who are also ready to change, it is a promising start.

Quotes:

"The authorities are at first turn benevolent and do not see the need for change. The system is not set up to change. Through the information and studies, we provide over the years, movement is slowly coming. The whole process takes years and slowly there seems to be a slight sense of urgency" (BK, Program director).

"In the healthcare environment needs to be recognition for the urgency of the problem. That is, the increase in costs and raising number of people with diabetes type 2. Which makes healthcare quality, sustainability and affordable impossible in the future. Recognition that there needs to be a different approach in healthcare. Instead of symptom control to solving the cause. Creating willingness and openness for a new, different approach - to lifestyle medicine. It's the most necessary part for the implementation of the pilot. From that point, in the next phases vision and strategy can be developed" (MB, Program coordinator).

Evaluations methods

Justifications: All the members uniformly supported the importance of evaluation that VL carries out at three levels; (1) perspective of the patients, (2) clinical outcomes of the patients, (3) and perspectives of health professionals who carry out the training course. Based on these different types of data, they were improving the program over the years.

Quotes:

"In the determination of the successfulness, evaluation needs to be existent in the health care context" (MB, Project coordinator).

"It is key: collecting data and evaluating, and make use of the learnings from these evaluations enough" (EC, Director data)

"Only by collecting data you can improve the program. It is also very helpful in the financial discussion" (NZ, General Practitioner).

Capacity building

Justifications: In order for the program to work most effectively, the respondents were convinced that a lot of work and effort needs to be put into the operation of the team that implements the program. For this reason, regular team training takes place, both before and during the implementation of the training course.

Quotes:

"In the first pilot phases, learnings on a small scale for the implementers is first priority" (MB, program coordinator).

"Within the programme there is significant capacity building - training of nurses and doctors" (EC, director data).

"We stay up to date with information about the development in the field. We train our own staff" (MH, medical team).

"If this is the case it would be excellent. In Hong Kong we experienced that the trained team was too small and it depended to much on these people who were not able to continue the program on their own" (NZ, GP).

3.1.5. Conclusions and main recommendations

Based on the self-described development of the objectives of VL best practice (**chapter 3.1.1.**), already as a simple narrative presents the high importance of the vision, goal, purpose and aim of the best practice, which will be followed in this project.

While describing core features of VL best practice (**chapter 3.1.2.**), members of VL were also asked to reflect on main barriers and facilitators they encountered (please see Table 14), as well as lessons learnt and their recommendations for C4D pilot countries (please see Table 15). In addition, they were specifically asked on how they were/are solving problems, please see Box 3.

Table 14 - Main barriers and facilitators, VL narrative

Main barriers	Main facilitators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sceptical attitude and lack of knowledge of healthcare professionals working in the field about the potential to reverse type 2 diabetes with a lifestyle intervention • Financial barriers • Identifying and recruiting participants • Brand and product awareness • Growth of similar initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing quantity of research about reversing type 2 diabetes with lifestyle interventions • Finding a team willing to work based on emerging research and patient results • Learning from own mistakes • Developing online skills of the team and the organisation • Identifying innovative funding sources for initial pilots, such as family foundations, government grants and innovation funding stream of health insurance company

Table 15 - Lessons learnt and recommendations for C4D pilot countries, VL narrative

Lessons learnt	Recommendations for C4D pilot countries
Assure patients' safety in medication adjustments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before the start of the program VL medical team discusses the medication adjustments with the patient's GP or internal medicine specialist. During the program there is regular contact between the healthcare professional, patient and medical team in the progress of medication reduction. • During the treatment blood glucose levels are measured frequently and medication is adjusted in line with blood glucose levels • VL strictly informs the patient's healthcare professional about the progress and results • VL has an education program for healthcare professionals to support patients in the appropriate way after finishing the program
Connect with the healthcare system for patient recruitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify HC professionals within the existing healthcare system who are willing to engage with VL based on existing research and reported

Lessons learnt	Recommendations for C4D pilot countries
	<p>patient experience from VL best practice and can refer patients to the program</p>
<p>Use the power of the group dynamics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take time to check if a participant is able to participate in a group program • use community resources to increase the connection between the participants • build a safe environment within the group so that participants can openly share experiences
<p>Pathophysiology of insulin resistance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take time for people to understand the pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes including time to process the knowledge. Make the information easy to understand including explaining the “why” behind the steps in the program. • Learning by knowledge, by experience and by “just doing it”. • Don’t use words such as diet. It’s a lifelong change in lifestyle.
<p>Preparation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that all necessary processes are clear before the start of each pilot program. Think about the patient flow, recruitment, medical safety, and all preparations for the program.

Box 3. An approach VL uses to solve the problems, VL narrative

VL team has developed guidelines and protocols for all aspects of the program, where the problem might occur, such as participant inclusion, organisation of the program including program days and medical protocols (and will be shared with C4D pilot countries). For example, to keep the quality of the program, an improvement cycle is being used; and there is a clear cycle to report incidents to ensure medical safety. All teams work closely together to maintain the quality of the program, for example by having a meeting before program days to prepare and having a de-brief after program days. Complex patients are also discussed within the team. Monthly interventions, webinars, training and education are in place to keep the team up to date on the latest (scientific) knowledge, discuss cases, support and personal development. There is always medical back-up for the core program teams working on the ground. The medical team consists of an internist and two family doctors who are available if there are medical incidents. The necessity depends on the complexity of patients included. VL also has protocols and systems for secure reporting of (medical) incidents, in line with national legislation and requirements.

Based on deeper insights into what are the characteristics of the implementation process (using CFIR approach, **chapter 3.1.3.**) and minimum maturity characteristics of the context (using SCIROCCO framework, **chapter 3.1.4.**), further conclusions and recommendations can be drawn.

For C4D pilot countries, the most important conclusions and recommendations are coming from the studies on implementation process (**chapter 3.1.3.**). Key characteristics, supporting successful implementation, are related to the intervention itself, to outer and inner setting and to characteristics of individuals related to VL best practice, supported by various processes. Lessons learnt are presented in Table 15.

Table 16 - Summary of key characteristics of the implementation process, using CFIR approach

Domain	Description
Intervention characteristics	VL best practice was internally developed with strong support of a wide variety of outside stakeholders. Unique to the Dutch context, it addresses the complex and multidimensional nature of type 2 diabetes management based on lifestyle intervention by focusing on nutrition, exercise, sleep and stress reduction. It includes a multidisciplinary team of experts and is available in both face-to-face and online format. The practice operates successfully in different local settings within and outside Netherlands. Coverage is provided by the Dutch health insurance package (for low complexity patients) and through private insurers (for high complexity patients).
Outer setting	Patient needs and views are continuously considered through interactions with patient federations and program participants. The practice is adaptable to meet patient needs and increase accessibility. Organization is continuously engaged to outside stakeholders, including Healthcare Groups (of physicians), nurses, scientists, specialists, patient federations, government and health insurers. Program is aligned with national policies and funding frameworks.
Inner setting	The organizational structure supports continuous information flow between VL management team, VL training team, Scientific council and Core program team, including frontline professionals and participants of the program. There is significant support for the practice implementation across the organization and frontline professionals involved in the program. Goals are clearly communicated, acted upon, and aligned with the staff. Continuous learning and improvement are encouraged within the intervention team.

<p>Characteristics of individuals</p>	<p>There is an overall recognition of the importance of lifestyle medicine philosophy in diabetes management and education among individuals from VL. Self-reflection in achieving implementation goals are valued and supported through several processes (online and face-to-face interventions, 'VL Caffee', webinars and trainings). Individuals exhibit a strong and passionate commitment to the goals of the organization and believe they have an impact on practice development.</p>
<p>Process</p>	<p>There are clear protocols in place to implement the practice, including the provision of training to the frontline professionals. During the program, patient participants and frontline professionals are continuously engaged through various mechanisms. There are continuous efforts to identify and empower champions ("points of light") within and outside of the organization to overcome indifference or resistance that the intervention may provoke at different levels of operation. Continuous quantitative and qualitative feedback about the progress and quality of implementation is in place, accompanied with regular personal and team debriefing about progress and experience.</p>

Main successes and challenges, arising from the in-depth study of VL practice using CFIR approach, are available in Table 17.

Table 17 - Main successes and challenges of VL best practice, identified using CFIR approach

Main successes	Main challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a comprehensive program for people with type 2 diabetes based on lifestyle medicine approach that addresses the multidimensional nature of diabetes (self) management. • Inclusion of the program into the Dutch basic insurance package for low complexity patients since 2023, with important steps made towards expanding the coverage for high complexity patients as well. • Development of an online based program with comparable outcomes to the face-to-face version and increased accessibility to the program. • Continuous focus on engagement and networking with internal and external stakeholders involved (managers, program coordinators, scientists, decision-makers, patient participants) with a vision to improve and scale-up the practice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistances at various levels of healthcare system when communicating about the importance and impact of lifestyle medicine approach in type 2 diabetes management and expanding the program to new settings. • Hesitation on part of the private insurers to fund the program being motivated by the short term savings (e.g. reduction of insulin use) instead of long-term decrease in overall burden of disease (e.g. of chronic complications such as retinopathy and diabetic foot) and increased quality of life. • COVID-19 pandemic which was mitigated to an extent by developing an online-based program but is appropriate only for low complexity patients. • Access to people with lower socio-economic status remains one of the more important challenges. VL is engaged with the University students in research on how to facilitate the access to the intervention by this population.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translation and adaptation of the program into settings outside Netherlands, namely Hong Kong and India, which showcases its adaptability in significantly different cultural contexts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients might not be aware of the program’s existence and the ways to access it.. Additionally, the caregivers might not advice their patients to join the program, so significant efforts are made to communicate with the general practices and Healthcare Groups (of physicians) to increase the awareness about its existence.
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Based on the analysis of VL best practice implementation experience, several recommendations and key messages for successful implementation within C4D can be drawn:

Table 18 – Key messages for future implementers, based on CFIR approach

Key messages for successful implementation process within C4D	
Guiding questions to facilitate self-reflection of the team throughout implementation process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ WHAT is your long-term goal? Do you want to embed the program in the healthcare system or run it in parallel? ✓ WHO is implementing the program and WHO can you work with? ✓ WHO are the parties? (stakeholders, “points of light”) ✓ WHAT is the diabetes patients association’s position in your country? ✓ WHICH strategies work for you? ✓ WHAT do you already have or what you could have?
General advice for the implementers in C4D	<p>Proceed step-by-step, go forward when you understand your needs and existent resources. Remain adjustable, flexible and open to opportunity.</p> <p>Showcase a strong 'business case' as good story sells. Have that in mind when getting funding after the project ends.</p> <p>Keep good relationships with stakeholders; showcase results continuously.</p> <p>Continuous Education of staff is key, but especially important at the beginning.</p> <p>Recommended staff to be included at the very start of practice development are a nurse & dietitian.</p>

The in-depth understanding of VL best practice also identifies key characteristics of the context (based on SCIROCCO framework, chapter 3.1.4.), that support successful future

implementation within C4D. Further details on favourable characteristics of the context are given in Table 19.

Table 19 - Key favourable contextual characteristics for successful VL best practice implementation, based on SCIROCCO framework

Readiness to change
If the existing systems of care need to be re-designed to provide C4D pilot practices approach within countries, this will require change across many levels, the creation of new roles, processes and working practices, and new systems to support information sharing and collaboration across care teams. This will be disruptive and may be viewed negatively by workers, press and public, so a clear case needs to be made for those changes, including a justification, a strategic plan, and a vision of better care.
Evaluation methods
As new approaches (such as care pathways and services) are introduced to support care aligned to C4D pilot practices, there is a clear need to ensure that the changes are having the desired effect on quality of care, cost of care, access and citizen experience. This supports the concept of evidence-based investment, where the impact of each change is evaluated, e.g. by health economists working in universities or in special agencies. Health technology assessment is an important method here and can be used to justify the cost of scaling up the C4D pilot practice to regional or national level.
Capacity building
Capacity building is the process by which individual and organisations obtain, improve and retain the skills and knowledge needed to do their jobs competently. As the systems of care are transformed, many new roles will need to be created and new skills developed. These will range from technological expertise and project management, to successful change management. The systems of care need to become “learning systems” that are constantly striving to improve quality, cost and access. They must build their capacity so as to become more adaptable and resilient. As demands continue to change, skills, talent and experience must be retained. This means ensuring that knowledge is captured and used to improve the next set of projects, leading to greater productivity and increasing success.

In conclusion, key characteristics of implementation process are identified within intervention itself, in outer and in inner setting, as characteristics of individuals and within the process. These provide main roadmap to lead C4D pilot practices design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and have a formative impact during Plan-Do-Study-Act cycles within C4D. Main successes and challenges provide insight into how VL best practice reflects on itself, how much they were successful based on their primary goals and purposes. Irrespective of different current contexts within C4D pilot countries, some general lessons learned were identified including the advice on continuous reflection process. Main favourable characteristics of the context, that is supportive to future C4D implementation are readiness to change, evaluation to support evidence-based investment, and capacity building (“learning systems”).

3. 2. Situation analysis of national/regional and local contexts including main stakeholders

Understanding of the relevant contexts within C4D pilot countries at national or regional level as well as at local level, where C4D pilot practice will be implemented, is an important baseline activity needed to develop a successful and sustainable C4D pilot practice. The positive characteristic (facilitatory) as well as negative characteristics (barriers, obstacles) need to be carefully considered when deciding at respective C4D pilot practice level which elements of VL best practice can be adopted as they are, or need to be adapted, or might not be appropriate and have to be abandoned. In addition, some elements perceived as essential for the context might need to be added.

The approach used in C4D for this activity was highly influenced by the preliminary analysis of data on in-depth review of VL best practice, such as the importance of team dynamics leading to shared values and beliefs and common goals, developing common understanding of the context and acknowledging, which characteristics are under the influence of the team (strengths and weaknesses) or outside of their reach (opportunities and threats).

The four steps of this analysis were:

- (I) defining C4D pilot local team, (preliminary) multidisciplinary team and their roles;
- (II) defining shared purpose and the common scope of the C4D pilot practice,
- (III) identifying supporting and inhibiting characteristics of the context at national/regional level and at C4D pilot level as well as defining main stakeholders and their level of involvement, and
- (IV) assessment of the identified characteristics as Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats for the C4D pilot practice implementation with re-definition of the shared purpose and the common scope of the C4D pilot practice based on those insights, if needed.

The detailed description of the methodology and the rationale can be found at Annex II. Full reports from individual countries are attached as Annex III. Situation analysis of national/local contexts including main stakeholders, per C4D pilot country. In chapter 3.2.1 and 3.2.2 we present selected elements of the analyses, across C4D pilot countries.

3.2.1. Situation analysis of national/regional and local contexts

The process of development of shared purpose and common goal of C4D pilot local teams within C4D pilot countries, across countries are shown in Table 20.

Table 20 - Purpose and scope development within C4D pilot local teams, per C4D pilot country. Differences among Step II and Step IV are marked with bold.

Country	Step II	Step IV
Belgium	<p>The aim of C4D practice is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reinforce early management of type 2 diabetes patients through an intensive program based on lifestyle changes. • Improve the health, well-being and quality of life of diabetes patients by enhancing patient's empowerment and self-efficacy. • Reduce costs associated with increased risk of disability, health-related retirement, and development of patient complications. <p>The scope of the C4D practice is to improve and promote health in Wallonia by reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and associated risk factors, both at the societal and personal level, through early management of patients with type 2 diabetes through an effective empowering lifestyle education program.</p>	<p>Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen health providers' multidisciplinary teamwork and cross-functional communication • Reinforce early management of type 2 diabetes patients through an intensive program based on lifestyle changes. • Increase social support and inclusion by encouraging patient involvement and experience sharing. • Improve the health, well-being and quality of life of patients by enhancing patient's empowerment and self-efficacy. • Reduce costs associated with increased risk of disability, health-related retirement, and development of patient complications. <p>The scope of the C4D practice is to improve and promote health in Wallonia by reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and its associated risk factors through early management of patients with type 2 diabetes in effective lifestyle education programs delivered by collaborative multidisciplinary teams.</p>
Bulgaria	<p>The aim of C4D practice in Bulgaria reflects the general objective of C4D practice: to improve and foster health in a current EU Member State by reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and related risk factors. This should happen on 2 levels simultaneously: the societal and personal one by stimulating effective lifestyle treatment and</p>	<p>The aim of the C4D practice in Bulgaria is to compensate for deficits in the training of health workers by building on the existing health education programs related to public health protection. Profiled diabetes control programs based on new learning technologies and future patient needs.</p> <p>The scope of C4D practice in Bulgaria is</p>

Country	Step II	Step IV
	<p>implementing various training programmes tailored patients' needs.</p> <p>In addition, C4D practice can serve a valuable opportunity in Bulgarian context to reproduce successful practices of coordination between multidisciplinary regional expert team and central administrative structure both engaged in promotion of healthy lifestyle and raising awareness of Diabetes Type 2. By involving experts with various background we aim to strengthen the coordination between health professionals dealing with treatment of Diabetes type 2 and lifestyle practices that can further impact the course of the disease on individual level.</p> <p>The scope of the C4D practice Bulgaria is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to propose design, to check its suitability and to assess its impact; - program for patients with type 2 diabetes that is digitally supported to persuade them in the fruitfulness of healthy living; - open new unexplored fields in Bulgarian context of possible determinants of the health of persons with diabetes type 2 such as physical activity, sleep and the decrease of stress; - providing platform for interaction tete-a-tete between medical specialists and patients who are able to reunite theory and practice in regards to Diabetes type 2, - to define and select the best approaches to re-educate diabetes specialists in regional and national context, that will help them to master digital tools as well as to rely on regular live contact with the selected patients - the development of protocol and national plan for expansion of the best practices throughout the implementation of the project in order to secure sustainability on national level and to foster public dialogue on the update of national policies towards people living with diabetes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increased quality of education of health workers, which in turn will lead to better access to services designed for patients with type 2 diabetes; - to identify the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches to limit type 2 diabetes - introduction and application of new technologies to ensure optimization of services for patients with type 2 diabetes; - to use the potential of C4D to optimize type 2 diabetes policy;
Finland	<p>The aim is to develop and test a new web-based lifestyle education concept and new materials to support adoption and maintenance of healthy lifestyles for people with type 2 diabetes. Finnish Diabetes Association will set up the web-based lifestyle education course to complement their current education platform for people with diabetes. The course will be tested in a pilot action which will be conducted in cooperation with one</p>	<p>The aim and scope stayed the same as in Step II.</p>

Country	Step II	Step IV
	<p>wellbeing services county. Two consecutive pilot-groups, 20 persons with diabetes in each group will be implemented, utilizing Plan-Do-Study-Act framework to identify and resolve encountered challenges that might hinder the larger-scale adoption of the practice. The implementation process as well as the patient-level outcomes will be evaluated, as well as the costs of the implementation.</p> <p>The scope of the practice:</p> <p>Health and wellbeing of people with type 2 diabetes will improve. The new web-based lifestyle education will be implemented and scaled-up in new wellbeing services counties. The service will be largely available and easily accessible for people with type 2 diabetes in Finland.</p>	
Greece	<p>The purpose of C4D practice Greece is to increase the capacity and quality of education at secondary healthcare level including new topics, new approaches and digital tools, with an aim to increase effective lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes. In addition, C4D serves as an unique opportunity to introduce to Greek context the approaches on how to design, pilot, monitor and evaluate educational programmes for patients in general, how to design and evaluate in a formative way digitally supported educational programmes with an aim to optimise the effectiveness based on the future patient needs and availability of the human resources, and to deliver the proposal for upgrading of the existing system for training of diabetes educators and medical doctors on coaching and the use of digital solutions.</p> <p>The scope of the C4D practice Greece is</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to design, test and evaluate (using PDSA cycles), - a digitally-enhanced educational program for patients with type 2 diabetes to support their healthy life choices, delivered at secondary level of care, - that will be compatible to the organizational, professional and cultural context, existing terminology and symbols and building on the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches, and upgrading them with specific topics (physical activity, sleep and stress reduction), 	<p>The purpose of C4D practice Greece is to increase the capacity and quality of education at secondary healthcare level including new topics, new approaches and digital tools, with an aim to increase the efficiency of the existing resources in delivering effective lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes. In addition, C4D serves as an unique opportunity to introduce to Greek context the approaches on how to design, pilot, monitor and evaluate educational programmes for patients in general, how to design and evaluate in a formative way digitally supported educational programmes with an aim to optimise the effectiveness based on the future patient needs and availability of the human resources, and to deliver the proposal for upgrading of the existing system for training of diabetes educators and medical doctors on coaching and the use of digital solutions.</p> <p>The scope of the C4D practice Greece is</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to design, test and evaluate (using PDSA cycles), - a digitally-enhanced educational program for patients with type 2 diabetes to support their healthy life choices, delivered at secondary level of care, - that will be compatible to the organizational, professional and cultural context, existing terminology and symbols and building on the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches, and upgrading them with specific topics (physical activity, sleep and stress reduction),

Country	Step II	Step IV
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - by fully embracing a co-creation approach and research methodologies in social sciences, including the most recent ones, - with the optimal use of face-to-face interaction in combination with digital solutions - and to identify the approaches to increase the skills of diabetes educators, medical doctors and other healthcare professionals in areas identified (such as coaching, use of digital tools, and related to physical activity, sleep and stress reduction as topics), - and to use the potential of C4D to increase visibility of importance of education in type 2 diabetes at national level. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - by fully embracing a co-creation approach and research methodologies in social sciences, including the most recent ones, - with the optimal use of face-to-face interaction in combination with digital solution to increase the efficiency of the existent (human) resources, - and to identify the approaches to increase the skills of diabetes educators, medical doctors and other healthcare professionals in areas identified (such as coaching, use of digital tools, and related to physical activity, sleep and stress reduction as topics), - and to use the potential of C4D to increase visibility of importance of education in type 2 diabetes at national level.
Hungary	<p>Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is raising awareness in the society, increasing the participants' health-consciousness, educating them and help them in achieving a better quality of life.</p> <p>The scope of the practice is: first of all to implement a pilot project that helps the participants to achieve a better quality of life. Secondly, we would like to execute such a project of which experiences can be used later, and through the dissemination we could decrease the number of people newly diagnosed with type 2 diabetes (T2D).</p>	The aim and scope stayed the same as in Step II.
Italy	<p>The aim of C4D practice is to reduce the burden of type 2 diabetes and of its complications in overweight or obese individuals and possibly reduce medication by: increasing motivation and daily activity, improving nutrition, quality of life and social interaction, reducing body weight.</p> <p>Scope of the C4D practice is:</p> <p>Patients' perspective: to improve the quality of life of individuals with Type 2 Diabetes also in the presence of (still manageable) complications, and to increase their awareness about the disease and the role of healthy lifestyles in reducing its burden.</p> <p>Clinicians' perspective: to explore the potential role of healthier lifestyles adoption and maintenance in supporting the "reverse type 2 diabetes" paradigm; to implement a structured model of care based on previously conducted exploratory, individual attempts dealing with "consciousness of the disease and motivation to react" and with "new nutrition paradigms in diabetes"</p>	The aim and scope stayed the same as in Step II.

Country	Step II	Step IV
	Health System stakeholder: to explore a better management of type 2 diabetes through a new model of care relying on healthier lifestyles and digital health	
Malta	<p>The aim of C4D in Malta is to ameliorate the current practices in diabetes care as delivered in the local general hospitals, primary and community care in Malta. The pilot study will provide a more structured approach on diabetes care, with a programme that includes a multidisciplinary team of professionals that will in turn, highlight the need of a team of dedicated professionals to cater for such a growing population of Type 2 diabetics. C4D will also bring about updated knowledge on current practices in diabetes care in other European countries, with validated tools and practices. Thus, through the replication and adaptation of such practices, Malta will be able to deliver best practice for the wellbeing of the Maltese population. In addition, the digital platform, and other social media platforms, will provide updated and continuous support to the pilot participants. While hoping that this study will be sustainable in long term, Malta plans to replicate the study in the larger hospital in Malta and thereafter to roll out the project to include primary, secondary and community care.</p> <p>The scope of the C4D practice in Malta is based on the following;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To develop a structured approach to the care of Type 2 diabetes • To highlight the importance of a multidisciplinary team when caring for clients suffering from Type 2 diabetes • To identify the gaps in current management of Type 2 diabetes and work on ways of how to ameliorate the services using the C4D project • To identify the gaps in education for the MDT and increase their skills to provide a holistic approach • To increase the efficiency of the existing resources on diabetes through the digital platform and social media platform. • To work on providing further resources on diabetes care • To develop an action plan to be able to scale it up and deliver it in Malta's general hospital and other clinics 	The aim and scope stayed the same as in Step II.

Country	Step II	Step IV
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To use the C4D EU project to bring out the importance of optimal care of clients diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes from all aspects of care, both at personal and national level. • To empower clients to self-manage their condition which in turn will help them in making informed choices on their health • Together with the clients, to assess the individual's specific education needs, work on common goals, work on a plan and its implementation and monitor its outcome. 	
Poland	<p>The aim of C4D practice is to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - implement a good practice into the universal model of care in Poland in order to reverse treatment of type 2 diabetes by limiting pharmacotherapy in a safe and effective way through behavioral therapy, - promote a lifestyle changes that can bring improved quality of life in people with type 2 diabetes - reduce healthcare associated costs - develop and disseminate a team/multidisciplinary/comprehensive relations with patients. This will be possible only when attention is being paid to the complexity of the type2 diabetes therapies — i.e. the need to involve many specialists who will support patients in taking an active role in managing their disease and build their motivation to undertake changes. - Increase patients' wellbeing and quality of life <p>The scope of the practice is to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop an effective model of organisation of care for patients with type 2 diabetes that can be implemented in different healthcare units - train the team of multidisciplinary specialists by experts from the Dutch organisation "Voeding Leef" who will conduct a pilot program in our country, evaluate its effects and will train other specialists in order to scale this practice - prepare a recruitment strategy for C4Dpractie 	The aim and scope stayed the same as in Step II.

Country	Step II	Step IV
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop a repository of didactic materials for trainers - develop a Knowledge Exchange Platform for Patients (maintaining effects for patients participating in the program, motivation to change for new patients, support groups) - implement lifestyle interventions on the group of 40 patients with diabetes 2 (by achieving satisfactory metabolic compensation, which will allow for complete or partial abandonment of pharmacological treatment). - translate and adapt to polish environment educational materials for patients for better self-management - evaluate the pilot achievements - prepare implementation report of pilot study - present the conclusions of the pilot study carried out to the Polish Ministry of Health in order to possibly scale the described practice in our country. 	
Portugal	<p>The aim of C4D practice is to improve the clinical outcomes and quality of life of people with type 2 diabetes through the establishment and evaluation of a safe and structured European Good Practice.</p> <p>Scope of the C4D practice is to empower people with type 2 diabetes to adapt and adopt lifestyle measures, and to provide training to the healthcare teams in motivational and coaching approaches, in primary, hospital and patient association care units, to improve self-management support and care delivery.</p>	The aim and scope stayed the same as in Step II.
Slovakia	<p>Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is to improve general health conditions of population in Slovakia with focus on diabetes type 2 prevention and treatment, by reducing related risk factors and improving health of patients (healthier blood glucose levels with potential lower medication consumption) through effective lifestyle treatment and implemented programme.</p> <p>Scope of the C4D practice is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transfer of the identified best practice “Reverse Diabetes2 Now experience” from VL and implementation in Slovak 	The aim and scope stayed the same as in Step II.

Country	Step II	Step IV
	<p>conditions which includes activities such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Training of Experts ○ Training of patients ○ Implementation of effective lifestyle treatment for patients ○ Monitoring and reporting ○ Building of Evidence based on outputs and measurement 	
Slovenia	<p>The purpose of C4D practice Slovenia is to increase the capacity and quality of education at secondary healthcare level including new topics, new approaches and digital tools, with an aim to increase the efficiency of the existing resources in delivering effective lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes. In addition, C4D serves as an unique opportunity to introduce to Slovenian context the approaches on how to design, pilot, monitor and evaluate educational programmes for patients in general, how to design and evaluate in a formative way digitally supported educational programmes with an aim to optimise the effectiveness based on the future patient needs and availability of the human resources, and to deliver the proposal for upgrading of the existing system for training of diabetes educators and medical doctors on coaching and the use of digital solutions.</p> <p>Scope of the C4D practice:</p> <p>The scope of the C4D practice Slovenia is</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to design, test and evaluate (using PDSA cycles), - a digitally-enhanced educational program for patients with type 2 diabetes to support their healthy life choices, delivered at secondary level of care, - that will be compatible to the organizational, professional and cultural context, existing terminology and symbols and building on the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches, and upgrading them with specific topics (physical activity, sleep and stress reduction), - by fully embracing a co-creation approach and research methodologies in social sciences, including the most recent ones, - with the optimal use of face-to-face interaction in combination with digital solution to 	<p>The purpose of C4D practice Slovenia is to increase the capacity and quality of education at secondary healthcare level including new topics, new approaches and digital tools, with an aim to increase the efficiency of the existing resources in delivering effective lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes. In addition, C4D serves as an unique opportunity to introduce to Slovenian context the approaches on how to design, pilot, monitor and evaluate educational programmes for patients in general, how to design and evaluate in a formative way digitally supported educational programmes with an aim to optimise the effectiveness based on the future patient needs and availability of the human resources, and to deliver the proposal for upgrading of the existing system for training of diabetes educators and medical doctors on coaching and the use of digital solutions.</p> <p>The scope of the C4D practice Slovenia is</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to design, test and evaluate (using PDSA cycles), - a digitally-enhanced educational program for patients with type 2 diabetes to support their healthy life choices, delivered at secondary level of care, - that will be compatible to the organizational, professional and cultural context, existing terminology and symbols and building on the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches, and upgrading them with specific topics (physical activity, sleep and stress reduction), - by fully embracing a co-creation approach and research methodologies in social sciences, including the most recent ones, - with the optimal use of face-to-face interaction in combination with digital solution to

Country	Step II	Step IV
	<p>increase the efficiency of the existent (human) resources,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - and to identify the approaches to increase the skills of diabetes educators, medical doctors and other healthcare professionals in areas identified (such as coaching, use of digital tools, and related to physical activity, sleep and stress reduction as topics), - including development of action plan for scaling-up the educational program at national level including the permanent platform, and that will include the identified gaps related to diabetes education (competencies, approaches, topics, organisation) at micro (individual patient-HCP interaction), meso (healthcare organisation including healthcare teams) and macro level (healthcare system), - and to use the potential of C4D to increase visibility of importance of education in type 2 diabetes at national level. 	<p>increase the efficiency of the existent (human) resources,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - and to identify the approaches to increase the skills of diabetes educators, medical doctors and other healthcare professionals in areas identified (such as coaching, use of digital tools, and related to physical activity, sleep and stress reduction as topics), - including development of action plan for scaling-up the educational program at national level including the permanent digital platform (i.e. https://e-diabetes.si/), and that will include the identified gaps related to diabetes education (competencies, approaches, topics, organisation) at micro (individual patient-HCP interaction), meso (healthcare organisation including healthcare teams) and macro level (healthcare system), - and to use the potential of C4D to increase visibility of importance of education in type 2 diabetes at national level.
Spain	<p>The Spanish consortium agrees regarding the Step II questions:</p> <p><u>** What would you like to accomplish within the work of C4D?</u></p> <p>The Spanish consortium is to design a T2D pilot lifestyle intervention strategy, which would be based on therapeutic education and led by primary care nurses. The aim is to test this strategy in several primary care centers to collect data to support its subsequent scaling up as the first stage of a progressive deployment in the National Healthcare System.</p> <p>We will work on how to create a new T2D alternative treatment protocol and to improve communication between the public and private health sector in diabetes treatments.</p> <p>T2D patients demand greater involvement of healthcare professionals and the design of practical activities to identify the needs and priorities of patients with T2D.</p> <p>It is also address by the Spanish consortium how to highlight changing lifestyle habits contributes to the management of chronic diseases in general and T2D particularly, supporting the development of their decision-making skills and promoting the prevention of complications in T2D.</p> <p>In addition, the facilitating support of new educational technology and the online T2D community platform will improve communication,</p>	<p>The purpose Spanish Consortium has related to C4D are the development of the participants quality of life because of their better understanding of T2D, empowering them to a greater control of their glucose levels and glycemic control.</p> <p>Their individual awareness, to learn how to make healthier choices will reduce their medication needs and comorbidities improving selfcare. They will receive psychological support to reinforce their motivation and progress.</p> <p>Patients and professionals' bonds will be reinforced with more connection with health professionals.</p> <p>The scope of the practice for the Spanish Consortium is to stablish an effective and sustainable intervention that will be replicable and transfer inside the health system to expand to more T2D.</p> <p>It is intended to get involved all stakeholders, from individual patients to their associations, health care staff and other policy makers related to T2D so as to ensure a favourable result in the long-term maintenance of lifestyle changes and motivation.</p> <p>We count on the implementation of psychological support for all patients in the public health system as part of their regular T2D follow up.</p>

Country	Step II	Step IV
	<p>cooperative interaction among T2D participants and fluent dialogue with professionals. It also includes the learning process assessment, evaluating how behavioral changes and new attitudes towards T2D appear and to identify where to adapt, adopt, adjust or abandon according to the pilot's experiences.</p> <p>The Spanish consortium pursues to enhance the collaboration of multidisciplinary professionals as a complementary team, promoting the development of a scientific research network to support this approach effectiveness, contributing to its sustainability as part of the established health system in place.</p> <p>Finally, we will encourage collaborative interactive projects including T2D associations and different stakeholders to engage them with this project.</p> <p><u>** When C4D ends, what would you like to see as the result?</u></p> <p>After the T2D intervention program development it is expected that its participants will follow the proposed treatment and activities to improve their condition self-management, particularly related to diet and physical activity, reducing the use of their medication too. Participants would understand that their treatment success depends overall on their determining diabetes factors proper management.</p> <p>Besides, it is intended to obtain a broad and comprehensive framework on the learning process and self-care awareness, to create a new solid evidence-based treatment, and to promote self-care and the adherence to therapeutic self-management.</p> <p>The visibility and recognition of the multidisciplinary team and the widespread of the program among the population and professionals will extend to more people with T2D throughout the country and this new professional's approach will grow.</p> <p><u>** What would you like to see that would happen after C4D ends?</u></p> <p>The Spanish consortium would extend the practice and scale it up adapting to other conditions and proving its effectiveness in new different scenarios, as a solid T2D Best Practice. A stable maintenance of physiologic parameters (glycemic index, body weight, plasma lipids, blood pressure) in T2D through systematic promotion of healthy lifestyles is feasible and affordable by the Health System with the corresponding reduction of T2D patients in the respective region and in the country. That will contribute to the expansion of C4D protocol along regional and national Health Care System.</p>	<p>Quality health care services expansion and accessibility will be facilitated with the new resource's availability for face-to-face and online program development, counting on the production of educational programs for patients and health care professionals, including new technologies and medical devices arising a network for the exchange of information for patients and professionals.</p>

Country	Step II	Step IV
	<p>A general change of mentality would occur, from the political commitment, at national and local jurisdictions, to align themselves in the strategy of promotion of healthy habits perspective, self-management individual care with regulations that would enhance and facilitate this approach. Not another road to nowhere after three years of C4D Joint Action.</p> <p>Based on the exhaustive data analysis, scientific value and support to the figures would prove efficient this method, preventing avoidable costs and improving patients 'conditions at the same time.</p>	

Assignment of the roles within C4D pilot local teams, needed for efficient team work within C4D pilot countries, across countries are shown in Table 21.

Table 21 - C4D pilot local teams, per C4D pilot country

Country	Organiser	Expert	Decision maker	Other
Belgium	x	x	x	N/A
Bulgaria	x	x	N/A	N/A
Finland	x	x	x	N/A
Greece	x	x	N/A	N/A
Hungary	x	x	x	N/A
Italy	x	x	N/A	N/A
Malta	x	x	x	IT Expert
Poland	x	x	x	N/A
Portugal	x	x	N/A	N/A
Slovakia	x	x	N/A	Project manager
Slovenia	x	x	N/A	N/A
Spain	x	x	x	Senior Advisor Project manager

Note: use the following legend:

X = already defined

N/A = not applicable or not assigned yet

Representation of professional groups within (preliminary) C4D Multidisciplinary team across C4D pilot countries is shown in Table 22.

Table 22 - C4D Multidisciplinary team, per C4D pilot country

Country	Nurse	Dietitian	Medical Doctor	Coach	C4D practice coordinator	Other
Belgium	x	x	N/A	X (Coach/ Psychologist)	x	N/A
Bulgaria	x	x	x	x	x	N/A
Finland	x	x	x	x	x	N/A
Greece	x	x	x	N/A	x	Administrative role
Hungary	x	x	x	x	x	N/A
Italy	N/A	x	x	x	x	Psychologist C4D platform developer
Malta	x	x	x	N/A	x	Clinical Psychologist Psychotherapist
Poland	x	x	x	x	x	N/A
Portugal	x	x	x	N/A	x	Psychologist
Slovakia	x	x	N/A	x	x	N/A
Slovenia	x	x	x	N/A	x	N/A
Spain	x	x	x	x	x	Pharmacist

Note: use the following legend:

X = already defined

N/A = not applicable or not assigned yet

The collection of positive characteristics at national/regional level across C4D pilot countries is shown in Table 23.

Table 23 - Context analysis at national/regional level, positive characteristics, per C4D pilot country (the text is shortened to better fit the format, full length text is available in Annex III.)

Context analysis at national/regional level, positive characteristics	
<p>Belgium – current situation</p> <p>* the text is shortened to better fit the format, for full description please see Annex III.</p>	<p>The project has the support from key stakeholders</p> <p>The pre-trajectory care is experiencing positive developments.</p> <p>Governmental and MoH support to health prevention and promotion</p> <p>Existence of the local multidisciplinary networks (RMLs) to support GPs by organizing the care trajectory.</p> <p>Psychologists or educators/nurses in diabetes could take the role of the life coach.</p> <p>Diabetes educators/nurses can have a motivating role.</p>
<p>Belgium – foreseen future</p> <p>* the text is shortened to better fit the format, for full description please see Annex III.</p>	<p>Connections to Walloon Agency for a Quality Life (AVIQ, established) and to local multidisciplinary networks (planned). Belgian C4D pilot practice as an intensive lifestyle intervention could fill up this gap of lack of lifestyle related solutions for the patients and GPs.</p> <p>C4D is by supporting health promotion practices in line with the Proxisanté health reforms and the Walloon prevention and promotion plan: Proxisanté has underlined the need to facilitate interdisciplinary communication and fund meetings of interdisciplinary teams of health professionals; since the program strengthens interdisciplinary communication, it may be eligible for financing.</p> <p>C4D will train healthcare providers for leading group sessions and increase their efficacy, in alignment to HALT2DIABETES Flemish program. Additional efforts will be needed to reach vulnerable populations who need it most.</p> <p>Patient motivation is the determinant factor. The motivating role of the diabetes educators/nurses can be even more important if the first diabetes education session becomes mandatory in the new pre-trajectory.</p>
<p>Bulgaria – current situation</p>	<p>National policy.</p> <p>Existing organisation with administrative capacity (National Program Council) – national coordinating structure – National Center for Public Health & Analysis and then Regional Health Inspectorate to implement the policy on local level.</p> <p>National expert council on endocrinology at the MoH.</p> <p>The Law for Health Insurance –type 2 diabetes is enlisted in the list for subsidized services to reduce the financial burden for the patients (the State pays for certain tests, medical exams and the concrete algorithm for diagnosing Diabetes Type 2.</p> <p>Availability of diabetes education at primary (GPs, registered nurses, health promotion centres) and secondary (hospitals - diabetes clinic) level of health care.</p>
<p>Bulgaria – foreseen future</p>	<p>Developing national policies with the implementation of good practices in the field of diabetes.</p> <p>The inclusion of various experts from related medical fields (dietician, nurse) can reduce the work pressure among the doctors, who are specialists in diabetes.</p>

Context analysis at national/regional level, positive characteristics	
	<p>Providing low-threshold diabetes services among the uninsured.</p> <p>Increasing capacity to deliver education at all levels of care.</p>
Finland – current situation	<p>Many wellbeing counties have been developing lifestyle education for people with type 2 diabetes.</p> <p>People with type 2 diabetes are willing to receive more nutritional education.</p> <p>Diabetes nurses are well educated also in lifestyle education.</p>
Finland – foreseen future	<p>Importance of prevention of type 2 diabetes has been widely recognised in wellbeing counties.</p> <p>There are possibilities to evaluate the nutritional quality hopefully new methods will be used somehow.</p> <p>Diabetes nurses' importance to diabetes education is more credited.</p>
Greece – current situation	<p>State implementation plans for diabetes, yearly national diabetes conferences and high social media visibility.</p> <p>Increasing capacities at primary diabetes care and provision of education at all levels of diabetes care.</p> <p>Evolving process for type 2 diabetes education at primary care (family medicine practices, health promotion centres).</p> <p>Existing telemedicine approaches for type 2 patients.</p>
Greece – foreseen future	<p>Digitalisation in healthcare.</p> <p>Peer support is already developed.</p>
Hungary – current situation	<p>More than 100 health promotion offices in the country. They can reach many people also at schools and workplaces and as we see they really enthusiastic about their job. Many of them function within hospitals.</p> <p>There are competent professional bodies.</p> <p>There are some well-known role models with T2D who can people look up to.</p> <p>Many information can be found about T2D especially on the internet.</p> <p>More and more healthy choices are available for people with T2D in the shops.</p>
Hungary – foreseen future	<p>We hope that the number of health promotion offices will increase.</p>
Italy – current situation	<p>Funds (grants and programmes) to promote digital health.</p> <p>National plan for chronic diseases associated with national recovery and resilience plan- Mission 6 initiatives.</p> <p>Positive impact of e-health initiatives during Sars-Cov2 pandemic.</p> <p>Raising interest towards health promotion.</p> <p>Raising interest to educate and train multidisciplinary teams towards integrated, healthier lifestyles promotion.</p>
Italy – foreseen future	<p>Funds (grants and programmes) to sustain digitally-based initiative for non-communicable diseases prevention.</p>

Context analysis at national/regional level, positive characteristics	
	<p>Integration of/coordination among regional and national e-health services.</p> <p>Integration of currently excluded health professions in the healthcare systems.</p>
Malta – current situation	<p>Diabetes is a national priority.</p> <p>Diabetes tackled at both individual, societal, and family perspective. Approach is based on how the disease impacts the person as a whole.</p> <p>Specialised care delivered by multidisciplinary team to patients with newly diagnosed diabetes.</p> <p>Shared care programmes with multidisciplinary team and primary health centres.</p> <p>Work on modifiable risk factors.</p>
Malta – foreseen future	<p>Redesign of a new National Diabetes Strategy.</p> <p>Development of new ways on how to involve the public.</p> <p>Priorities being developed in new strategy.</p> <p>Integrated Social marketing programme.</p> <p>Integrated approach to tackle chronic disease is the way forward.</p>
Poland – current situation	<p>Existence of regional health policy programmes that include behavioural therapy for type 2 diabetes patients.</p> <p>Possibility to implement regional policy programmes by other local governments according to the same scheme- if they get a positive recommendation of Agency for Health Technology Assessment and Tariffs.</p> <p>Inclusion of type 2 diabetes patients' education in the coordinated care at primary level (medical team of GP, nurse, educator and dietician).</p> <p>Increasing awareness among patients about importance of self- management of disease.</p>
Poland – foreseen future	<p>Dissemination of behavioural therapy-based care model in subsequent practices and strengthening/promoting good practices based on behavioural therapy.</p> <p>Implementation of universal model of care focused on behavioural therapy.</p> <p>Ability to scale proven and comparable solutions.</p> <p>The possibility of disseminating the model of coordinated care and ultimately covering this model of care for the whole population.</p> <p>Reduction of the use of medicines by patients and improving the health parameters of patients covered by the programme by reversing the care model.</p>
Portugal – current situation	<p>Specialised human resources.</p> <p>Partnerships with Municipalities.</p> <p>Participation of patient representatives.</p> <p>Diabetes Functional Coordinating Units.</p> <p>Built knowledge with “Diabetes em Movimento” and “Juntos é mais fácil” (lifestyle programs).</p>
Portugal – foreseen future	<p>Adapt dietary guidelines.</p>

Context analysis at national/regional level, positive characteristics	
	<p>Adapt motivation assessment.</p> <p>Adopt online platform.</p> <p>Add quality of life assessment.</p> <p>Add social support.</p>
Slovakia – current situation	Existing chain of regional health consultancy offices (36).
Slovakia – foreseen future	Available EU funding.
Slovenia – current situation	<p>National diabetes plan 2020-2030 as a strategic guidance with 2 yearly implementation plans, with functional Steering Group, yearly national diabetes conferences and high social media visibility.</p> <p>National payer provides payment for increasing capacities at primary care and for provision of education at all levels of care.</p> <p>Existence of GDPR-protected repository of patient data (with very limited functionalities).</p> <p>Proactive national association of nurses in diabetes education developing education at all levels of care with explicit support from MoH, including recommendations, approaches and tools.</p> <p>Visibility and availability of website of national association of nurses designed to support diabetes education.</p> <p>Evolving process for type 2 diabetes education at primary care (family medicine practices, health promotion centres) under the leadership of NIJZ.</p> <p>Well studied telemedicine approaches in type 2 diabetes in primary care (and in pregnancy as a model of approach).</p> <p>Availability of diabetes education at primary (GPs, RNs, health promotion centres) and secondary (hospitals – diabetes clinic) level of healthcare.</p> <p>Adherence to (certain types of) educational programs very high.</p> <p>Longterm existence of diabetes education at secondary level, with extensive trainings, knowledge and skills of diabetes teams.</p>
Slovenia – foreseen future	<p>Digitalisation in healthcare one of the cornerstones of health reform; in place a process to improve and extend the functionalities of GDPR-protected repository of patient data.</p> <p>Peer support (via experienced persons with T2D -‘lay consultants’) is being under development (Ljubljana primary care unit).</p> <p>Telemedicine is in development: there are initiatives to develop standardised and unified online educational materials (videos) accessible nationwide.</p> <p>At MoH there is project on Health literacy to be concluded in 2023, a Strategy for Health literacy will follow; clinical pathway (also for diabetes, including gaps) was analysed within this project and what kind of information would be useful for a person with a condition traveling through the system.</p> <p>Terminology and philosophy of 19th century (speaking about services, patients, levels, specialities etc.) should be overcome and this is one of the opportunities. Language shapes reality (L. Wittgenstein). Let’s think about the level of individual person who does not care where he receives help.</p>

Context analysis at national/regional level, positive characteristics	
Spain – current situation	<p>National health system:</p> <p>Participation of the Spanish National Ministry of Health will evaluate the development and conclusions of the activity at the central level.</p> <p>Universal health system in place and running.</p> <p>Public health care system with a broad portfolio of services including diabetes education.</p> <p>Electronic Health record and regular T2D programmed visits in place.</p> <p>Integrated Diabetes Plan in place. It includes an integrated T2D care process.</p> <p>System-patients professionals interaction:</p> <p>Strong commitment of healthcare professionals to patients.</p> <p>Follow up of type 2 diabetes patients at health centers.</p> <p>Close relationship with the patient.</p> <p>Multidisciplinary team motivated and ready to work with type 2 diabetes and learning proactively.</p> <p>Knowledge exchange between health and non-health personnel.</p> <p>Expert diabetes nurse who can train on an individual level.</p> <p>Regular optional training in place (General Planning Directorate).</p> <p>Updated information through new communication channels.</p> <p>Possibility of taking courses to improve knowledge of diabetes.</p> <p>Phone and video chat healthcare.</p> <p>E-learning and technology applied to learning.</p> <p>Patients:</p> <p>Increased social awareness of the importance of acquiring healthy lifestyles as a measure to prevent the onset of diseases.</p> <p>Individual patient advice.</p> <p>Planning structure care plans.</p>
Spain – foreseen future	<p>Universal health assistance.</p> <p>European project engaging several countries: when positive results, new supportive strategies.</p> <p>Same evaluation methodology will provide common understanding at country level.</p> <p>Increased prestige of the healthcare system.</p> <p>Reduction of the economic cost: on medication and treatment of complications.</p> <p>Equity approach among European Countries.</p> <p>Impact on regional, national and international health policies.</p> <p>Lifestyle Key Performance Indicators included as part of medical records.</p> <p>Liaison nurses and social workers are regular members of the multidisciplinary teams.</p> <p>Social workers engaged in training and follow up of type 2 diabetes.</p> <p>Emphasis on prevention in educational programs.</p>

Context analysis at national/regional level, positive characteristics	
	<p>The prospect of group techniques over individual ones as more efficient therapeutic education.</p> <p>Greater empowerment of the patients and self-control of type 2 diabetes.</p> <p>Patients will be more involved if they can see the positive results of the interventions (body weight loss; lower glucose, plasma lipids and blood pressure; reduction in the need of drug etc.) for themselves.</p> <p>Increased awareness and involvement of patients in their disease.</p> <p>Being able to adapt new learning technologies to the reality.</p> <p>Structured individual and group diabetes education programs.</p> <p>Continuity of care report in place and regular writing report extended.</p> <p>Individual and group structured diabetic educational programs.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes population aware and mature to work on their own progress and control.</p> <p>Patients with type 2 diabetes generate their own reflection, own learning.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes goals are settled by patients, taking control and responsibility of their own process.</p> <p>Specific type 2 diabetes telemedicine access.</p> <p>New health education platforms and tools that improve disease perception and can be implemented in similar pathologies.</p> <p>More people will be able to use internet devices properly that can help to take care of their own health.</p> <p>Being able to adapt new learning technologies to the reality.</p>

The collection of negative characteristics at national/regional level across C4D pilot countries is shown in Table 24.

Table 24 - Context analysis at national/regional level, negative characteristics, per C4D pilot country (the text is shortened to better fit the format, full length text is available in Annex III.)

Context analysis at national/regional level, negative characteristics	
<p>Belgium – current situation</p> <p>* the text is shortened to better fit the format, for full description please see Annex III.</p>	<p>A national healthcare system remains too treatment oriented.</p> <p>There is a need to develop efficient intensive lifestyle program based on robust scientific evidence.</p> <p>The pre-trajectory care is rarely initiated by general practitioners due to the complexity of the subcategory criteria and the heavy administrative workload. There is a lack of diabetes educators in some áreas.</p> <p>Flemish and Walloon health promotion initiatives related to type 2 diabetes lack of security in funding, limited to referrals initiatives and pilot programs.</p> <p>The communication between the different healthcare providers needs to be improved (one of the aims of Proxisanté).</p>

Context analysis at national/regional level, negative characteristics	
	<p>A lack of clarity on the role of the local multidisciplinary networks in the management of type 2 diabetes patients.</p> <p>An unequal distribution of funding according to the territories.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes education sessions are knowledge-based and lack patient involvement and empowerment.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes education sessions are mostly delivered in one-on-one sessions and not much in group sessions.</p> <p>Additional efforts will be needed to reach vulnerable populations who need it most - double discrimination.</p> <p>There might be a lack of accredited psychologists.</p>
<p>Belgium – foreseen future</p> <p>* the text is shortened to better fit the format, for full description please see Annex III.</p>	<p>A national healthcare system that remains too treatment oriented. There is a need to demonstrate the cost effectiveness of such lifestyle intervention to make it reimbursable as a lack of reimbursement could seriously question the sustainability of the program.</p> <p>It is not known whether the flat rates for diabetes education in individual session and group session will both be increased.</p> <p>Flemish and Walloon health promotion initiatives related to type 2 diabetes lack of security in funding. The adapted physical activity is no longer fully reimbursed as the "chronic integrated care" pilot projects have seen their roles redefined for the Proximité reforms.</p> <p>An unequal distribution of funding according to the territories.</p> <p>Even if 4 diabetes education sessions get accessible to all the patients in the pre-trajectory, it could remain very knowledge oriented. Group diabetes self-management education and support is also important.</p>
<p>Bulgaria – current situation</p>	<p>Low budget of the national program.</p> <p>Limited health personnel – insufficient number of endocrinologists, who are concentrated mainly in the regional cities (uneven distribution on the territory of the country). This impedes high quality of cares, prophylaxis and monitoring of treatment.</p> <p>Health devices related to control of diabetes are at the expense of the patients.</p> <p>Lack of concrete initiatives that are binded with the national policies (National Center for Public Health & Analysis experts should educate nutritionists and physical trainers, all supervised by endocrinologists).</p>
<p>Bulgaria – foreseen future</p>	<p>Increasing number of patients with type 2 diabetes at all levels of care and insufficient funding.</p> <p>The growth of C4D practice is highly dependent on changing attitudes and systemic changes in practice.</p>
<p>Finland – current situation</p>	<p>Almost half of people with diabetes don't know whether they can have lifestyle education or not, and only about one fourth feel they receive enough lifestyle education.</p> <p>Less than one fifth of people with type 2 diabetes feels they receive nutritional education as much as they need. There are not enough dieticians working in the wellbeing counties.</p> <p>Many diabetes nurses' positions have been transferred other positions.</p>
<p>Finland – foreseen future</p>	<p>There are not enough resources to develop and broaden the lifestyle education in wellbeing counties.</p> <p>Wellbeing counties have no money to hire more dieticians.</p>

Context analysis at national/regional level, negative characteristics	
	There are shortage of nurses in total and also in diabetes nurses.
Greece – current situation	<p>Fragmentation and regional differences, both in terms of at which point is the patient being appointed to education at the secondary level, as well as what kind of information is being provided to them (including differences in methods and approaches). HCPs at the secondary level do not have a clear understanding if and what kind of preventive (e.g. education) and therapeutic activities were provided at the primary level. Similarly, GPs do not have a clear understanding what kind of education has been provided to persons with type 2 diabetes that have been appointed to education via HCPs.</p> <p>Differences in education between primary and secondary care.</p> <p>No systematic approach/platforms to support patients' education.</p> <p>No common e-health record.</p>
Greece – foreseen future	Increasing numbers of patients with type 2 diabetes at all levels of care, with different expectations from healthcare system, including digital services and support on one hand, and having more complex conditions including unfavourable socioeconomic conditions on the other. The interventions might actually broaden the gap in health across socioeconomic gradient if not designed well.
Hungary – current situation	<p>People are not conscious concerning their body and their health behaviour.</p> <p>There are no dieticians in the primary health care so if someone needs a dietician he/she will definitely have to pay for that.</p> <p>There ARE and there will always be people who share uncertain, unproven information about type 2 diabetes and try to convince people or sell them something (usually their own product).</p> <p>There are many information about type 2 diabetes (good and bad information can be found on the internet as well).</p> <p>However, maybe their financial situation is not good enough to buy healthy food.</p>
Hungary – foreseen future	<p>The problem is that the situation of the health promotion offices is unstable so we can only hope that they will function in the future too. The government does not give them enough financial support.</p> <p>There are and there WILL always be people who share uncertain, unproven information about type 2 diabetes and try to convince people or sell them something (usually their own product).</p>
Italy – current situation	<p>Health professionals specialized in healthy lifestyle promotion not included in healthcare systems.</p> <p>Patients' inadequate digital skills and resources.</p> <p>Patients' inadequate knowledge and awareness of the disease and its complications.</p> <p>Patients' inadequate motivation to relevant changes towards healthier lifestyles.</p> <p>Patients' inadequate socio-economic conditions to support changes towards healthier lifestyles.</p>
Italy – foreseen future	Poor investment in the public health service.
Malta – current situation	Projections are not all accomplished since priorities changed due to Covid pandemic.

Context analysis at national/regional level, negative characteristics	
	<p>Cooperation is required from the public and unfortunately, not always present.</p> <p>Shortage of staff and increased workload and patient needs due to increasing obesity and older population.</p> <p>Shortage of staff, increased workload, priorities change.</p> <p>Do not always refer clients to the professional providing specialised care or not aware of such services.</p>
Malta – foreseen future	<p>Priorities might change.</p> <p>Human and financial resources may not be adequate.</p>
Poland – current situation	<p>Limited clinical setting with little availability of multidisciplinary teams unwilling to the new medial approaches.</p> <p>Lack of effective implementation of diabetic guidelines into the clinical practice.</p> <p>Regional outreach of Health Prevention Programme.</p> <p>The diabetic pathway is not a systemic solution- optional implementation of coordinated care in primary healthcare units.</p> <p>No guarantee for changing the patient’s lifestyle despite the support of specialists.</p> <p>Dispersion of activities with only regional coverage- no systemic solutions.</p>
Poland – foreseen future	<p>Limited range of practical training.</p> <p>Differences between different solutions/ Interventions — inability to compare.</p> <p>The need to apply for programs by local governments instead of introducing a systemic solution.</p>
Portugal – current situation	<p>Scarcity of psychologists, nutritionists and exercise physiologists across the national health system.</p> <p>Low data portability.</p> <p>Fragmented care and limitation in consultation time.</p> <p>Low health literacy.</p> <p>Limited training for doctors and nurses in coaching and motivational approaches.</p>
Portugal – foreseen future	<p>Lack of financial resources.</p> <p>Lack of human resources in national health system.</p> <p>On-going major organizational changes.</p> <p>Low formal commitment on community lifestyle programs.</p>
Slovakia – current situation	<p>Low attendance and popularity in regional health consultancy offices.</p> <p>Lack of national plan to beat diabetes.</p> <p>National Health Promotion program does not mention diabetes.</p> <p>Not enough funding.</p>
Slovakia – foreseen future	<p>Low workforce availability.</p>

Context analysis at national/regional level, negative characteristics	
Slovenia – current situation	<p>Fragmentation and regional differences, both in terms of at which point is the patient being appointed to education at the secondary level (e.g. at diagnosis, complications etc.) as well as what kind of information is being provided to them (including differences in methods and approaches). HPs at the secondary level do not have a clear understanding if and what kind of preventive (e.g. education) and therapeutic activities were provided at the primary level. Similarly, GPs do not have a clear understanding what kind of education has been provided to persons with type 2 diabetes that have been appointed to education via HCPs.</p> <p>At primary care, education is mainly delivered and financed in a structured way (courses in health promotion centres with opportunities for individual education); at secondary level, the financing is different and does not support structured education and the payment of digital/non face to face visits is not clear.</p> <p>There is a need to build capacities for a continuous coaching approach and lifestyle support. Education is frequently perceived (by persons with type 2 diabetes and sometimes by HCPs) as acquiring a certain set of information (e.g. “dieting”).</p> <p>An extensive development of new medicines and technologies (e.g. sensors) in diabetes management in recent years resulted in educators being focused on explaining their use, less on lifestyle change planning.</p> <p>The numbers of RNs diabetes educators at secondary level is being reduced, while education itself became broader and more nuanced. Unclear availability and potential roles of other HPs, dietitians, psychologists, coaches, physiotherapists.</p> <p>No systematic approach/platforms to support patients’ education.</p> <p>No common e health record.</p>
Slovenia – foreseen future	<p>Increasing numbers of patients with type 2 diabetes at all levels of care, with different expectations from healthcare system, including digital services and support on one hand, and having more complex conditions including unfavourable socioeconomic conditions on the other. The interventions might actually broaden the gap in health across socioeconomic gradient if not designed well.</p> <p>Decrease the number of healthcare professionals and other professionals working in healthcare, including those related to diabetes education.</p> <p>The scaling up of C4D practice is highly dependent on systemic changes (and sometimes even reforms), but the outcomes are unsure.</p>
Spain – current situation	<p>Decentralization of the health system at national level.</p> <p>Different administrative local health systems to coordinate.</p> <p>Incomplete and non-homogeneous implementation of therapeutic education in primary healthcare.</p> <p>Not enough time per patient, including time to educate type 2 diabetes patients.</p> <p>Inadequate primary care relationship professionals- patients.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes paternalistic management attitude still coexist.</p> <p>Tendency to introduce medical treatment at early stages as first option.</p> <p>Over-prescription: excessive medicalization in type 2 diabetes.</p> <p>Unequal approach/type 2 diabetes coach and training depending on the professional responsible.</p> <p>Regardless stage of type 2 diabetes, same messages are delivered to the patient</p>

Context analysis at national/regional level, negative characteristics	
	<p>No clarity on the individualized prescription of knowledge for change in lifestyles.</p> <p>Not having a diabetes nurse or doctor as a reference in all health centres.</p> <p>Lack of specific profiles for those positions.</p> <p>No dietitian or coach available in most cases.</p> <p>No psychological support in place for type 2 diabetes.</p> <p>Poor culture on group health education.</p> <p>Lack of protocolized infrastructure.</p> <p>Deficient lifestyle change treatment follow-up.</p> <p>Poor number of liaison nurses (the one relating to hospital and primary care systems).</p> <p>Poor participation of social workers (patients at risk of exclusion).</p> <p>Scarce number of human resources available for education for the number of patients (nurse educators and dietitians).</p> <p>Healthcare professional burned out because overloaded</p> <p>Total or partial absence of continuity of care report between different levels of care.</p> <p>Resistance to change (of health professionals/ person with diabetes)</p> <p>Lack of knowledge about the impact of healthy lifestyles on disease control (the most effective treatment for diabetes).</p> <p>No standardized training for healthcare professionals in motivation and psychological management of the patient.</p> <p>Lack of regular self-care training for professionals.</p> <p>Lack of advanced practice nursing training in diabetes.</p> <p>Lack of regular standard training in diabetes among health professionals.</p> <p>Ageing population with greater difficulty in acquiring new lifestyle habits and healthy behaviours.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes population is increasing in numbers, unaware of responsibilities for their own process.</p> <p>There are no regulatory standards that prevent obesogenic environments.</p> <p>Unhealthy lifestyle from earlier ages.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes treatment based on pharmacological treatment.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes autonomy and control loss inducing disengagement and treatment dependency.</p> <p>No structured or specific type 2 diabetes training: fix and limited sessions not adjusting to individual needs as a chronic process of the disease.</p> <p>Patients' resistance to change.</p> <p>Advice easy to forget if not immediate acquisition of new habits.</p> <p>Poor training focuses on patients' digital capacity building.</p>
Spain – foreseen future	Prospective to have less professionals available as ratio patients per medical professionals increase while decreasing the time to take proper care of the patient.

Context analysis at national/regional level, negative characteristics	
	<p>Uncertainty about the possibility of generalizing education due to lack of funding and/or human resources.</p> <p>Increasing rates of aging according to demographic projections, which implies a greater number of comorbidities, and therefore of T2D.</p> <p>Resistance to change educational strategies among professionals.</p> <p>Insufficient professionals' number (rural areas, regular absences, on-call duty etc).</p> <p>Resistance of professionals towards the change of educational strategies.</p> <p>Early prescription of drugs, difficult to erase.</p> <p>Reduction in pharmaceutical research on anti-diabetic treatments.</p> <p>High prevalence of people with obesity and type 2 diabetes with tendency to increase over time.</p> <p>Applying lifestyle change regulations effectively is complex without the collaboration of the patient.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes patients' change resistance to improve their quality of life.</p> <p>Possibility of obsessive thoughts in relation to lifestyle.</p> <p>Digital divide.</p> <p>Patient resistance to education due to associated psychosocial problems.</p>

The collection of positive characteristics at local setting, across C4D pilot countries is shown in Table 25.

Table 25 - Context analysis at local setting, positive characteristics, per C4D pilot country (the text is shortened to better fit the format, full length text is available in Annex III.)

Context analysis at local setting, positive characteristics	
<p>Belgium – current situation</p> <p>*see other examples on local level in Annex III.</p>	<p>Local multidisciplinary network (RML) Cegeno– Fosses-la-Ville has a medium size team but good collaborations. They have a team of 8 educators in diabetes and also work with an excellent dietician.</p> <p>The team frequently attends trainings and conferences to be up to date.</p> <p>They have similar interest in some component program. They regularly organize recreational workshops with a dietician so they are used to group sessions. and wanted to start mindfulness session for the patients.</p>
<p>Belgium – foreseen future</p> <p>*see other examples on local level in Annex III.</p>	<p>Local multidisciplinary network (RML) Cegeno– Fosses-la-Ville has similar interest in some component program., such as relaxation exercises which is closely related to mindfulness.</p>
<p>Bulgaria – current situation</p>	<p>The members of the multidisciplinary team have experience in international projects.</p> <p>Most patients are treated by the same team for a long time and trust the healthcare team, which ensures a high degree of adherence to the project.</p>

Context analysis at local setting, positive characteristics	
	Basic education for a healthy lifestyle is available through the preventive activities of the expert of Regional Health Inspectorate.
Bulgaria – foreseen future	Positive adaptation to daily clinical practice. Expanding education.
Finland – current situation	Many people with diabetes experience that they have access to dietician. Most people with diabetes have access to lifestyle counselling. The diabetes nurses are able to give referrals to dieticians and coaches and physical activity counsellors at low threshold. The diabetes nurses try to include lifestyle counselling in every meeting with the patient. There is a dietician in Wellbeing Services County of South Karelia, and compared to the rest of the country there are more dieticians working in the wellbeing services county (but still too few).
Finland – foreseen future	There were digital care possibilities during EKSOTE (previous organization) – are they still available. Prevention is important in Wellbeing Services County of South Karelia - improving. There will definitely be users for the intervention if the best practice is sustainable, implemented and scaled-up.
Greece – current situation	Multidisciplinary team members, skilled in international projects. Basic healthy lifestyle education already available. Most of the patients are treated by the same team for a long time and they trust the healthcare team; if the team invites a patient to join a “project”, they usually agree and join it with high expectations.
Greece – foreseen future	Positive adaptation of everyday clinical practice. Education with the use of digital platform.
Hungary – current situation	As a national centre in the country we have many professional resources that we can use. The attitude of the patients’ family doctors can be supportive.
Hungary – foreseen future	<i>None identified.</i>
Italy – current situation	Raising interest on exploring reversing type 2 diabetes. Plans for re-organization of territory healthcare. Positive impact of e-health local initiatives. Interest in motivating patients, families and caregivers towards healthier lifestyles. ISS (National Institute of Health) expertise in digital health programmes.
Italy – foreseen future	Funds (grants and programmes) to assess reversibility of type 2 diabetes. Re-organization of territory healthcare. Integration of e-health initiatives in regional health systems.

Context analysis at local setting, positive characteristics	
Malta – current situation	<p>National Diabetes Yearly conference.</p> <p>Introduction of telemedicine during Covid pandemic.</p> <p>Diabetes management course at university level available.</p> <p>Centre of Excellence in Diabetes Care – under construction.</p> <p>Interest at large on healthy lifestyle, even amongst local councils.</p> <p>Education material available.</p>
Malta – foreseen future	<p>Involve a wider cohort of professionals.</p> <p>Extend the service to more patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes.</p> <p>Offer such programmes at Continuing Professional Development level.</p> <p>To become a Public Health Priority with Government providing further funding.</p> <p>Integrate them in a digital platform and made available this way.</p>
Poland – current situation	<p>Multidisciplinary team already available at primary health units with adapted coordinated care approach.</p> <p>Support from National Health Fund and Medical University of Warsaw’s experts (diabetes dietician experts included).</p> <p>Basic healthy lifestyle education already available at primary healthcare level.</p>
Poland – foreseen future	<p>Positive adaptation of new paths into everyday clinical practice.</p> <p>Education supported by the use of digital platform.</p>
Portugal – current situation	<i>Same as at national level.</i>
Portugal – foreseen future	<i>Same as at national level.</i>
Slovakia – current situation	<i>To be defined in later stage.</i>
Slovakia – foreseen future	<i>To be defined in later stage.</i>
Slovenia – current situation	<p>Multidisciplinary team members, skilled in international projects.</p> <p>Support from NIJZ and national diabetes experts included in NIJZ team.</p> <p>Basic healthy lifestyle education already available at primary healthcare teams and health promotion centres.</p> <p>Most of the patients are treated by the same team for a long time and they trust the healthcare team; if the team invites a patient to join a “project”, they usually agree and join it with high expectations.</p>
Slovenia – foreseen future	<p>Positive adaptation of everyday clinical practice.</p> <p>We are revitalizing regular meetings with the teams from primary sector to discuss certain topics and mainly to agree upon future collaboration and upon the way how to exchange patient data.</p> <p>Education with the use of digital platform.</p>

Context analysis at local setting, positive characteristics	
Spain – current situation	<p>Protocols in place.</p> <p>There is a Comprehensive Diabetes Plan in the Region.</p> <p>Integrated management of personal health records (linking of various sources of information through the single health record number).</p> <p>A single and universal personal health record.</p> <p>Accumulated experience in the management by Integrated Care Process initiative (including ‘Healthcare for people with diabetes’).</p> <p>Some small regions allow a close patient-nurse educator relationship.</p> <p>Highly experienced, knowledgeable local team with access to patients.</p> <p>Improved patient-physician relationship.</p> <p>There are voluntary training courses currently run by the Planning DG.</p> <p>Possibility of taking courses at The Galician Healthcare Service to improve knowledge of diabetes.</p> <p>High prestige of medical institutions in clinical research, particularly in diabetes.</p> <p>The population is receptive to collaborate in health research projects.</p>
Spain – foreseen future	<p>Promotion of community activities as a wellness driver.</p> <p>Proven cases will stimulate participation.</p> <p>Entrusted teams, system and community get recognition.</p> <p>Bonds reinforced between institutions to incorporate aspects of the activity into educational strategies.</p> <p>Inclusion of C4D in common daily practice.</p> <p>C4D could support dialogue, collaboration and better coordination of institutions in the field of diabetes education.</p> <p>Population pyramid less aged than the average regional population (particular case).</p> <p>Involvement and recognition of the work and its results, integrating it into the daily practice of diabetes professionals.</p> <p>Evidence based approach.</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes patients participate in C4D pilot in the way that best suits their needs giving flexibility and adapting to individual needs.</p> <p>Decreased pressure on patient care due to patient autonomy.</p>

The collection of negative characteristics at local setting, across C4D pilot countries is shown in Table 26.

Table 26 - Context analysis at local setting, negative characteristics, per C4D pilot country (the text is shortened to better fit the format, full length text is available in Annex III.)

Context analysis at local setting, negative characteristics	
Belgium – current situation *see other examples on local level in Annex III.	Local multidisciplinary network (RML) Cegeno– Fosses-la-Ville are worried about the new modalities of the pre-trajectory because the educators are already quite overwhelmed.
Belgium – foreseen future *see other examples on local level in Annex III.	<i>None identified.</i>
Bulgaria – current situation	High workload of team members. Degree of patient satisfaction with the project. The level of education of medical professionals and this is reflected in the approach to patient education.
Bulgaria – foreseen future	<i>None identified.</i>
Finland – current situation	Still many are lacking, they don't know if they can have access to dietician. One third would like to have more information about nutrition and exercise. Know-how of the person giving lifestyle counselling varies depending on the nurses' background – the patients' care is not equal. There are too few dieticians and wellbeing coaches – patients need to wait long to the appointments. There is lack of doctors and nurses in Wellbeing Services County of South Karelia - Diabetes nurses are not able to give enough intensive lifestyle counselling due to their heavy workload and also other nurses take care of people with diabetes than diabetes nurses. There is a high turnover of the nurses in the wellbeing services county. Little chances for the nurses to get training in lifestyle change. People with diabetes and mental health challenges don't get the lifestyle counselling they need because their main care is not diabetes centred.
Finland – foreseen future	Foreseen cutting of costs in the areas of social welfare and healthcare. Many patients are elderly – they do not have access to or capacity to use digital services. Too much hype on digital services – we still need personal contacts when dealing with patients with diabetes.
Greece – current situation	Extremely busy clinical setting, with unstable availability of multidisciplinary team members. There is a “post-COVID” effect and patients are not keen to visit hospital more than really necessary.
Greece – foreseen future	Potential obstacles arising outside the local setting.
Hungary – current situation	Participants' financial situation. The attitude of the patients' family doctors can be resisting.

Context analysis at local setting, negative characteristics	
Hungary – foreseen future	Participants’ financial situation.
Italy – current situation	Patients’ inadequate socio-economic conditions to support changes towards healthier lifestyles. Patients’ inadequate motivation to relevant changes towards healthier lifestyles.
Italy – foreseen future	Poor investment in the public health service.
Malta – current situation	Not all professionals invited to attend. Public might not be that fluent in digital health and prefer face-to-face interaction. Limit on the person who can enrol. Delivery of services dependent on budget availability of local council. Material needs to be updated.
Malta – foreseen future	May not attend due to workload and shortage of staff. Education to the public required. Does not necessarily means a greater intake. Digital platform under construction.
Poland – current situation	Limited clinical setting with little availability of multidisciplinary teams unwilling to the new medial approaches.
Poland – foreseen future	Potential obstacles arising outside local setting.
Portugal – current situation	<i>Same as at national level.</i>
Portugal – foreseen future	<i>Same as at national level.</i>
Slovakia – current situation	<i>To be defined in later stage.</i>
Slovakia – foreseen future	<i>To be defined in later stage.</i>
Slovenia – current situation	Extremely busy clinical setting, with unstable availability of multidisciplinary team members. Unclear payment for digital services. The level of education of HCPs at primary level might vary from team to team and this is reflected in the approach to education of the patients. There is a “post-COVID” effect and patients are not keen to visit hospital more than really necessary.
Slovenia – foreseen future	Potential obstacles arising outside the local setting. Current situation in the society and especially in health care sector is unsure.
Spain – current situation	Professionals' agenda overloaded. Professionals fatigue.

Context analysis at local setting, negative characteristics	
	<p>Few nurses involved in diabetes education.</p> <p>Low interest on focusing on the mental health.</p> <p>Not having a diabetes nurse or doctor as a reference professional in the health centers.</p> <p>Not the same education for everyone. The education level of diabetes depends on the health professionals that are taking care of that patient.</p> <p>No dietitian available.</p> <p>No exercise coach available.</p> <p>Lack of time and resources.</p> <p>Resistance to change on the part of professionals and patients Language barrier from original practice.</p> <p>Resistance to change on the part of professionals and patients.</p> <p>Aged & scattered population mostly in rural areas.</p> <p>Geographic areas with adverse socioeconomic status.</p> <p>Digital divide.</p>
Spain – foreseen future	<p>Uncertainty about the possibility of continued funding for education improvements.</p> <p>The sustainability of public healthcare system is under pressure due to the increase of the population aging and its chronic condition.</p> <p>Changes in the political situation and organizational models.</p> <p>Institutional engagement required for sustainability of the project.</p> <p>Multiple research projects must be ensured.</p> <p>Mind-sets evolution required.</p> <p>Excessive patient responsibility.</p> <p>Need to adapt the program to the patient and his or her limitations.</p> <p>Lack of time for teamwork.</p>

3.2.2. Main stakeholders

Acknowledging the existence and importance of main stakeholders early in the project is essential to facilitate the alignment and integration of the newly developed C4D pilot practice to the contexts, and to build already into its design the elements of sustainability. Main stakeholders, i.e. key individuals, institutions or organizations that may show interest for C4D outputs, or are affected by the work within C4D, or are important advocates for continuation and potential scalability of C4D, need to be identified, and ideally involved at an appropriate level, such as a full participation, a consultation, or are informed fully (specifically) or only briefly (during usual communication). If their potential (positive) influence is wisely used, the

reach of C4D within the countries can be much wider. On the other hand, potential negative influences need to be addressed and diminished as soon and as much as possible.

The full lists of the main stakeholders and their level of involvement from individual C4D pilot countries are attached as Annex III. Situation analysis of national/local contexts including main stakeholders, per C4D pilot country.

Representation of main stakeholders per their planned level of involvement across C4D pilot countries is shown in Table 27. The involvement may be described as a full participation (the stakeholder might be directly or retrospectively included to the C4D pilot local team), consultation (the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D pilot local team), as informed ((the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process), or briefly informed (the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usual C4D communication and dissemination activities).

Table 27 - Main stakeholders and their planned level of involvement, per C4D pilot country

Country	Full participation	Consultation	Informed	Briefly informed
Belgium	Local multidisciplinary networks (RML) : RML Maison du Diabète RML Liège et Liège Est RML Cegeno RML AGRF RML UOAD RML Grand Namur	SPF Santé Publique (The Federal Service of Public Health, Safety of the Food Chain and the Environment) The Walloon Agency for a quality life Association Belge du Diabète (Non profit organisation) Diabetes Liga (Non profit organisation)		Belgium Federal Cabinet Walloon Ministry of Health Cabinet The National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance The Federation of Associations of General Practitioners of the Walloon Region The Walloon Federation for Health Promotion Promo Santé & MG Chronicopole (project)

Country	Full participation	Consultation	Informed	Briefly informed
				PACT Santé Chronilux (project) Résinam (project) Rélian (project) RML Charleroi RML Point Santé
Bulgaria			National program board for the implementation of the National Program for the Prevention of Chronic Non-Communicable Diseases Program board of the National Program for the Prevention of Chronic Non-Communicable Diseases – Blagoevgrad Southwestern University "Neofit Rilski", department of social activities	Five medical facilities from Blagoevgrad region Regional structure of the Bulgarian Red Cross Municipality of Blagoevgrad
Finland		JV executive director of FDA TL, Advisory board member from Finland (UEF)	RN head of communications of FDA AN, expert of health care services in THL SS, ministerial advisor in MoH US, professor of dietetics in UEF	MH head of outpatient care in Wellbeing Services County of South Karelia AR head of wellbeing and prevention in Wellbeing Services County of South Karelia The board of FDA Directors of other welfare counties
Greece			Hellenic Endocrine Society National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	Hellenic Diabetes Association

Country	Full participation	Consultation	Informed	Briefly informed
				<p>Hellenic Diabetes Federation</p> <p>Patients with Diabetes Athens Vlub</p> <p>Health journalists</p>
Hungary		Hungarian Dietetic Association	<p>Hungarian Diabetes Association</p> <p>Professional Association</p>	
Italy	ISS, Head of IT Service AOUP, Director of Diabetology Unit		ISS, Head of Department Italian MoH, Prevention Unit	<p>ISS, Head of Scientific Communication Service</p> <p>*Regional Health Service</p> <p>*Patients' associations</p> <p>*Scientific Societies</p>
Malta			<p>Steering Group of the National Diabetes Strategy (2016-2020; 2023 -)</p> <p>Maltese Diabetes Association</p> <p>Malta Association of Public Health Medicine</p> <p>Malta Health Network</p>	
Poland	<p>Federation of Education in Diabetology/ EK</p> <p>Regional consultant in the field of family nursing- MP</p>	<p>Polish Association of Diabetology/ LC</p> <p>Section of Medical Dietetics POLSPEN/ DSW</p>	<p>Ministry of Health/ AN- Minister of Health</p> <p>Association of Family Medicine/ AMM</p> <p>Dean of the Faculty of Health Sciences in Medical University of Warsaw – MG</p>	<p>AOTMiT - Agency for Health Technology Assessment and Tariffs</p> <p>Rector of Medical University of Warsaw – ZG</p>

Country	Full participation	Consultation	Informed	Briefly informed
Portugal	Diabetes Patient Association		Diabetes Patient Association Primary care health units Regional Health Authorities Scientific societies	Academic institutions
Slovakia	MoH SR St. Elizabeth University of Health and Social Work in Bratislava	Public Health Authorities		Central State and Administration Bodies Local Administration Bodies Regional Authorities (8 regions) Municipalities Medical and Public Health schools Research and Educational Institutions Healthcare Providers Health Insurance Groups Social Insurance Group
Slovenia			Steering group of the National Diabetes Plan 2020-2030 National association of diabetes nurse educators	National association of diabetologists Top management in the Hospital Patient diabetes association Novo mesto National institute of

Country	Full participation	Consultation	Informed	Briefly informed
				public health – regional office Health promotion centre (Health centre Novo mesto)
Spain	NPS MJFC RA Diabetes Advisory Council of the Principality of Asturias (CADPA). Foundation for Biosanitary Research and Innovation of the Principality of Asturias (FINBA). CGG PM AD - Sub-directorate of Care, Training and Care Continuity. FundeSalud.	Association of Diabetics Principality of Asturias (ASDIPAS). President of the International Society of Bioethics. Head of the Endocrinology and Nutrition Service of the HUCA. Central University Hospital of Asturias. Members of the Asturias Diabetes PCAI (Key Interdisciplinary Care Program). ARS Federation of Associations of People with Diabetes of Extremadura (FADEX). Extremadura Diabetes Society (SEDI). Galician Federation of Diabetic Associations (FEGADI). Regional Ministry of Health and Consumers Affairs of Andalusia: Chief of the Health Promotion and Local Health Action Service. General Directorate for Public Health and Pharmaceutical Organisation. The Andalusian Strategy for the Promotion of a Healthy Life.	Patient Schools, belonging to the Asturias School of Care. Asturias Society of Family and Community Medicine (SaMFyC). Asturias Association of Community Nursing (SEAPA). Older people University (PUMUO). Cantabria School of Health. Extremadura Society of Endocrinology and Nutrition. Extremadura Society of Family and Community Nursing. Specialised Healthcare Training of the SAS: Teaching units in: Primary Care Nursing; Family Physicians; Endocrinology and Nutrition Regional Ministry of Educational Development and Vocational Training of Andalusia Federation of Associations of Diabetics of Andalusia, member of the Spanish Federation of Diabetes. Healthcare services of the municipalities.	Cantabria Diabetes Association. IL – Managing Director of Primary Health of Cantabria. RW – General Director of Public Health. Cantabria Health Service. Cantabria Regional Ministry of Health. UNATE – Cantabria Permanent University. Spanish Society of Endocrinology and Nutrition. Diabetes Spanish Society. Spanish Obesity Society. Asociation of patients with diabetes of Aragón. Zaragoza Medical Profesional Association. Scientific societies:

Country	Full participation	Consultation	Informed	Briefly informed
		<p>The Andalusian Comprehensive Care Strategy.</p> <p>Andalusian Health Service:</p> <p>General Directorate for Healthcare and Health Outcomes.</p> <p>Deputy-Director of Information Technologies.</p> <p>Deputy-Director of Information Management</p> <p>Coordination of Information Systems</p> <p>Sevilla” and “Granada Nordeste” Health Districts.</p>	<p>Patient Schools, belonging to the Andalusian School of Public Health.</p>	<p>Andalusian Society of Family and Community Medicine (SAMFyC).</p> <p>Andalusian Association of Community Nursing (ASANEC).</p> <p>Andalusian Society of Endocrinology, Diabetes and Nutrition (SAEDYN).</p>

*the level of involvement of these stakeholders may change during the process of implementation

3.2.3 Conclusions and main recommendations

To bring to conclusion the results reported in this chapter, we have prepared a brief outline of the messages based of the stepwise approach which was used by the C4D pilot countries.

Step I: C4D Pilot local team and multidisciplinary team

All C4D pilot countries have assigned team organizers and experts from different fields. However, the table does not show the number of e.g. experts, which in some cases are from 1 to 5 people per team. Half of the countries have a decision maker, and 4 out of 12 countries have some other profiles such as Project manager, Senior Advisor and IT expert included in the team.

In two out of 12 countries, the MTD does not include a medical doctor. In all other countries, the team consists of a nurse, a dietician, and a medical doctor. In addition to the above-mentioned profiles, in more than half of the countries the team also consists of a coach, and in 11 out of 12 countries also a C4D practice coordinator. Other additional profiles that appear

exceptionally are: administrator, C4D platform developer, psychologist, clinical psychologist, psychotherapist and pharmacist.

Step II and IV: Purpose and scope development within C4D pilot local teams

The C4D pilot local team had to create the common purpose and shared scope of their team. Due to intermediate steps and further meetings, the original idea could be upgraded, so in the last, fourth step, both purpose and scope could be redefined per C4D pilot country. As the results in Table 20 show, 7 out of 12 countries kept the original scope and purpose, 5 reformed it based on further meetings. The aim of this step was to reach an agreement based on what was perceived as important and feasible in the contexts of each C4D pilot country.

Step III: Context analysis national/local setting, positive and negative characteristics of current situation and foreseen future & Main stakeholders

In the third step of this process, the C4D pilot countries had to consider the current situation and the foreseen future of their practices and define the positive and negative characteristics both at the national/regional and at local level. Further analysis across the countries is not foreseen, but despite the general differences among the 12 countries, main challenges are largely the same, and participation within C4D is perceived as an important action to further improve type 2 diabetes education, and main stakeholders seem to be mainly on board.

As part of the work in task 5.1, the C4D pilot countries had to provide a list of stakeholders and determine their level of involvement. Partners within the 12 countries identified 151 main stakeholders, for 22 if they plan full participation, and for 30 consultation. The dissemination and communication activities are planned to be very active, since 40 stakeholders will be fully, and 59 at least briefly informed.

In conclusion, all of C4D pilot countries have functional C4D teams with roles assigned and with an agreement on shared purpose and common goal, and in 10 out of 12 have defined a multidisciplinary team. All of C4D teams were able to identify positive and negative characteristics both at the national/regional and at local level (in 10/12 countries where the local level is already defined), and assigned them to be Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats, thus providing important baseline insight into the context to be able to decide on whether to adopt, adapt or abandon certain elements of VL, or maybe to add elements that might be found as to be essential. Despite the variability of health systems structures, processes and financing among the 12 countries, main challenges are largely the same (such as role of digitalisation, increasing number of patients, decreasing number of healthcare professionals). 151 main stakeholders were identified by C4D teams, and their foreseen level

of involvement is defined. Several of them are planned to be fully involved or actively consulted. The dissemination and communication activities within C4D pilot countries are planned to be very active, since a big number of stakeholders is planned to be or at least briefly informed.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The main strength of the methodologies used is the scientific rigor, i.e. the strict application of the scientific methods to ensure robust and unbiased design of the methodology for in-depth review of VL best practice, its analysis, interpretation and reporting of result. Especially in a qualitative research, this is the approach on how to establish trust and confidence in the findings of these results. The capacities within NIJZ team to assure the scientific rigor were complemented by extremely generous commitment and intense participation of many members of VL team, starting 5 months before the official start of C4D, supported by C4D coordinators; this is the second major strength of this report.

Weaknesses of this report are related to the suboptimal skills and capacities of C4D pilot teams within C4D pilot countries on the use of social/implementation science methods and principles, and to the tight schedule to provide complex information VL practice and on the context situation. Therefore, the methodology used was adjusted to the information on VL practice available at that time point, the skills of C4D teams, with an aim to fit into the schedule of activities within C4D.

This report identifies essential elements for successful implementation process within intervention characteristics, outer and inner setting, characteristics of individuals and within the process.

VL best practice

Regarding intervention characteristics, it is important that VL best practice was internally developed with strong support of a wide variety of outside stakeholders. Unique to the Dutch context, it addresses the complex and multidimensional nature of type 2 diabetes management based on lifestyle intervention by focusing on nutrition, exercise, sleep and stress reduction. It includes a multidisciplinary team of experts and is available in both face-to-face and online format. The practice operates successfully in different local settings within and outside Netherlands. Coverage is provided by the Dutch health insurance package (for low complexity patients) and through private insurers (for high complexity patients).

In relation to outer setting, patient needs and views are continuously considered through interactions with patient federations and program participants. The practice is adaptable to meet patient needs and increase accessibility. Organization is continuously engaged to outside stakeholders, including Healthcare Groups (of physicians), nurses, scientists, specialists, patient federations, government and health insurers. Program is aligned with national policies and funding frameworks.

Within inner setting, the organizational structure supports continuous information flow between VL management team, VL training team, Scientific council and Core program team, including frontline professionals and participants of the program. There is significant support for the practice implementation across the organization and frontline professionals involved in the program. Goals are clearly communicated, acted upon, and aligned with the staff. Continuous learning and improvement are encouraged within the intervention team.

As per characteristics of individuals, there is an overall recognition of the importance of lifestyle medicine philosophy in diabetes management and education among individuals from VL. Self-reflection in achieving implementation goals are valued and supported through several processes (online and face-to-face interventions, 'VL Caffee', webinars and trainings). Individuals exhibit a strong and passionate commitment to the goals of the organization and believe they have an impact on practice development.

Finally, the process of the implementation includes clear protocols in place to implement the practice, including the provision of training to the frontline professionals. During the program, patient participants and frontline professionals are continuously engaged through various mechanisms. There are continuous efforts to identify and empower champions ("points of light") within and outside of the organization to overcome indifference or resistance that the intervention may provoke at different levels of operation. Continuous quantitative and qualitative feedback about the progress and quality of implementation is in place, accompanied with regular personal and team debriefing about progress and experience.

C4D implementing countries contexts

Situation analysis of contexts within C4D implementing countries shows, that all of them have C4D teams with roles assigned and with an agreement on shared purpose and common goal, and in 10 out of 12 have defined a multidisciplinary team. All of C4D teams identified positive

and negative characteristics both at the national/regional and at local level. Despite the variability of health systems among the 12 countries, main challenges are largely the same (such as role of digitalisation, increasing number of patients, decreasing number of healthcare professionals). 151 main stakeholders were identified by C4D teams, and their level of involvement is defined.

To conclude, the contexts within C4D pilot countries might differ a lot from the VL best practice context. Nevertheless, some general lessons learnt can be taken: (1) Continuous education of staff is key, but especially important at the beginning. Recommended staff to be included at the very start of practice development are a nurse & dietitian; (2) Proceed step-by-step, go forward when you understand your needs and existent resources. Remain adjustable, flexible and open to opportunity; (3) Showcase a strong 'business case' as good story sells. Have that in mind when getting funding after the project ends, and (4) Keep good relationships with stakeholders; showcase results continuously.

In this report, key characteristics of the context, that facilitate successful future implementation within C4D are identified to be readiness to change, evaluation (to support evidence-based investment) and capacity building (“learning system”). Based on the baseline analysis of the contexts within C4D piloting countries, another round of reflection from C4D teams through those three lenses might be very useful in next step. This would give insights into how wisely adapt VL best practice to suit the actual needs of C4D countries and support the development of C4D practices, that will bring the change to C4D countries and will be sustainable after C4D ends.

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6. ANNEXES

6.1. Annex I. Methodological guidance document for in-depth review of VL best practice

Developed within CARE4DIABETES (Task 5.1,) by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

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1. BACKGROUND

This document includes methodological materials (guides, templates and questionnaires) that were used to perform the collection of qualitative data for in-depth review of VL best practice within Task 5.1 of the Joint Action CARE4DIABETES. The information gathered is aimed at supporting the adoption and adaptation process of the VL best practice by pilot countries in CARE4DIABETES, and to achieve a successful implementation of the CARE4DIABETES pilot actions within different settings across EU.

In-depth review consists of several steps:

- Description of the objectives of VL practice and how they were developed
- Description of the core features of VL practice
- Description of the implementation process of VL practice (CFIR elements)¹²
- Description of context characteristics minimum maturity requirements for VL practice implementation) using SCIROCCO approach¹³

¹² <https://cfirguide.org/>

¹³ <https://www.scirocco-project.eu/maturitymodel/>

- Description of elements of sustainability that supported/are still supporting VL practice (*this part is related to work on sustainability within Work Package 4 and will not be mentioned in detail*).

For each of the steps, a dedicated methodological document was developed by NIJZ in collaboration and in agreement with VL. Experiences and methodological approaches used in JA CHRODIS+ and JADECARE informed the design of guides for conducting CFIR-based focus group for implementation process and interviews on elements of sustainability. Agenda of the on-site study visit can be found as Attachment I. For description of context characteristics and implementation process, expert advice was provided by Yhasmine Hamu, Irati Erreguera, Jon Txarramendieta, Ane Fullaondo and Esteban de Manuel from Kronikgune (Health Services Research Institute from Basque Country), specifically on the use of SCIROCCO Tool and convening a SCIROCCO consensus-building workshop. Timeline of the work is presented in Box 1.

Box 1. Timeline of the steps

Timeline of steps:

- June – September 2022: development of methodological approach and draft materials by NIJZ
- September - October 2022: alignment meetings with VL and C4D Coordinator on methodological approach and on human resources dedicated
- November 2022: upgrading of guides, templates and questionnaires for each step, selection of respondents from VL best practice to participate in the in-depth review per each step
- December 2022: collection of the information on objectives of VL best practice and how they were developed and of the core features of VL best practice (word template, alignment and refinement meetings); development of the structure, format and participants selection at on-site study visit of NIJZ and C4D Coordinator at VL best practice premises in Amsterdam, Netherlands
- January 2023: collection of the final information on objectives of VL best practice and how they were developed and of the core features of VL best practice; completion of individual online assessments using SCIROCCO Tool by selected respondents from VL best practice; finalisation of the activities related to on-site study visit;
- February 2023: On-site study visit of NIJZ and C4D Coordinator at VL best practice premises in Amsterdam, Netherlands; preliminary results of the in-depth review presented at the Kick-off meeting
- March – June 2023: Analysis of results and preparation of D5.1

2. METHODOLOGICAL MATERIALS USED FOR IN-DEPTH REVIEW OF VL BEST PRACTICE

The most scientifically appropriate approach to collect information was adjusted to the type of the data. To collect descriptions and basic data to inform further analytical steps, available resources were studied; for missing data, a collaboratively designed word template was used to complete the data (please see 2.1.). To assess the relative importance of context dimensions for successful implementation, individual assessment via online tool was collected after briefing with VL practice core team, finalised by group workshop to achieve a consensus. To explore relevant characteristics of the implementation process, a focus group was conveyed, the prompting questions being informed by the data from objectives and core features descriptions and preliminary studies on context characteristics. In addition, semistructured interviews included some questions related to implementation in general, and provided the second source of data. Please see also Table 1.

Table 1 - Approaches to collect information for in-depth review of VL best practice

Content	Approach used
Description of the objectives and core features of VL practice	2.1. Core features of VL best practice - word template
Description of context characteristics with minimum maturity requirements	2.2. Guide to complete online individual assessment of good practice using SCIROCCO Tool 2.3. Guide to conduct SCIROCCO Consensus-building workshop
Description of the implementation process of VL practice (CFIR elements)	2.4. Guide for CFIR based focus group on implementation process 2.5. Guide for individual in-depth interview (partly)
Description of elements of sustainability, that supported/are still supporting VL practice	2.5. Guide for individual in-depth interview on elements of sustainability of VL best practice <i>(this part is related to work on sustainability within Work Package 4 and will not be mentioned in detail)</i>

Methodology to analyse qualitative data

To analyse qualitative data acquired during focus group and interviews (related to 2.4. and 2.5.), thematic analysis method¹⁴ was used. The sessions were recorded with the consent of the participants, and transcribed. In the next step of thematic analysis, transcription was coded by the researchers, and grouped according to themes. Themes were predetermined – based on the topic, we were using implementation research framework CFIR, but were conscious that if this framework might not sufficiently cover the data, new/additional themes can arise during the process of analysis itself (e.g. Grounded theory approach)¹⁵. Before analysed information is reported and publicly disseminated, there should be at least one round of revision by people who participated in the research activities.

2.1. Core features of VL best practice – word template

Final template and guidance defined: *date*

Core research team: *names, institutions*

Respondents: *names, institutions.*

Steps and timeline: *described in sufficient detail*

Box 2. Example from C4D

Guidance and template development (final version Sept 14 2022): NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Denis Oprešnik, Simona Jazbinšek, Anja Brunec; Respondents: VL team: Emma Coles, Mirjam Blijleven, Maud Verburgh; Dates: delivered to NIJZ by VL on Dec 19 2022; possible revisions and updates between Dec 19 2022 – Jan 31st 2023; available for CARE4DIABETES partners on Feb 1st 2023.

In order to ensure a smooth adoption/adaptation process of the VL best practice by pilot countries in CARE4DIABETES, and to achieve a successful implementation of the CARE4DIABETES pilot actions within pilot countries, in-depth understanding of VL practice is needed.

The purpose of this document is to address the first two steps of the in-depth review of VL practice- the objectives including their development, and core features of VL best practice.

¹⁴https://books.google.si/books?hl=sl&lr=&id=RR1tEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=uwe+flick+an+introduction+to+qualitative+research+pdf&ots=VKLCML7Hiv&sig=JA6tROcU-bLL8tnMICqInXIUgH8&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=uwe%20flick%20an%20introduction%20to%20qualitative%20research%20pdf&f=false

¹⁵ <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2001-05785-001>

Firstly, the information on the objectives of VL best practice and how they were developed is provided. Then, the document describes the core features of VL practice, including: patient population; human resources including competencies of the VL teams and other stakeholders (capabilities needed); other resources; detailed description of the intervention; monitoring and evaluation; funding mechanisms; main barriers and facilitators; problem-solving approach. This document ends with 5 lessons learnt, as the most important recommendations for pilot countries.

(Note: Some sections of the template that NIJZ team provided to VL best practice team already included information from the programme's website and the project application, to be confirmed/upgraded if needed.)

1. Objectives of VL best practice

Objectives of VL practice are:

Insert text here

Description of the process to develop the objectives including rationale/arguments for decisions:

Insert text here

2. Patient population description

Inclusion criteria:	Exclusion criteria:
Insert text here	Insert text here

Additional information, if needed:

Insert text here

3. Human resources including competencies of the VL teams and other stakeholders

Table 2 - Human resources including competencies of the VL teams and other stakeholders

VL teams	Team members' profession	Core competencies (relevant for VL best practice)	Role/tasks
VL management team	Insert text here	Insert text here	Insert text here
Core program team at VL			
VL medical team			
VL Training team			
Add lines if needed			
Other stakeholders (outside VL) involved (names, roles/tasks)			
Insert text here			

4. Other resources

Insert text here

5. Detailed description of the intervention

The idea is to use as much as possible the existent documents you already have in English. Maybe the easiest solution is to have a short summary here and then links to web resources, documents as annexes to this file, etc.

Phase I: Intensive care treatment programme
Insert text here
Phase II: After-care treatment programme
Insert text here

6. Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms/tools

Again, the idea is to use as much as possible the existent documents you already have in English. Maybe the easiest solution is to have a short summary here and then links to web resources, documents/publications as annexes to this file, etc.

<p>General description of the evaluation and monitoring approach/mechanism/tools</p> <p>Insert text here</p>
<p>Expected results and long-term outcomes</p> <p>Insert text here</p>
<p>Achieved results and long-term outcomes</p> <p>Insert text here</p>
<p>Effectiveness</p> <p><i>(Extent to which the objectives of the intervention were achieved. Add also any unintended consequences that the intervention led to.)</i></p> <p>Insert text here</p>
<p>Efficiency</p> <p><i>(Extent to which (monetary and non-monetary) inputs were used to achieve desired outcomes.)</i></p> <p>Insert text here</p>
<p>Evidence-base</p> <p><i>(The strength and validity of evidence used to develop or evaluate the intervention.)</i></p> <p>Insert text here</p>
<p>Equity</p> <p><i>(Extent to which the intervention reduced inequalities in society.)</i></p> <p>Insert text here</p>
<p>Coverage</p> <p><i>(Extent to which the intervention reached the whole target population.)</i></p> <p>Insert text here</p>

7. Funding mechanism(s)

Please explain how you secured stable funding resources necessary for the delivery of the intervention, including key stakeholders involved.

Insert text here

8. Main barriers and facilitators

Main barriers:
 Insert text here

Main facilitators:
 Insert text here

9. Approach to solve the problems

Can you please share with the consortium, how you were solving the problems, when they appeared, generally?

Insert text here

10. 5 lessons learnt and recommendations for pilot countries

Table 3 - Lessons learnt and recommendations for pilot countries

Lessons learnt	Recommendations for pilot countries
Insert text here	Insert text here

2.2. Guide for CFIR based focus group on implementation process

Final guidance defined: *date*

Core research team: *names, institutions*

Respondents: *names, institutions*

Steps and timeline: *described in sufficient detail*

Box 3. Example from C4D

Guidance document development (final version: January 2023) NIJZ team: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec; Participants of CFIR based focus group on implementation process: Barbara Kerstens, Program director, Emma Coles, Data and Care Relations Director, Project Manager

(Background in business and management), Mirjam Blijleven, program coordinator (background in health sciences, nutrition and health), Maud Verburgh, program coordinator (background in hotel management), Lotte Shaffer, operational manager (background in dietetics), Nathalie Wilmsen, Research Coordinator (background in nutrition science).
Timeline: Workshop: February 2 2023, during on-site study visit; detailed report (within the final report on in-depth review of best practice (Deliverable 5.1)), due date June 2023.

Purpose and objectives: to explore different contextual factors that characterized the implementation process of the VL best practice. Identified characteristics of the implementation process provide key insights for the future implementers about the approaches taken to successfully implement the practice, the role of different actors (champions and institutions) in its development, the barriers/facilitators the practice encountered. Learnings will be used to guide and support C4D implementers during their implementation processes.

Method: Focus group is based on Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR)¹⁶. This method enables a discussion between group of individuals with knowledge about the practice development and implementation from different professional perspectives. Focus group as a method brings more thorough understanding about different processes that led to practice implementation, while participants have the opportunity to exchange and revise ideas, experiences and understandings relevant to this topic. The focus group is based on CFIR framework, where the practice implementation is explored through 5 key domains (Intervention characteristics, Outer Setting, Inner Setting, Characteristics of individuals and Process). As some domains have been explored in more detail using other methods, the questions in these activity are adjusted accordingly.

Procedure and Questionnaire

Thank you for taking the time to have this Focus group discussion with us. Its purpose is to explore different aspects that characterized the implementation process of the VL best practice. Identified characteristics of the implementation process will provide key insights for the CARE4DIABETES partners with pilots who will develop their own adapted practices as well as work package leaders and others who will support them in this process.

**Potentially: We selected Focus group as qualitative research because it enables a discussion between group of individuals with knowledge about the practice development and*

¹⁶ Dodati referenco

implementation from different professional perspectives. Focus group as a method can bring more thorough understanding about different processes that led to practice implementation, while you have the opportunity to exchange and revise ideas, experiences and understandings relevant to this topic. The focus group will be based on CFIR framework, which is a tool we use for analysis - the practice implementation is explored through 5 key domains (Intervention characteristics, Outer Setting, Inner Setting, Characteristics of individuals and Process).

*If you agree, we would record this discussion and make notes for the purposes of analysis. Before we communicate your messages with others within CARE4DIABETES, we will share the focus group report to you for possible revisions. At any point during our discussion we can stop the recording or you can make explicit request, if some statements should not be reflected within the report. The focus group will take approx. 2h to complete. *Recording starts. One interviewer leads the focus group, the second one takes care of notes, recording device and poses sub-questions where appropriate.*

Table 4 - Questions for focus group discussion based on CFIR constructs

Questions	CFIR constructs (potentially addressed)
<i>At the start of our discussion, we would like for each of you to reflect a bit on what makes the VL best practice a success story. What do you personally, based on your experience, role and values, find as having a key impact on practice success? You can share with us a short story, an anecdote or even just a thought? (*check where the focus is at: people, events, structures, funds, clinical outcomes, recognition?)</i>	Inner setting, Outer setting, Intervention characteristics, Characteristics of individuals
<i>In addition to what you have presented, what in your opinion were/are the drivers that support implementation of the VL best practice? How was the decision made to implement the program? (*check if they consider them as something internal or external to the practice)</i>	Inner setting, Outer setting, Process
<i>What steps did you need to take to fully implement the practice? (How complex was it to implement the practice and make it operational? How did you prepare for implementation?) Consider: duration, scope, intricacy, support needed, patient involvement approach, communication strategy, training, resources (*we inquire about their planning process)</i>	Intervention characteristics, Process
<i>What kind of barriers did you experience or are you still experiencing with practice implementation? How did/do you overcome them? Sub: Were there significant changes within your practice? Which? How has your team stayed resilient?</i>	Inner setting, Outer setting

<i>In your personal view, how do patients perceive your practice? Are they included in any way in the process of change/practice improvement? (evaluation, feedback loops)</i>	Intervention characteristics, Process
<i>In CARE4DIABETES, your practice will be a basis for development of new practices related to diabetes education. What would be your main message to the future implementers that will be adopting/adapting your practice?</i>	N/A
<i>Before we conclude this focus group, would any of you like to add anything else that might be important but was not yet addressed? (Are there other aspects of your practice implementation that should be discussed?)</i>	All

Thank you. This concludes our discussion.

2.3. Guide to complete online individual assessment of good practice using SCIROCCO Tool

Final guidance defined: *date*

Core research team: *names, institutions*

Respondents: *names, institutions.*

Steps and timeline: *described in sufficient detail*

Box 4. Example from C4D

Guidance document development (final version September 14 2022): NIJZ team: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec; Participants of individual SCIROCCO assessments (same as SCIROCCO Consensus-building workshop): VL team: main contact: Emma Coles, Data and Care Relations Director, Project Manager (Background in business and management). Other respondents: Barbara Kerstens, Program director; Lotte Shaffer, operational manager (background in dietetics); Nynke van der Zijl, Head of medical team (background in medicine); David Bakx, Regional manager of care relations (background in nutrition and dietetics); Nathalie Wilmsen, Research Coordinator (background in nutrition science); Minke den Hollander, nurse medical team (background in nursing); Mirjam Blijleven, program coordinator (background in health sciences, nutrition and health); Maud Verburgh, program coordinator (background in hotel management); Timeline: Guidance document delivered to VL on September 14 2022; Briefing of NIJZ team with VL (Emma Coles) on September 19 for potential additional alignment; Selection of respondents by VL (5-8 respondents from VL as proposed in the section below) composition suggested from NIJZ; Introductory meeting with respondents, if needed, prompted by Emma and provided by

NIJZ, in December/January 2023); mail from Emma to respondents to start with assessments to be delivered on January 10 2023. Due date: January 25 2023.

In order to ensure a smooth adoption/adaptation process of the VL best practice by pilot countries in CARE4DIABETES, and to achieve a successful implementation of the CARE4DIABETES pilot actions within pilot countries, in depth understanding of VL practice is needed.

The purpose of this document is to present a step-by-step process to complete the individual good practice assessment using online SCIROCCO Tool, in order to gather information on minimum maturity requirements for successful VL best practice implementation, using SCIROCCO Maturity Model¹⁷ as a conceptual framework.

Selection of the most relevant respondents will be made by VL. Additional introductory meeting may be scheduled, if needed. All responses will be reviewed by NIJZ team. A consensus-building workshop (face-to-face) will follow after the completion of individual assessments with the same respondents. The workshop will be led by NIJZ team and scheduled in agreement with VL and coordinators.

HOW TO CHOOSE RESPONDENTS: respondents who will conduct individual good practice assessments using online SCIROCCO Tool should be able to understand the VL practice from a bird perspective and thus possess the knowledge about what are the necessary contextual maturity requirements for successful adoption of the VL practice. The respondent group should consist of up to 8 members of VL practice, including management, finance, communication and health professionals.

WHAT IS SCIROCCO TOOL: an online self-assessment tool to address the challenge of adoption and scaling up of good practices in healthcare, developed for integrated care, but can be used for good practices in any area. It eases the adoption of practices by: defining maturity (readiness) to adopt the good practice; assessing the maturity of healthcare systems; and assessing maturity requirements for implementation of the good practice.

In CARE4DIABETES, the participating representatives of VL best practice will complete the individual assessment, responding to an on-line maturity assessment questionnaire which consists of:

¹⁷ <https://www.scirocco-project.eu/maturitymodel/>

- 12 dimensions, each of which addresses a part of the overall effort for implementation of the best practice,
- An explanatory narrative for each dimension,
- Assessment scale rated from 0 to 5 with a text box to provide justification for the response,
- Spider diagram illustrating the assessment outcomes,
- Functionalities for sharing and comparing spider diagrams of different users as a basis for consensus building.

Fig. 7. SCIROCCO tool

PURPOSE IN CARE4DIABETES: to assess the Maturity (Readiness) Requirements¹⁸ of the VL practice, which should be considered by the future implementers in CARE4DIABETES to successfully adopt/adapt the best practice to their local setting. When future implementers will be analysing their contexts, the maturity requirements will be used to understand if adoption of the best practice is feasible and to what extent the adaptation is needed.

Important! When you will be conducting individual good practice assessment, it is important to look into the future – based on your experience with your local context identify which are

¹⁸ Maturity requirements can be understood as the minimum that the chosen good practice needs from its environment (context), for it to be possible to operate. If we ask the question "Would the good practice be possible if this requirement was absent from the environment?" and we get the answer NO, then it is required by the practice.

absolutely key contextual characteristics of the local settings where the best practice will be transferred to.

Instructions to register, conduct good practice assessment at an online platform and share results with NIJZ

1. STEP – REGISTRATION

- Access the online SCIROCCO tool at: https://scirocco-exchange-tool.inf.ed.ac.uk/en_gb/
- Click on LOGIN/REGISTER button
- Click on REGISTER
- Provide personal information and define 8-character password in the Registration section
- Click on Register (You should instantly receive confirmation mail to your e-mail inbox)

2. STEP – COMPLETING INDIVIDUAL GOOD PRACTICE ASSESSMENT

- When you are logged in, click on INTEGRATED CARE ASSESSMENTS button at navigation menu
- Then click on GOOD PRACTICE ASSESSMENTS
- Proceed by clicking on CREATE NEW PRIVATE GOOD PRACTICE ASSESSMENT button
- You have entered the individual Maturity assessment section and now you are ready to start, please see Figure 2!

Eng

Maturity Assessment

The objective of this page is to assess the maturity requirements of good practices. This is what the good practice needs from its environment in order for it to be possible to carry out the good practice.

Questions marked with * are compulsory. Please fill in the 'Assessment' tab, and then the 'Country/region' tab.

Assessment name (optionally, provide your name or stakeholder group):
 ttest[Country/region][GoodPractice] 10chars max

Assessment Country/region*

D1 D2 D3 D4 D5 D6 D7 D8 D9 D10 D11 D12

1. Readiness to Change ⓘ

0- No acknowledgement of compelling need to change
 1- Compelling need is recognised, but no clear vision or strategic plan
 2- Dialogue and consensus-building underway; plan being developed
 3- Vision or plan embedded in policy; leaders and champions emerging
 4- Leadership, vision and plan clear to the general public; pressure for change
 5- Political consensus; public support; visible stakeholder engagement

Please indicate the requirements of the domain which justify your reply:*

Save

Fig. 8. Starting page of the maturity assessment using SCIROCCO online tool

- Below the Assessment button, you will find the 12 Dimensions with corresponding scale 0-5 and a text box where you provide justification for your response. You can move between questions (per dimension) by clicking on the blue buttons (D1, D2, D3 ...)
- To help you understand the scope of each dimension, there is a narrative explanation available by clicking on information icon next to the dimension name, please see Figure 3:

Fig. 9. Information icon opens narrative explanation of the dimension

- Once you select a number on a scale that best reflects your idea about the maturity requirement in question, you can observe the change in the spider diagram as seen in the picture, please see Figure 4.

Fig. 10. Selection of the response for the respective dimension

- Complete the assessment using scale AND providing justifications in the text box for each of the 12 dimensions.
- Then click on the Country/region button, please see Figure 5.

Fig. 11. Selecting Country/Region

- In this section fill in the missing information by selecting appropriate item from the existing list (Country/region – Netherlands; Good practice – ReverseDiabetes2Now). Click the SAVE button. Please see Figure 6.

Maturity Assessment

The objective of this page is to assess the maturity requirements of good practices. This is what the good practice needs from its environment in order for it to be possible to carry out the good practice.

Questions marked with * are compulsory. Please fill in the 'Assessment' tab, and then the 'Country/region' tab.

Assessment name (optionally, provide your name or stakeholder group):

ttest[Country/region][GoodPractice]

Assessment

Please choose your country/region:*

Good practice: *

Fig. 12. Selecting the practice

3. STEP – SHARE YOUR RESULTS

- After clicking on the SAVE button, a pop-up window will appear. Choose the option SHARE ASSESSMENT WITH OTHER USERS and click SUBMIT, please see Figure 7.

Fig. 13. Saving and sharing results

- A window SHARE ASSESSMENT will appear. In the box below type the e-mail address denis.opresnik@nijz.si and select EDITOR option. Then click SHARE, please see Figure8.

Share Assessment

If you are the editor of an assessment, this page allows you to:

- Share your assessment with somebody else who has an account, by providing the person's email address and choosing whether he/she will be a viewer or editor of the assessment. You can later decide to change the person's role, or even un-share the assessment with the person.
- Share your assessment publicly with all users, for viewing only (i.e. they will not be able to edit it). You can later decide to remove the public sharing of your assessment.

Users who share assessment DOPreNetherlRD2Ntest

USER	ROLE
denis.opresnik@nijz.si (you)	Editor, originator

The assessment is not currently shared with other users

Share with individuals

Share with your communities

Share publicly

Please indicate the email addresses of the user(s) whom you would like to share the assessment with:

Viewer

Editor

Fig. 14. Sharing the results with NIJZ team

- You can check and download the individual assessment you completed by again clicking on INTEGRATED CARE ASSESSMENTS button at navigation menu. Then click on GOOD PRACTICE ASSESSMENTS. In the picture, at the bottom right corner, you can see your assessment you already shared with us. You can export a PDF or Excel file on your computer by clicking on the respective icons or make changes to your assessment and further share the results. Please see Figure 9.

Fig. 15. Saving the individual results

Congratulations! You have completed the individual good practice assessment using SCIROCCO TOOL. The next step will be to assess the results in a dedicated consensus-building workshop at Voeding Leeft. Looking forward to meeting you there!

NIJZ team

2.4. Guide to conduct SCIROCCO consensus-building workshop

Final guidance defined: *date*

Core research team: *names, institutions*

Respondents: *names, institutions*

Steps and timeline: *described in sufficient detail*

Box 5. Example from C4D

Guidance document development (final version : January 2023: NIJZ team: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec; Participants at SCIROCCO Consensus-building workshop - VL team: Barbara Kerstens, Program director, Emma Coles, Data and Care Relations Director, Project Manager, Lotte Shaffer, operational manager, Nynke van der Zijl, Head of medical team, David Bakx, Regional manager of care relations, Nathalie Wilmsen, Research Coordinator, Minke den Hollander, nurse medical team, Mirjam Blijleven, program coordinator, Maud Verburgh, program coordinator. Timeline: all individual online assessments already collected; Workshop: February 3 2023, during on-site study visit; After the workshop: a summary report, due date: end of February 2023; detailed report (within the final report on in-depth review of best practice (Deliverable 5.1)), due date June 2023.

This section presents information used in a format of Powerpoint presentation during the on-site study visit, specifically as supporting materials to conduct SCIROCCO consensus building workshop with the same participants that conducted online individual SCIROCCO assessments.

The presentation consists of general information on the use of SCIROCCO Tool, the purpose and objectives of the workshop, information acquired through the individual assessments (in the form of individual spider diagrams, combined scoring and combined justifications). This information is used as a trajectory for discussion and consensus building that ultimately resulted in the definition of key maturity required.

Introduction

SCIROCCO Tool

- **WHAT:** an online self-assessment tool to address the challenge of adoption and scaling up of good practices in healthcare, developed for integrated care (can also be used for good practices in other areas).

- **WHY:** to ease the adoption of practices by: defining maturity (readiness) to adopt the good practice; assessing the maturity of VL practice; and assessing maturity requirements for

implementation of the good practice (as a follow-up to online individual good practice assessments).

- **WHERE to:** to help future implementers in CARE4DIABETES when analysing their contexts. The maturity requirements will be used to understand if adoption of the best practice is feasible and to what extent the adaptation is needed in their local setting.

Process and expected outcomes

- all individual online assessments should be already collected
- after this workshop: a report on context characteristics including individual and consensus-based visual diagrams to be used for implementers to analyse their contexts against identified maturity requirements and potentially adopt the practice. Due date: *defined*.
- The detailed results will also be presented within the final report. Due date: *defined*.

Results will be used to offer guidance on implementation of VL practice in pilot countries of CARE4DIABETES.

1. Collection of individual SCIROCCO assessments

Individual SCIROCCO assessments are collected. For an example from C4D, please see Figure 10. Please see also Attachment II for more details on example from C4D.

Fig. 16. Individual SCIROCCO assessments shown as spider diagrams, example from C4D

2. Combined results of individual SCIROCCO assessments

Individual scores per each SCIROCCO dimension are then presented as a spider diagram below to show commonalities and differences among individual assessments. For an example from C4D, please see Figure 11.

Fig. 17. Individual SCIROCCO assessments shown in a joint spider diagram, example from C4D

3. Discussion and consensus on the scores per each SCIROCCO dimension

In the next step, complete results of individual assessments (including scoring and justifications) are presented to the group using a dedicated template, please see Figure 12 and Figure 13 as C4D example. Moderator briefly summarizes key points and leads the discussion toward the consensus regarding the score of the particular dimension and justification.

Dimension	Justification
No. X	- xxx (insert all individual justifications as bulletpoints)
Scores	
0:	
1:	
2:	
3:	
4:	
5:	

Fig. 18. Combined individual SCIROCCO assessments showing scores and justifications, blank template

Dimension	Justification
<p>2</p> <p>STRUCTURE & GOVERNANCE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not widely implemented, more on regional level • / • For a long time, it is unclear who is in charge of change. We go from one agency to another and no one can tell who is ultimately the decision-maker. • If we want to start training health care professionals who will do the program this is very important. Otherwise too much time will be lost in politics. • It has to be clear which path we have to follow. • To implement a pilot, in the first setting on a small scale, informal partnerships between different disciplines are needed for in the first line health care. Collaboration is needed to successful implement in a healthcare clinic or so. • The board is involved with the plans and strategy from Voeding Leefft. • There are small scale and larger scale structures to implement lifestyle medicine, but there is still a lot of improvement possible.
Scores	
0 ●	
1 ●	
2 ● ●	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final:
3 ●	
4 ● ●	
5 ●	

Fig. 19. Combined individual SCIROCCO assessments showing scores and justifications, example from C4D

4. Final result - SCIROCCO spider diagram with consensus-based scoring

Final results are then presented using Online and Excel versions of the blank SCIROCCO spider diagram (available at https://scirocco-exchange-tool.inf.ed.ac.uk/en_gb/), where scoring can be inserted in real time and is appropriate to use during the workshop. Based on the scoring results, three main maturity requirements are selected to produce recommendations.

Fig. 20. SCIROCCO spider diagram

5. Key contextual SCIROCCO dimensions for successful VL implementation including justifications

Insights from individual assessments and discussion within consensus building workshop are used to inform this recommendations-building step that are summarised in template, shown as Table 5. They identify three main contextual SCIROCCO dimensions for successful VL implementation including justifications.

Table 5 - Key contextual SCIROCCO dimensions for successful VL best practice implementation including justification

KEY CONTEXTUAL REQUIREMENTS	
Maturity requirement 1	
Name of contextual dimension (SCIROCCO):	
Justifications:	
Maturity requirement 2	
Name of contextual dimension (SCIROCCO):	

Justifications:	
Maturity requirement 3	
Name of contextual dimension (SCIROCCO):	
Justifications:	

2.5. Guide for semi-structured interview on elements of sustainability*

*data gathered that is related to sustainability, is not included in this report, but will be used in activities within work package on sustainability within C4D.

Final guidance defined: *date*

Core research team: *names, institutions*

Respondents: *names, institutions*

Steps and timeline: *described in sufficient detail*

Box 6. Example from C4D

Guidance document development (final version: January 2023) NIJZ team: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec; Participants: Interviewers: Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik; 1st interview: Barbara Kerstens, Program director, Emma Coles, Data and Care Relations Director and Project Manager (Background in business and management); 2nd interview: Nicole de Groot, Nurse Medical Team (background in nursing), Connie Hoek, dietitian expert, with VL from start, program developer; Timeline: Interviews: February 2 2023, during on-site study visit; detailed report (within the final report on in-depth review of best practice (Deliverable 5.1)), due date June 2023.

Duration of each interview is approximately 1h.

Procedure and Questionnaire

Thank you for taking the time to have this interview with us. Its purpose is to understand a bit more, how the VL best practice managed to stay alive and thrive for this long. The messages from your story and experiences you have will be important to the pilot implementers in CARE4DIABETES when thinking about which steps should they take to assure sustainability of their practices. Together, we will guide them in this process in a very structured way (as we

dedicated an entire work package to sustainability), but it all starts by learning from your experiences.

*If you agree, we would record this interview and make notes for the purposes of analysis. Before we communicate your messages with others within CARE4DIABETES, we will share the interview report to you for possible revisions. At any point during our discussion we can stop the recording or you can make explicit request, if some statements should not be reflected within the report. The interview will take approx. 1h to complete. *Recording starts. One interviewer leads the interview, the second one takes care of notes, recording device and poses sub-questions where appropriate.*

At the beginning, please explain what is **your role** within VL and within VL best practice in particular? **When** did you join the VL? *The question might be redundant, depends on how the visit will be structured.

Please, take us back to the **practice beginnings**. What is **the story of VL best practice** (from your perspective)? (Alternatively: How it all started? What was the trigger?)

KEY QUESTION: (After that first push, excitement, engagement) **what do you think were the most important aspects that kept the practice alive, so to say?**

Consider (if not covered in initial response) the role/impact/support of:

- Champions:
- Increasing/building capacities:
- Networks (including policy makers, institutions):
- Patients/target groups (engagement, needs, accessibility)
- Policies, external funds:
- Communication, visibility:
- Adjustments/Mitigating actions to overcome potential barriers:

Is there **anything else** that might have influenced the sustainability of your practice that we did not address? (Consider: unexpected events, stakeholders' support, success stories)

Having all this experiences in mind, **would you do anything differently** when developing and implementing your practice?

What would be your **recommendations for future implementers** (that will be adopting/adapting your practice) in terms of building the sustainability potential of their practices?

At the end, we would like to have your take on the **key elements of sustainability** we have been using in a similar Joint Action and have been identified with the support of collaborating best practices. These elements are framed as (**each element to be explained more freely*):

1. Policy environment: Policy frameworks and vertical linkages were essential in assuring the practice sustainability
2. Sustainability ownership: Holders of sustainability are present at different levels of operation
3. Culture of collaboration and consensus seeking: Culture is an imperative contextual factor that influences the implementation and sustainability of practices

Do you think these elements sufficiently reflect what was presented and discussed by you today or is there something missing, should something be phrased differently etc.? Please, give us your thoughts.

This concludes our interview. Thank you!

3. Final results presentation

Final results are presented as short texts, spider diagram or tables.

Description of the objectives and the core features of VL practice:

Short texts and tables, describing the elements as defined in the Chapter 2.1.

Description of the implementation process of VL best practice (CFIR elements)

Final descriptions are informed by outcomes of CFIR-informed focus group and semi-structured interviews. Data is grouped and shown using predetermined implementation research framework CFIR, please see Table 6 as a summary table, and Tables 7 to 11 showing key constructs per each domain including justification. Most relevant key constructs per domain were chosen based on the previous understanding of VL best practice. (For more details on full analysis of C4D as an example please see Attachment III).

Table 6 - Summary of key characteristics of the implementation process using Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research

Domain	Description
Intervention characteristics	

Outer setting	
Inner setting	
Characteristics of individuals	
Process	

Table 7 - Characteristics of the intervention, key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Intervention source	
Evidence Strength & Quality	
Relative advantage	
Adapatability	
Trialability	
Complexity	
Cost	

Table 8 - Outer setting: key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Patient Needs & Resources	
Cosmopolitanism	
External Policy & Incentives	

Table 9 - Inner setting: key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Networks & Communications	
Culture	
Implementation Climate	
Compatibility	

Key constructs	Justification
Goals & Feedback	
Learning Climate	
Leadership Engagement	
Access to Knowledge & Information	

Table 10 - Characteristics of individuals: key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Knowledge & Beliefs about the Intervention	
Self-efficacy	
Individual Identification with Organization	

Table 11 - Process: key constructs with justification

Key constructs	Justification
Planning	
Engaging	
Formally Appointed Internal Implementation Leaders	
Champions	
Reflecting & Evaluating	

In addition, several other aspects can be covered, such as:

- Main successes and challenges
- Individual characteristics of sustainability (reported in the work of WP4)
- Recommendations for future implementers, such as guiding questions to facilitate self-reflection of the team throughout implementation process, and general advice.

Description of context characteristics and minimum maturity requirements for VL practice implementation) using SCIROCCO approach

Main result of assessment of the context is based on consensus-scoring of SCIROCCO dimensions, showing the relative importance of maturity requirements, as spider diagram, please see Figure 15. Key main contextual SCIROCCO dimensions for successful VL implementation including justifications, based on the three most important requirements are then reported as a Table, please see Table 12. (For more details on intermediate analyses of C4D as an example please see Attachment II)

Fig. 21. Spider diagram with consensus-based scoring on SCIROCCO maturity requirements

Table 12 - Key contextual SCIROCCO dimensions for successful VL best practice implementation including justification

KEY CONTEXTUAL REQUIREMENTS	
Maturity requirement 1	
Name of contextual dimension (SCIROCCO):	
Justifications:	
Maturity requirement 2	
Name of contextual dimension (SCIROCCO):	

Justifications:	
Maturity requirement 3	
Name of contextual dimension (SCIROCCO):	
Justifications:	

4. List of attachments

Attachment I. Agenda of on-site study visit

Attachment II. Individual SCIROCCO assessments showing scores and justifications, per each dimension.

Attachment I. Agenda of on-site study visit

Table 1 - Detailed overview of the program – Day 1 (February 2nd 2023)

Time	Activity
10.00 – 10.30	Arrival at Voeding Leeft office - Dutch welcome and office tour
10.30 – 12.30	CFIR based focus group - About the implementation process
12.30 – 13.30	Lunch at Voeding Leeft office - with team Voeding Leeft
13.30 – 14.30	Travel to location program Reverse Diabetes2 Now
14.30 – 15.00	Cycling tour - From Driebergen-Zeist station to location Better Meetings, Austerlitz
15.00 - 15.30	Arriving & welcome at Better Meetings Austerlitz - Tour
15.30 – 16.30	Insights Reverse Diabetes2 Now program and reflection
16.30 – 17.00	Break
17.00 – 18.00	First round in depth interview
18.00 – 18.30	Insights program Reverse Diabetes2 Now - Cooking workshop - blood glucose measurement
18.30 – 19.30	Dinner at location Better Meetings, Austerlitz
19.30 – 20.30	Second round in depth interview
20.30 – 21.00	Cycling back to Driebergen-Zeist
21.00 -	Train to Amsterdam Central

Table 2 - Detailed overview of the program – Day 2 (February 3rd 2023)

Time	Activity
09.00	Arrival at Voeding Leeft office

09.30 - 11.30	Scirocco consensus-building workshop
11.30 – 12.30	Third round in depth interview
12.30 – 13.30	Lunch at the office with Dutch treat
13.30 – 14.00	Surprising closing activity
14.00 -	End program

Attachment II. Individual SCIROCCO assessments showing scores and justifications, per each dimension.

Dimension	Justification
<div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p data-bbox="263 689 284 719">1</p> <div style="background-color: #1a2b4d; color: white; padding: 5px; margin-top: 10px;">Scores</div> <p data-bbox="263 936 284 965">0 ●</p> <p data-bbox="263 1003 284 1032">1 ● ●</p> <p data-bbox="263 1070 284 1099" style="color: red;">2 ● ● ●</p> <p data-bbox="263 1137 284 1167">3 ●</p> <p data-bbox="263 1205 284 1234">4 ●</p> <p data-bbox="263 1272 284 1301">5</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> They have to be open for change, but if they don't know how it's fine. We can show them. The need to address the problem of diabetes should be present. In between answer 1 and 2. There is a need for change and there are stakeholders, but not in every division. It takes a long time to make the change. But we see a switch in health care and more attention for prevention. With the help of ambassadors and leading doctors a first group of health care professionals can be selected for training who will select the patients that are suitable for the program. The awareness that lifestyle medicine needs to be integrated in regular care to make future care more sustainable and effective is increasing. Recently, a plan has been developed with specified goals. This is now being implemented, but still in an initial stage. The authorities are at first turn benevolent and do not see the need for change. The system is not set up to change. Through the information and studies we provide over the years, movement is slowly coming. The whole process takes years and slowly there seems to be a slight sense of urgency. In the healthcare environment needs to be recognition for the urgency of the problem. That is, the increase in costs and raising number of people with diabetes type 2. Which makes healthcare quality, sustainability and affordable impossible in the future. Recognition that there needs to be a different approach in healthcare. Instead of symptom control to solving the cause. Creating willingness and openness for a new, different approach - to lifestyle medicine. It's the most necessary part for the implementation of the pilot. From that point, in the next phases vision and strategy can be developed. Task is clear, teams are ready to make a change. <p>Final:</p>

Fig. 1. Dimension Readiness for change

Dimension	Justification
<p data-bbox="261 495 284 526">2</p> <p data-bbox="320 539 421 573">STRUCTURE & GOVERNANCE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not widely implemented, more on regional level • / • For a long time, it is unclear who is in charge of change. We go from one agency to another and no one can tell who is ultimately the decision-maker. • If we want to start training health care professionals who will do the program this is very important. Otherwise too much time will be lost in politics. • It has to be clear which path we have to follow. • To implement a pilot, in the first setting on a small scale, informal partnerships between different disciplines are needed for in the first line health care. Collaboration is needed to successful implement in a healthcare clinic or so. • The board is involved with the plans and strategy from Voeding Leeff. • There are small scale and larger scale structures to implement lifestyle medicine, but there is still a lot of improvement possible. <p data-bbox="467 801 544 824">• Final:</p>
<p data-bbox="261 618 331 640">Scores</p> <p data-bbox="261 689 284 721">0 ●</p> <p data-bbox="261 757 284 788">1 ●</p> <p data-bbox="261 824 284 855">2 ● ●</p> <p data-bbox="261 891 284 922">3 ●</p> <p data-bbox="261 958 284 990">4 ● ●</p> <p data-bbox="261 1025 284 1057">5 ●</p>	

Fig. 2. Dimension Structure and governance

Fig. 3. Dimension Digital infrastructure

Dimension	Justification
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">4</div> </div> <div style="margin-top: 10px;"> <p>Scores</p> <p>0</p> <p>1</p> <p>2 ● ● ●</p> <p>3 ●</p> <p>4 ● ● ●</p> <p>5 ●</p> </div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We have realized different manuals and handbooks for the program. • Point 2 For process coordinator in all phases - inclusion and program run in the pilot phase - there must be followed protocols in medical advice and when to act. • A lot of guidelines in the healthcare sector. • The process has been unclear for a long time and now the process seems easier for a subsequent provider. • It makes it a lot easier if there's a route we need to take to embed it. • If standard diabetes care processes are in place these can be used. Ideally lifestyle is recognized as a tool to manage diabetes. • I think we are doing a pretty good job at this point, but improvements can be made. • We have learned in the past ten years what works and what doesn't. Basically the program only needs small local adjustments. <p>Final:</p>

Fig. 4. Dimension Process coordination

Dimension	Justification
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">5</div> </div> <div style="margin-top: 10px;"> <p>Scores</p> <p>0</p> <p>1 ● ● ● ●</p> <p>2 ●</p> <p>3</p> <p>4 ● ● ● ●</p> <p>5 ●</p> </div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are different flows. For pilot programs and for the regular Keer diabetes 2 om program • For follow up; recognition and results, helpful for the pilot is a sustainable cash flow. Because of the duration of behavior change and the program effectiveness on the long term (which is needed for scaling up to demonstrate), it determines if follow up could be possible. • Funding initially came from a budget from the ministry of economic affairs, not social affairs. However, this injection is far too small for implementation. Ot was ultimately the insurers who supported via innovation budget. • The government has a budget for innovation and implementation of new ideas for health care, but it is hard to receive part of this budget and this is mostly for pilot projects. To my knowledge, there is not really a sustainable source for organizations like Reverse Diabetes2 Now to implement this on a larger scale. • It takes a lot of effort to train the teams and to start the program. In Hong Kong we experienced that although the program was very successful, without a solid financial plan for the long term the program won't continue. • The subsidy is most of the time for pilots. When the data and the results are good, sometimes a long term subsidy will be given. • Reverse Diabetes2 Now has a combination of donation and national funding with reimbursement schemes but started with pilot funding. • It is important that there is time (and therefore money) to implement something in healthcare. <p>Final:</p>

Fig. 5. Dimension Finance and funding

Dimension	Justification
<p>6</p> <p>REMOVAL OF INHIBITORS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People have to be willing / flexible to be able to avoid problems. • There is awareness of inhibitors but many are still in place. • Even after all these years, there are a lot of obstacles we are facing in the health care sector. • We have learned from our program in Hong Kong and India and should be able to develop a tool for common obstacles and how to deal with them. • I think we are aware of obstacles and that we (theoretically) know what we can do about it, but putting this into practice on a larger scale is still hard. • There is insufficient understanding of the force field. • An realistic strategy about possible barriers and obstacles needs to be thought of. • We think in possibilities.
Scores	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final:
0	
1 ●●●●	
2 ●	
3	
4 ●●●●●	
5	

Fig. 6. Dimension Removal of inhibitors

Dimension	Justification
<p>7</p> <p>POPULATION APPROACH</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We do small projects, for example in one GP practice • Research beforehand is needed to indicate the number of possible pilot participants. Needs and possibility in recruiting specific patients groups, because of specific inclusion criteria for participating in the pilot study. It might be better to have tighter inclusion criteria in the first pilot studies. • The need for population-based approaches is not felt and even professionals working with integrated approaches do not work sufficiently with population-based approaches. • This strategy is gaining more and more attention, but is not yet being put into practice on a large scale. More research needs to be done. • This is an intensive program. Local teams need to be trained and experience the effect with the patient with Type 2 diabetes. In a later stadium other patients with the metabolic syndrome for instance can be helped as well.
Scores	
0 ●	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are a lot of initiatives but more regional and not for everyone! There is a switch to more prevention in stead of symptom control. • Diabetes patients, COPD patients and cardiovascular patients get specific support which means diabetes is recognized as an important disease burden and the nurses in this existing care system can be educated about the impact of lifestyle and lifestyle programs.
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • /
2 ● ●	
3 ● ● ●	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final:
4 ● ●	
5	

Fig. 7. Dimension Population approach

Dimension	Justification
<p>8</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • / • Citizens have access to data and are able to choose to follow the programme and then get approval from their doctor. • This is one of the most important questions, but there is not enough focus on this aspect. • Empowerment is very important in the program, the patient needs to get back in the driver seat. • I know self direction is believed to be important in our health care, but the possibilities to actively do this are still limited in my opinion. People are mostly dependent on the expertise of their doctor/specialist. However, shared decision making is gaining popularity. • There is insufficient information on the importance of self-direction. An example is the communication during corona, here little was said about what people can do besides a vaccine or themselves. • This is very important for setting up the pilot. Empowerment is a big item in the pilot program, because of the self empowerment people need to have in their own progress and successfulness in the pilot program. They need to have access in their own medical information and data. • We have our own community, so people are able to find information they need. It would be great if we can make a tool for people with different language/ lower social status as well. • Final:
Scores	
0	
1 ● ●	
2 ●	
3 ● ● ● ● ●	
4 ●	
5	

Fig. 8. Dimension Citizen empowerment

Dimension	Justification
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">9</div> </div> <div style="margin-top: 10px;"> <p>Scores</p> <p>0 ●</p> <p>1 ●</p> <p>2 ●</p> <p>3 ●</p> <p>4 ●●●●</p> <p>5</p> </div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the determination of the successfulness, evaluation needs to be existent in the health care context. • I think we are very good at collecting data and evaluating, but I am not sure whether we make use of the learnings from these evaluations enough. Also, I doubt whether the results are systematically published. • Not sure. • / • The program is being evaluated by the members of the program as well as the results. • There is hardly any attention ear here, nor is it on the agenda. • Only by collecting data you can improve the program. It is also very helpful in the financial discussion. • There is no standard evaluation of integrated care services which makes it difficult to compare the results to the results of lifestyle programmes. <p>• Final:</p>

Fig. 9. Dimension Evaluation methods

Dimension	Justification
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 20px;">10</div> <div style="border: 1px solid red; padding: 5px; background-color: #f08080; text-align: center; color: white;"> <p>BREADTH OF AMBITION</p> </div> </div> <div style="margin-top: 20px;"> <p>Scores</p> <p>0 ●</p> <p>1 ● ●</p> <p>2 ● ● ● ●</p> <p>3 ●</p> <p>4</p> <p>5</p> </div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • / • Not at every place. • In my opinion the different levels of our health care system operate to much on their own (also within the levels, different specialists for example), and combining care of different levels can be hard for patients. The convenience for patients is not a priority. • / • There is room for improvement. • It is often still the patient himself who indicates that he wants things to be different. A handful of doctors work or own initiative this way, but it is not encouraged in any other way. • This will improve during the program. • The programm is embedded within primary care - the doctor or nurse has to approve patients participation and the programm nurse has direct contact with the patient's nurse or doctor. <p>• Final:</p>

Fig. 10. Dimension Breadth of ambition

Dimension	Justification
<p>11</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is insufficient overview of best practices and insufficient collaboration or a need to explore together what is possible. • Voeding Lefeft always tries to innovate and improve the program. • Innovation is considered important and the government has a large budget available to support organizations with their innovation projects. You can apply to receive part of this budget. • Innovation is difficult. Insurers have tariffs they can use for innovation which has supported Reverse Diabetes2 Now. • They have to be open for new innovations. • I don't know if we have an innovation board of if there is a plan for innovation. I know that we innovate by what we do! • More focus on initiatives. • Continuous loop of innovation is in the pilot process needed. Plan could be developed.
Scores	
0	
1 ●●●●●	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final:
2 ●	
3 ●	
4 ●●	
5	

Fig. 11. Dimension Innovation management

Dimension	Justification
<p>12</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the first pilot phases, learnings on a small scale for the implementers is first priority. • Within the programme there is significant capacity building - training of nurses and doctors. • Investing in people is necessary. • We stay up to date with information about the development in the field. We train our own staff. • If this is the case it would be excellent. In Hong Kong we experienced that the trained team was too small and it depended too much on these people who were not able to continue the program on their own. • I think that improvements can be made here. • There is hardly any focus on the problem, the possible solution, let alone the capacities to get here. There is no attention to this in the curriculum of education from an early age. Nor for the doctors being trained. • Not sure.
Scores	
0	
1 ● ●	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final:
2	
3 ● ● ●	
4 ● ●	
5 ●	

Fig. 12. Dimension Capacity building

6.2. Annex II. Methodological guidance document for situational analysis of national/local contexts including main stakeholders

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain.

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1. Background

The purpose of this methodological guidance document is to support C4D pilot countries and their C4D Competent Authorities in assessing the context characteristics, relevant for the successful and sustainable implementation of their C4D pilot practice. Special interest within the context is put on identifying main stakeholders, including assigning their level of involvement (stakeholder analysis).

In developing this methodological approach, the expertise of NIJZ team from other Joint Actions employing the mechanism of best practice transfer was fully engaged (JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE), and supported by recent publication overview, such as the OECD Guidebook on Best Practices in Public Health¹⁹.

There is a plethora of potential frameworks to assess and analyse the context within health and healthcare. However, the timeline to develop the methodological guidance, to provide the support to C4D Competent Authorities responsible to deliver C4D pilot country reports, and allow time to execute the analysis and report back was extremely tight. In outlining the

¹⁹ <https://www.oecd.org/publications/guidebook-on-best-practices-in-public-health-4f4913dd-en.htm>

methodological guidance, we tried to leverage the complexity of methodology for context analysis, timeline and the capacities/competencies of C4D Competent Authorities. Therefore, 2-step SWOT analysis was used as a tool to assess and analyse the characteristics of the context, relevant for C4D pilot practice implementation. National/regional (depending on the structure of the healthcare system within the country) as well as local level contexts were included in the analyses. SWOT is one of the most known and used tools in healthcare, also by type of professionals available within C4D Competent Authorities. These results can be used for strategic decisions and even action planning in next stages of work within C4D.

In addition, the process of these first steps was highly influenced by preliminary analysis of information from in-depth review of VL best practice, as performed during the very first 2 weeks after C4D started. Those main messages were also presented at the Kick-off meeting of C4D to C4D consortium, in coordination with the presentation of the VL best practice by VL, so the partners were already sensitised to the top prerequisites for successful and sustainable implementation. The logics of the methodological approach chosen also supports well all other activities of C4D pilot countries within full duration of C4D, see Figure 1.

C4D Ms	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
calendar	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	
CARE4DIABETES Pilot activities summary																																					
Context analysis review and stakeholder engagement report (M2-M3)		P	P																																		
Implementation plan of the pilot country for Phase I and Phase II (M4-M9)			P	P	P	P	P	P																													
P1 for Phase I (M2 -M11) and phase II (M2-M11)			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X																											
Ethical approval received									X																												
Digital tool in place (portal or similar, for pilots with web-based approach alone or in addition to F2F)										X																											
Patients recruited (pts group A M11, pts group B M20)											X																										
Materials for Phase I and Phase II adapted and available										X																											
C4D practices teams trained										X																											
Monitoring system to follow the results and experiences of all D phases in place										X																											
D1 Phase I, pts group A (M12-M17), D1 Phase II, pts group A (M18-M23)											D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D															
S1+A1+P2 Phase I pts group A (M18-M20)																	S	A	P	S	A	P	S	A	P												
S1+A1+ P2 Phase II, pts group A (M24-M26)																									S	A	P	S	A	P							
Patients recruited (pts group B M20)																		X																			
D2 Phase I, pts group B (M21-M27), D2 Phase II, pts group B (M27 - M32)																							D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	
S2+A2+P3 Phase I, pts group B (M28-M29)																											S	A	P	S	A	P					
Final reporting from implementation experience (SQUIRE 2.0) & outcome and impact analysis (M33)																																			X		
Sustainability plan including action plans for 1-2 years after JA is over (M34)																																				X	

Fig. 1. Timeline of activities planned

2. Stepwise situational analysis of national/local contexts including main stakeholders' analysis

The analysis was performed at country level and took 4 steps: (I) defining C4D pilot local team, (preliminary) multidisciplinary team and their roles, (II) defining shared purpose and the common scope of the C4D pilot practice, (III) identifying supporting and inhibiting

characteristics of the context at national/regional level and at C4D pilot level as well as defining main stakeholders and their level of involvement, and (IV) assessment of the identified characteristics as Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats for the C4D pilot practice implementation with re-definition of the shared purpose and the common scope of the C4D pilot practice based on those insights, if needed.

Step I: C4D pilot local team

- Objectives:
 - to define C4D pilot local team and their roles
 - to define the (preliminary) multidisciplinary team
 - to define the individual prework before the next meeting
- Tacit objectives: to understand strengths of team members, to start developing common attitudes, values and beliefs, to share passion, to build up the sense of cohesion within the team and the openness in communication

Result: C4D pilot local team (an organiser, experts and potentially decision makers) and (preliminary) multidisciplinary team defined, and their roles assigned. Individual prework agreed and questions shared (What would you like to accomplish within the work of C4D? When C4D ends, what would you like to see as the result? What would you like to see that would happen after C4D ends?)

Rationale: preliminary analysis of VL best practice has shown the extreme importance of the team structure, shared beliefs and dynamics. Please see Box 1, how we formulated the message to C4D partners. Roles and hints for composition of C4D pilot local teams and C4D multidisciplinary teams are described in Box 2 and 3, respectively.

Box 1. Ideal C4D team

C4D team should be small, carefully composed, multidisciplinary, with aligned attitudes and beliefs in several areas, such as:

Shared attitude regarding the philosophy of lifestyle change in type 2 diabetes

Attitude towards the participants of the course: no blaming of participants, philosophy of empowerment, active involvement of participants, „let the participant tell the story“, adapt to the capability of the participants

Innovators

High level of readiness for change, sincere positive attitude towards reflective process, to monitoring and evaluation within the team, to be in constant communication regarding individual participants of the course and on „meta-learning“, what goes well and what not, constant participation in process of improvement of the practice (checklists, surveys, narratives)

Flexible, able to adjust

Patient to see the results (because they do not come immediately)

Resilient (as a team)

Passionate

Understands the context within country/region/setting of the C4D practice

And is able to co-create using 4A approach (adopt-adapt-abandon-add)

Box 2. Roles of C4D pilot local team

- Works on the tasks foreseen by Grand Agreement, such as defines the purpose/aim/general objective, scope, reviews context and identifies & involves stakeholders, designs the C4D practice for your setting and develops first implementation plan (Plan), develops digital approach if included, defines recruitment strategy, translates and adapts materials for patients and for training of healthcare professionals, is involved in train-the- training, designs monitoring system, leads process to gain ethical approval; monitors the implementation (Do) itself at different levels, executes analytical steps (Study, Act), and refines the implementation plans (next Plan), develops final report and sustainability plan.
- It is the core team in collaborative learning and knowledge generation.
C4D pilot local team consists of:
- Organiser (understands in depth C4D and communicates with Competent Authority team; MEETINGS: prepares, (incl. invitations, agenda, reporting) and chairs; C4D REPORTS: drafts, reaches consensus, delivers))

- Experts: with knowledges, skills (medicine), are at power positions (...and have time), experts in social sciences, experts in running methodologies (SWOT, PDSA, SQUIRE 2.0 etc), have experiences from projects executing the actual implementation, are „able“ for 4A approach, can motivate and empower, equip and support multidisciplinary team; it is possible/advisable to have some members in both teams
- Decision-maker(s) – potentially: to eliminate bottlenecks during the implementation of C4D practice, provide strategic vision, to support implementation process through the focus of the system, sustainability, scalability – BUT they have to have time.

Box 3. Roles of C4D multidisciplinary team

- Runs the C4D pilot practice with the patients (implements it=Do), provides feedback and reflections, shares experiences on real life practice
- Participates in continuous monitoring and assessment of implementation practice
- Participates in collaborative learning and knowledge generation

Step II: C4D pilot local team's scope

- Objectives:
 - o To define the shared purpose/aim/general objective of C4D pilot practice
 - o To define the common scope of C4D pilot practice
- Tacit objective: to develop common attitudes, values and beliefs, to share passion, to build up the sense of cohesion within the team and the openness in communication, to strengthen the readiness for change, resilience of the team, to run reflective process

Result: Shared purpose/aim/general objective of C4D pilot practice agreed. Common scope of the C4D practice agreed.

Rationale: the preliminary analysis of VL best practice has also shown, that shared expectations of all members of the team (purpose, for working definition used please see Box 4), and common understanding of “is this what we want to achieve” (scope, for working

definition used please see Box 5) are cornerstones for the successful collaboration. Ideally, individual purpose and scope are developed first (as responses to the questions “What would you like to accomplish within the work of C4D? When C4D ends, what would you like to see as the result? What would you like to see that would happen after C4D ends?”), followed by consensus meeting (-s) to agree on shared purpose and common scope. They should be ambitious, feasible and sustainable. It was underlined, that this is an iterative process and the decisions are not final. If there is enormous dissonance, scheduling of another meeting with the same objectives was suggested.

Box 4. Purpose, aim, general objective

These terms are often used interchangeably. The working definitions are:

Purpose= the reason for which something is done or created or for which something exists

Aim= to have the intention to achieve (something)

General objective(s)= predetermined results towards which effort is directed. Objectives are specific (SMART) and may be defined in terms of outputs, outcomes and/or benefits. Often appear at the beginning of a report to inform the reader of its purpose. For example: „This joint action aims to develop and test a practice in lifestyle education for type 2 diabetes in Country by January 2026,,

Box 5. Scope

The working definition is:

Scope = the totality of outputs, outcomes and benefits and the work required to produce them. The scope statement clearly delineates what is in scope (the work required). Everything else is out of scope. The scope thus defines the boundaries of what will and won't be part of the project work within C4D, and has to be aligned to the C4D budget and schedule.

Step III: Context review and main stakeholders' analysis

- Objectives:

- To define positive and negative characteristics related to lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes currently and in the future, at national/regional level and at the local setting, where C4D pilot practice will be implemented
- To define main stakeholders and their level of involvement
- Tacit objective: to develop common attitudes, values and beliefs, to share passion, to build up the sense of cohesion within the team and the openness in communication, to strengthen the readiness for change, resilience of the team, to run reflective process, and to build a common vision.

Results: positive and negative characteristics of the context at national/regional and local level identified. Main stakeholders identified and their level of involvement assigned.

Rationale: awareness and the potential for interaction with impactful characteristics of the context at different levels is essential part of decisions making process of transferring a best practice (please see OECD Guidebook on Best Practices in Public Health). Positive (enabling) and negative (barriers) characteristics are important, and some may be positive and negative at the same time (in this case additional description is needed). They may reflect several views, such as design of the practice, patient empowerment, evaluation, comprehensiveness of the practice, education and training, equity and ethical considerations, governance, interaction with other systems, sustainability and scalability (based on work of JA CHRODIS PLUS). The perceived future changes in the context are as well relevant to increase the potential for sustainability and scalability. The powers to achieve change are frequently positioned outside the institution involved in the project, and stakeholder analysis (identification and assigning the level of involvement) pushes the institutions to work with main stakeholders (for the working definition please see Box 6) as early as possible in the project evolution. For this step, organisers from C4D pilot local team were advised to invite external participants, with the understanding on the full overview at national, regional and local level.

Box 6. Main stakeholders and level of involvement

The working definition is:

Main stakeholders are individuals, institutions or organizations that in any way may show interest for the activity, program, intervention or policy relevant to C4D field, or are affected by the work within C4D, or are important advocates for continuation and potential scalability of C4D pilot practice when C4D Joint Action ends. They can come from different fields and distinct expertise and experience (healthcare, education, research, communication and ICT technology, NGOs, patients' associations and civil society), to be as enriching and comprehensive as possible.

Their level of involvement may be:

- full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D pilot local team list
- consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D pilot local team
- informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process
- briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

Step IV: Re-definition of the scope

- Objectives:
 - o to define strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes
 - o To re-evaluate the shared purpose/aim/general objective and the common scope of C4D pilot practice
- Tacit objective: to develop common attitudes, values and beliefs, to share passion, to build up the sense of cohesion within the team and the openness in communication, to strengthen the readiness for change, resilience of the team, to run reflective process, and to build a common vision

Results: strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to C4D pilot practice implementation identified. Based on this assessment, shared purpose and common scope of C4D pilot practice re-evaluated.

Rationale: in this step, second part of SWOT analysis is performed. The characteristics of the contexts identified in Step III are evaluated through the lens of where the power to have influence resides. Those that are within the power of C4D pilot local team and/or C4D multidisciplinary team are strengths and weaknesses, and others are opportunities and threats. In the light of all insight collected, the C4D pilot local team is encouraged to re-evaluate the shared purpose and common scope by embracing strengths, ceasing the opportunities, minimising weaknesses and minimising the impact of the threats. They should still be ambitious, feasible and sustainable. This report at this stage represents the solid base for strategic decisions for adopt-adapt-abandon-add principle within C4D.

3. Support provided to C4D Competent Authorities and timeline

Due to the very tight timing of first activities within C4D and of their high relevance for the successful work within C4D, NIJZ team and VL team started the work 5-8 months before the actual beginning of the joint action, supported by the coordinators of C4D. The type of support provided to C4D Competent Authorities, that were responsible for this work and reporting is shown in Box 7.

Box 7. Support provided to C4D Competent Authorities

June 2022 – Feb 15 2023: Preparatory work (NIJZ and VL)

February 16 and 17 2023: Kick-off meeting with presentation of top prerequisites for successful and sustainable implementation of C4D pilot practice, including the importance of understanding of the context and main stakeholders at national/regional as well as local level. Workshop on how to assess the components of VL best practice in the light of the C4D pilot country context including main stakeholders, and then making decision on whether to adopt it (implement it as it is), adapt it (first change it to adhere to the contextual characteristics), abandon it (not to implement it at all, since it is not feasible/appropriate/sustainable etc with respect to the contextual characteristics), or add a component, that is assessed to be needed but does not exist in VL best practice.

March 7, 2023: presentations with explanatory video recordings were shared with C4D Competent Authorities on the overview of C4D work over the next 3 years, overview of the immediate activities related to Task 5.1 with deadline April 30 2023 (together with the word template, please see Attachment I, detailed guidance video recording for Step 1, Step 2, Step 3 and Step 4.

March 13, 2023: to further support the work, webinar was held for the members from C4D involved in development and implementation of C4D practices (Competent Authorities and Affiliated Entities). It was also recorded and made available at the shared platform.

March 13 – May 29 2023: additional individual videoconference (1 country), e-mail exchanges and reminders

March 30 2023, April 13 2023, April 27 2023, May 11 2023, May 25 2023: meetings of Task 5.1 NIJZ team and other Steering Committee members with members from C4D Competent Authorities, Affiliated Entities as C4D pilot local team members and/or C4D

multidisciplinary team members to support work within Task 5.1 in addition to other current activities in place.

April 12 2023: activation of ClickUp project management tool (THL and NIJZ) to support timely execution of activities including reminders.

Deadline for delivery of reports: April 30 2023. Last report collected on May 29 2023.

4. Results

The results are presented as tables or as short descriptions. Of note, personal information of members is reported by countries in alignment to national GDPR and other national data protection laws. In this report, unnecessary personal data is not disclosed.

Follow-up of the work:

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I			
II			
III			
IV			
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

Step I:

C4D pilot local team			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser			
Expert 1			
Expert 2			
Decision maker 1			
Decision maker 2			
Add lines if needed			

C4D multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D pilot practice			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator			
Medical doctor1			
Diabetes nurse1			
Dietitian1			
Coach1			
Add lines if needed			

Step II:

Shared purpose/aim/general objective of C4D pilot practice is: *text added*

Common scope of the C4D pilot practice is: *text added*

Step III:

Context analysis at national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative

Context analysis at local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative

Main stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement	Comments

Step IV:

Characteristics of the context within the power of C4D pilot local team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness

Characteristics of the context not within the power of C4D pilot local team and multidisciplinary team, or are in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats

Re-evaluated shared purpose/aim/general objective of C4D pilot practice is: *text added*

Re-evaluated common scope of the C4D pilot practice is: *text added*

List of attachments:

Attachment I Template for Competent Authorities of C4D, WP5, Task 5.1

NAME OF C4D PARTNER WITH PILOT IMPLEMENTATION, supported by NAME OF C4D COMPETENT
AUTHORITY

COUNTRY

Authors: Name1 Surname1, Name2 Surname2,xxx

Date: April 30 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

Contact e-mail: care4diabetes@nijz.si

jelka.zaletel@kclj.si, anja.brunec@nijz.si, denis.opresnik@nijz.si

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	xx	xx	
II	xx	xx	
III	xx	xx	
IV	xxx	xx	
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement date: XXXXX

Meeting participants: Name1 Surname1 Institution1, Name2 Surname2 Institution2...

Aim:

- Objectives:
 - o to define C4D team and their roles
 - o to define the (preliminary) multidisciplinary team
 - o to define the individual prework before the next meeting
- Tacit objective: to understand strengths of team members, to start developing common attitudes, values and beliefs, to share passion, to build up the sense of cohesion within the team and the openness in communication

Tentative timing: 60 min

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser			
Expert 1			
Expert 2			
<i>Decision maker 1</i>			
<i>Decision maker 2</i>			
Add lines if needed			

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator			
Medical doctor1			
Diabetes nurse1			
Dietitian1			
Coach1			
Add lines if needed			

To organiser: just after the meeting share with C4D team members (and at your decision with (some) members of multidisciplinary team) the questions that should be answered by e-mail up until 1 day before the next meeting. Ask each individual member of C4D team to send a few sentences as answers to these questions:

1. What would you like to accomplish within the work of C4D?
2. When C4D ends, what would you like to see as the result?
3. What would you like to see that would happen after C4D ends?

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Prework of all C4D team members, collected by organiser by e-mail before the consensus meeting:

To organiser: Collect the individual answers to these questions and present them briefly at the beginning of the meeting:

1. What would you like to accomplish within the work of C4D?
2. When C4D ends, what would you like to see as the result?
3. What would you like to see that would happen after C4D ends?

Consensus meeting date: xxx

Meeting participants

C4D team members: (Name1 Surname1, Name2 Surname 2,...)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team (Name1 Surname1, Name2 Surname2,...)

Aim:

- Objectives:
 - o To define the shared purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice
 - o To define the common scope of C4D practice
- Tacit objective: to develop common attitudes, values and beliefs, to share passion, to build up the sense of cohesion within the team and the openness in communication, to strengthen the readiness for change, resilience of the team, to run reflective process

Tentative timing: 90 min

To organiser: Collect the individual responses, discuss and agree on shared among C4D members, having in mind C4D Grant Agreement.

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D practice is xxxxxxxxxxxx

Scope of the C4D practice is:

The scope of the practice is xxxxxxxx

To organiser: They should be ambitious, feasible and sustainable. Please, note, that this is an iterative process and the decisions are not final. If there is enormous dissonance, schedule another meeting with the same objectives.

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date(-s): xxx

Meeting participants

C4D team members: (Name1 Surname1, Name2 Surname 2,...)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team (Name1 Surname1, Name2 Surname2,...)

External participants, providing the full overview at national, regional and local level (Name1 Surname1 Institution1 , Name2 Surname2 Institution2,...)

Aim:

- Objectives:
 - o To define positive and negative characteristics related to lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes currently and in the future, at national/regional level and at the local setting, where C4D practice will be implemented
 - o To define key stakeholders and their level of involvement
- Tacit objective: to develop common attitudes, values and beliefs, to share passion, to build up the sense of cohesion within the team and the openness in communication, to strengthen the readiness for change, resilience of the team, to run reflective process, and to build a common vision.

Tentative timing: 90 min (per each meeting)

To organiser: collect several positive and several negative characteristics of current situation in relation to lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes, first focusing to current situation and then to the future:

- At national/regional level
- At the level of the setting, where C4D practice will be implemented

They may reflect several views, such as design of the practice, patient empowerment, evaluation, comprehensiveness of the practice, education and training, equity and ethical considerations, governance, interaction with other systems, sustainability and scalability-

Some characteristics may be positive and negative at the same time – in this explanation is needed.

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1	1	1	1

2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
5	5	5	5

At local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
5	5	5	5

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

To organiser: Please use the following definition of the stakeholder:

Key stakeholders are individuals, institutions or organizations that in any way **may show interest** for the activity, program, intervention or policy relevant to C4D field, or **are affected by the work** within C4D, or are **important advocates for continuation and potential scalability** of C4D practice when C4D Joint Action ends. They can come from different fields and distinct expertise and experience (healthcare, education, research, communication and ICT technology, NGOs, patients' associations and civil society), to be as enriching and comprehensive as possible.

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
xxx			
xxxx			
xxxxx			
Add lines if needed			

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: xxx

Meeting participants

C4D team members: (Name1 Surname1, Name2 Surname 2,...)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team (Name1 Surname1, Name2 Surname2,...)

Aim:

- Objectives:
 - o to define strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes
 - o To re-evaluate the shared purpose/aim/general objective and the common scope of C4D practice
- Tacit objective: to develop common attitudes, values and beliefs, to share passion, to build up the sense of cohesion within the team and the openness in communication, to strengthen the readiness for change, resilience of the team, to run reflective process, and to build a common vision.

Tentative timing: 90 min

To organiser: based on the positive and several negative characteristics in relation to lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes, collected during previous meeting(-s), agree with meeting participants on which are within their power, and which are not or are in the future.

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5

To organiser: Having all this in mind, please re-evaluate with meeting participants if the purpose/aim/general objective and the scope as defined in Step II need to be adapted. They should be ambitious, feasible and sustainable.

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D practice is xxxxxxxxxxxx

Scope of the C4D practice is:

The scope of the practice is xxxxxxxx

6.3. Annex III. Situation analysis of national/regional and local contexts including main stakeholders, per c4d pilot country

List of attachments:

Attachment I Belgium

SCIENSANO CONTEXT REVIEW FOR PILOT IMPLEMENTATION, supported by the SPF Santé Publique and the AVIQ

BELGIUM

Authors: Charlotte Juton, Stefanie Vandevijvere, An-Sofie Vanherwegen

Date: April 30 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

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Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	23/03/2023	Charlotte Juton	
II	23/03/2023	Charlotte Juton	
III	11/04/2023	Charlotte Juton	
IV	27/04/2023	Charlotte Juton	
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement date: 23/03/2023

Meeting participants: Charlotte Juton Sciensano, Stefanie Vandevijvere Sciensano, An-Sofie Vanherwegen Sciensano and Astrid Lavens Sciensano

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Charlotte Juton	Sciensano	Organizer and expert in public health nutrition and determinants of obesity.
Expert 1	Stefanie Vandevijvere	Sciensano	Expert in public health nutrition, disease prevention and health promotion, nutrition policies, upstream determinants of obesity and diabetes.
Expert 2	An-Sofie Vanherwegen	Sciensano	Expert in the convention care pathways for type 2 diabetes.
Expert 3	Astrid Lavens	Sciensano	Expert in the convention care pathways for type 2 diabetes.
<i>Decision maker 1</i>	Léna Frateur	AVIQ*	Health prevention and promotion (first line of care).
<i>Decision maker 2</i>	Caroline Frere	AVIQ*	Health care services (first line of care). In regular contacts with all the local multidisciplinary networks (RML).
<i>Decision maker 3</i>	Laurence Doughan	SPF Santé Publique**	Expert in nutrition, in charge of the nutrition and health plan within the Ministry of Health.

* The Walloon agency for a quality life

** The Federal Service of Public Health, Safety of the Food Chain and the Environment

The composition of the actual multidisciplinary teams has not yet been determined because it will depend on the sites (namely the local multidisciplinary networks (RML))

that will be chosen. However, the different roles that will be included in the multidisciplinary teams are highlighted in the table below.

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator		Maison du Diabète RML Liège and Liège Est RML Grand Namur RML UOAD RML AGRF RML Cegeno	The on-site C4D coordinator is likely to be the coordinator of the RLM (see <i>prior information about the national healthcare system in relation to T2D in Belgium</i> page 9).
Diabetologist – a physician endocrinologist who specializes in the treatment of diabetes mellitus.			The diabetologist could be involved if certain patients with specific inclusion criteria who are part of the care trajectory (see <i>prior information about the national healthcare system in relation to T2D in Belgium</i> page 9) are included in the program.
Medical doctor/General practitioner			The general practitioner will be in charge of selecting and recruiting program participants. Their approval will be required for participants to be part of the program and they will be informed by the nurse or dietitian throughout the program process. They are not directly involved in delivering the program to participants.
Diabetes nurse/educators			A diabetes educator is a nurse, podiatrist, dietician or physical therapist who has completed certified training to deliver diabetes education ¹ .
Dietitian			The dietitian will be in close contact with the diabetes nurse/educator to ensure that treatment is tailored to dietary goals.
Coach			The profession of coach is not recognized in Belgium so we are thinking about possibly calling on a psychologist if available at the institution where the pilot will be implemented.

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Prework of all C4D team members, collected by organiser by e-mail before the consensus meeting:

To organiser: Collect the individual answers to these questions and present them briefly at the beginning of the meeting:

1. What would you like to accomplish within the work of C4D?

We want to effectively manage the adaptation, implementation and evaluation of a pilot lifestyle education program integrated into the health system in Wallonia to offer type 2 diabetes patients support to effectively and sustainably improve their lifestyle behaviours, in addition to current care pathways more oriented towards drug treatment, as well as exploring different ways to sustain the C4D project once completed.

2. When C4D ends, what would you like to see as the result?

Through the implementation of the pilot lifestyle education program, we would like to see the objective and subjective health of patients improve and for the patients to feel more empowered in the control and management of their diabetes. Additionally, we would like to see a multidisciplinary team that can and is motivated to lead group sessions and effectively collaborate with each other. Ideally, we would like to have a plan for the intervention to be sustained and upscaled in Wallonia and Belgium after the C4D project ends.

3. What would you like to see that would happen after C4D ends?

We would like to extend the program to other sites (scalability) in Wallonia and for the government to recognize the need for this lifestyle education program in order to make it reimbursable (sustainability). We would like to see if it could also be suitable for implementation in the Flemish region so as to cover the entire Belgian territory. Already in the consultation phase of the project, we will, where possible, evaluate the suitability of the program for the Flemish region.

Consensus meeting date: 23/03/2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Charlotte Juton Sciensano, Stefanie Vandevijvere Sciensano, An-Sofie Vanherwegen Sciensano and Astrid Lavens Sciensano

The aim of C4D practice is to:

- Reinforce early management of type 2 diabetes patients through an intensive program based on lifestyle changes.
- Improve the health, well-being and quality of life of diabetes patients by enhancing patient's empowerment and self-efficacy.
- Reduce costs associated with increased risk of disability, health-related retirement, and development of patient complications.

The scope of the C4D practice is to improve and promote health in Wallonia by reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and associated risk factors, both at the societal and personal level, through early management of patients with type 2 diabetes through an effective empowering lifestyle education program.

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date(-s): 11/04/2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Charlotte Juton Sciensano, Stefanie Vandevijvere Sciensano, An-Sofie Vanherwegen Sciensano and Astrid Lavens Sciensano

External participants, providing the full overview at national level

Name	Institution	Meeting date(s)
Laurence Doughan	The Federal Service of Public Health, Safety of the Food Chain and the Environment (SPF Santé Publique)	07/02/2023 In contact by email
Yolande Husden	The Walloon Health Minister cabinet	28/04/2023
Marina Libertiaux		
Mike Daubie Pascal Meeus	The National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance (INAMI/RIZIV)	

External participants, providing the full overview at regional level

Name	Institution	Meeting date(s)
Léna Frateur	The Walloon agency for a quality life (AVIQ)	07/02/2023
Caroline Frère		27/03/2023 31/05/2023 In contact by email and phone
Nicole Pirotte	Association Belge du Diabète	20/03/2023
Valérie Heuvelmans		15/04/2023 (Nursing day)
Luk Buyse	Diabetes Liga	24/02/2023
Inge Everaert		03/04/2023 In contact by email
Guy Delrée	The Federation of Associations of General Practitioners of the Walloon region (FAGW)	08/03/2023
Dounia Ouhadid	The Walloon Federation for Health Promotion (FWPS)	06/04/2023
Gaëlle Fonteyne	Promo Santé & MG	14/03/2023
Damiela Viciencio	Chronicopole	20/03/2023
Charlotte Dejehearts	PACT Santé	13/03/2023
Céline Mostade	Chronilux	16/03/2023
Nicolas Mincier	Résinam	

Julie Bechet	Rélian	28/03/2023
Anne-Sofie Lambert	PAQS	03/04/2023

External participants, providing the full overview at local level

Name	Institution	Meeting date(s)
Pierre Christophe Stavaux	RML Maison du Diabète	16/03/2023 In contact by email and phone
Isabelle Polis	RML Cegeno	22/03/2023
Sabrina Gibilaro	RML Liège et Liège Est	31/03/2023 15/04/2023 (Nursing day)
Véronique Szöllösi	RML AGRF	13/04/2023
Séverine Delhaye	RML UOAD	14/04/2023
Delphine Delporte		
Julien Laforge	RML Grand Namur	18/04/2023
Yves Mengal	RML Charleroi	24/03/2023
Axelle Spineux	RML Point Santé	17/03/2023
Christine Delem	RML Mons Borinage	11/04/2023
Maite Dele Pedro	RML Brabant Wallon	

General information about the healthcare system in Belgium

National health services are orchestrated and financed at the federal level by the National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance (INAMI/RIZIV)² and the Federal public service finance (SPF Finances)³ while prevention and health promotion plans are financed by the regional governments and executed by the Walloon agency for a quality life (AVIQ)⁴ in Wallonia and by the Vlaams Instituut Gezond Leven⁵ in Flanders.

Prior information about the national healthcare system in relation to type 2 diabetes in Belgium

With regard to type 2 diabetes, the national healthcare system is divided in three care pathways: pre-trajectory, care trajectory and diabetes convention according to certain criteria.

- The pre-trajectory is intended for newly diagnosed patients who are well controlled on oral antidiabetics.
- The care trajectory includes patients who have insufficient results with oral anti-diabetic medication and for whom insulin treatment is considered or patients who require 1-2 insulin injections per day⁶.
- The diabetes convention trajectory is intended for patients who need at least 3 insulin injections or 2 injections and who have a serious medical condition⁷.

In Wallonia, patients in pre-trajectory and care trajectory are cared for by general practitioners with the support of the local multidisciplinary networks (RML) while patients in diabetes

convention are cared for by diabetologists, endocrinologists specialised in diabetes mellitus, at the hospital.

Prior information about the implementation of new health reforms in Wallonia called Proxisanté⁸

This information is only a very brief summary of the participatory workshops that were carried out to reflect on the Proxisanté reforms. They do not in any way represent the final decree.

The new Walloon health reforms called Proxisanté aim to set up a common governance, a system of integrated care services and to support first line health actors.

A common governance refers to the coordination and collaboration between individuals, actors and organizations in the health sector. In practice, the structures within which health activities are implemented should be divided into three levels: macro, meso and micro. The macro would represent the governmental level, the meso the provincial level and the micro the local level.

An integrated care service system refers to improving the availability of health services according to the needs of the population. The integrated care service should be guided by indicators and be the subject of consultation between the regional and the federal to improve the organization of the care.

Support for frontline health actors includes an improvement and harmonization in the distribution of funding and the financial and digital support to strengthen the communication between the health actors.

The decree Proxisanté will be presented to the Walloon Parliament on June 2023 but should be in force from January 2024.

Co-funded by
the European Union

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 The interactions of the health care system within the framework of Proxisanté What does this mean for the management of patients with T2D?			
1.1	1.2	1.3 For the C4D project we are working in partnership with the AVIQ which is involved in the Proxisanté reforms. They advised us to reach out to the RML.	1.4 The idea of a system of integrated healthcare services and common governance will have an impact on the restructuring of healthcare structures and actors. The more collaborative and integrated they are, the better because they won't need as much effort to restructure. The missions of the RML are not destined to disappear.
2 General governance and project support The C4D has the support of key stakeholders.			
2.1 The project has the support of the SPF Santé Publique, the Walloon health minister cabinet, the INAMI/RIZIV, the AVIQ, the Walloon Federation for Health Promotion (FWPS santé), the Association Belge du Diabète (non-profit organization) and the RML.	2.2	2.3	2.4
3 National healthcare services and project sustainability A national healthcare system that remains too treatment oriented compared to the RD2 program.			
3.1 The healthcare system in Wallonia (and Belgium) is more treatment oriented than prevention oriented.	3.2 Reimbursed T2D related lifestyle interventions in the pre-trajectory and care trajectory are not sufficient: maximum 4 (only for the	3.3 The Reverse diabetes 2 now (RD2) is an intensive lifestyle intervention that could fill up this gap of lack of lifestyle related solutions for the patients and GPs.	3.4 There is a need to demonstrate the cost effectiveness of such lifestyle intervention to make it reimbursable as a lack of reimbursement

	<p>subcategory in the pre-trajectory) or 5 (in the care trajectory) sessions related to diabetes education and maximum 2 dietetic sessions.</p> <p>There is a need to develop efficient intensive lifestyle program based on robust scientific evidence ⁹⁻¹¹.</p> <p>The lack of prevention/lifestyle promotion programs in the national healthcare system hampers the second line of care because general practitioners do not have the knowledge, human resources and tools to refer patients to other more relevant care providers and programs than the specialists.</p>	<p>Besides, the RD2 has demonstrated good scientific results ^{12,13}.</p> <p>RD2 data from third-party payers shows good results in drug reduction (Annex 1, Figure 1).</p>	<p>could seriously question the sustainability of the program.</p> <p>Guidelines recommend the reimbursement of such program by “third-party payers or bundled in evolving value-based care and payment models”¹¹.</p>
<p>4 National health services The pre-trajectory care is experiencing positive developments.</p>			
<p>4.1 T2D prevention care in the pre-trajectory and care trajectory includes maximum 2 dietician sessions, maximum 2 podiatrist sessions (for people at risk) and 5 diabetes education sessions (only for the care trajectory) per year ^{14,15}.</p>	<p>4.2 In the pre-trajectory, only a subcategory of patients, i.e. patients aged 15 to 69 with a high cardiovascular risk associated with a BMI > 30 and/or arterial hypertension¹⁶, can benefit from 4 reimbursed diabetes education sessions per year tailored to the needs (given by diabetes educators, dieticians, nurses, physiotherapists or pharmacists)¹⁵ in addition to the 2 dietician sessions and the 2 podiatrist sessions for people at risk.</p> <p>The pre-trajectory care is rarely initiated by general</p>	<p>4.3 New modalities are expected in the pre-trajectory (renamed start trajectory) in June 2023 but they still need to be confirmed. It is likely that the 4 diabetes education sessions will be accessible and reimbursed for all pre-trajectory patients, in other words the subcategory will be removed. The first diabetes education session may be mandatory. A reduction in the administrative workload is also expected as well as a review of the flat rates for the educators / nurses specializing in diabetes.</p>	<p>4.4 It is not known whether the flat rates for diabetes education in individual session and group session will both be increased. A simple increase in the flat rate of individual diabetes education sessions could increase the number of individual sessions compared to the number of group sessions and strengthen individual practices.</p>

	<p>practitioners due to the complexity of the subcategory criteria ¹⁶ and the heavy administrative workload. If the pre-trajectory is prescribed, GPs must inform the RML which is not always the case. The pre-trajectory must be renewed by the GP every year.</p> <p>There is a lack of diabetes educators in some areas. They complain of not being able to live from their work because there are few of them for a large region to cover and the commutes are not reimbursed. The INAMI/RIZIV flat rates are therefore not adapted to the reality on the ground. In addition, they have to deal with an overload of paperwork. This profession is in danger and will not be able to provide additional pre-trajectory diabetes education sessions if the flat rates of the consultations are not increased.</p>	<p>According to the GPs, being able to redirect newly diagnosed patients to a diabetes educator will be time saving because they would not have to convince the patients, raise awareness, explain the importance of taking actions to control the evolution of the disease and its complications, its pathophysiology, etc.</p> <p>Other professions such as dietitians, nurses or physiotherapists should be involved in lifestyle intervention programs. RD2 relies on professions other than diabetes educators, which could take some pressure off their shoulders.</p>	
<p>5 Flemish and Walloon health promotion initiatives related to type 2 diabetes</p> <p>A lack of security in funding.</p>			
<p>5.1</p>	<p>5.2 In the Flemish region, the executive regional agency of the Agentschap Zorg en Gezondheid ¹⁷, the Vlaams Instituut Gezond Leven ⁵, has developed in partnership with the Diabetes Liga ¹⁸ the movement on referrals initiative that aims to prescribe physical activity for T2D patients ¹⁹ as well as</p>	<p>5.3</p>	<p>5.4 The HALT2DIABETES program ²⁴ in Flanders receives programme-based funding by the Agentschap Zorg en Gezondheid ¹⁷, which means that once the funding ends, it can be stopped if the regional government does not renew it.</p>

	<p>the HALT2DIABETES dietary 6-group sessions program that aims to work on eating habits in a practical way and learn how to eat healthier²⁰. The HALT2DIABETES pilot program initially started in 2 regions and is now fully implemented in 10 regions, is in the pre-implementation phase in 3 regions and in the initial preparation phase in 16 regions.</p> <p>In the Walloon region, some "chronic integrated care" pilot projects²¹ had developed the adapted physical activity (APA) program for patients with chronic diseases including T2D^{22,23}.</p>		<p>The APA is no longer fully reimbursed as the "chronic integrated care" pilot projects have seen their roles redefined for the Proxisanté reforms (see table <i>key stakeholders and their level of involvement</i> "Chronicopole, PACT Santé, Relian, Resinam and Chronilux" page 23).</p>
<p>6 Proxisanté and the Walloon AVIQ health promotion program "Horizon 2030"</p> <p>A focus on health promotion in line with the C4D project.</p>			
<p>6.1 During the Proxisanté plenary session at the Walloon Parliament, the vice president of the Walloon government and health minister Christie Morreale mentioned the importance to put more efforts in health prevention and promotion (video 2h36min 40s)²⁵</p>	<p>6.2</p>	<p>6.3 Proxisanté aims, among others, to integrate health promotion practices into the front line of care⁸.</p> <p>The AVIQ "Horizon 2030" prevention and health promotion plan aims, among others, to reduce T2D overall morbidity and premature mortality through 1) the reduction of risk factors like stress and poor sleep quality 2) T2D screening 3) an increased accessibility to prevention across the continuum of care 4) the reinforcement of the population health skills with a particular attention on the most vulnerable</p>	<p>6.4</p>

		<p>populations 5) the improvement of health professionals skills and their collaboration and 6) the reinforcement of chronic disease surveillance and its integration into the health information system²⁶.</p> <p>The program "Horizon 2030" also aims to improve health-promoting behaviors of the Walloon population by promoting healthy eating and increasing regular physical activity ²⁷.</p> <p>The CARE4DIABETES project promotes health promotion practices in line with the Proxisanté health reforms and the Walloon prevention and promotion plan.</p>	
<p>7 Proxisanté and multidisciplinary communication</p> <p>Proxisanté aims at improving the communication between the different healthcare providers.</p>			
<p>7.1</p>	<p>7.2 There is a global lack of communication between the different healthcare professionals. Interdisciplinary team meetings between healthcare providers to work on T2D cases are not the norm because healthcare professionals do not have the time and these meetings are not funded. Therefore, they don't know how each of them can help in the treatment of T2D and how they can work together to join forces and create synergies.</p>	<p>7.3 Proxisanté has underlined the need to facilitate interdisciplinary communication and fund meetings of interdisciplinary teams of health professionals ⁸.</p> <p>The CARE4DIABETES project, in accordance with Proxisanté, promotes interdisciplinary communication and cross-functional communication. In terms of scalability, more healthcare providers will need to be trained in the RD2 program through a train-the-trainer process with certification upon</p>	<p>7.4</p>

	We must strengthen communication between health professionals and define the role of each.	completion to encourage training compliance. Since the program strengthens interdisciplinary communication, it may be eligible for funding.	
8 The AVIQ and the missions of the RML A lack of clarity on the role of the RML in the management of type 2 diabetes patients.			
8.1 The RLMs were created in 2009 as pilot projects in association with medical circles and integrated home care services (SISD) to support GPs by organizing the care trajectory ²⁸ .	8.2 Some RML have been forced to add to their missions the care of patients in the pre-trajectory which was not initially included in their missions ²⁸ . The missions of the RMLs vary greatly from one region to another: some RML have merely a role of administrative assistance and directory of care providers, while others are much more involved in health promotion. This can be explained by the fact that no common organizational or strategic orientation was given to them and also by the difference in the allocation of funds and therefore of human resources. RML do not have a INAMI/RIZIV number, so they are not recognized as health establishments and have no legitimacy with mutual insurance companies. Consequently they cannot verify the insurability of the T2D patients ^{29,30} .	8.3	8.4
9 Walloon governance and RML subsidies An unequal distribution of funding according to the territories.			

9.1	9.2 Some RML do not have the financial and human resources ³¹ to properly take charge of the pre-trajectory or become more involved in health promotion. In addition, RML subsidies are no longer indexed despite the INAMI/RIZIV indexation requirement.	9.3 The results of the participatory workshops of health care providers for Proxisanté highlighted the need to move from one-time funding to structural funding harmonized between frontline partners ³¹ .	9.4 Proxisanté will need to financially support the integration of additional health promotion practices into the front line of care (the RML in the case of type 2 diabetes) however budget allocation for the implementation of the reforms remains unknown.
<p style="text-align: center;">10 Patients education</p> <p>Type 2 diabetes education sessions are knowledge-based and lack patient involvement.</p>			
10.1	<p>10.2 T2D prevention care in the pre-trajectory and care trajectory includes a lot of education sessions. Education sessions include:</p> <p>1) Provide your patient with accurate and understandable information about diabetes and its treatment: causes, evolution, recognition of possible complications, correction and prevention of hyper- and hypoglycaemia, possible effect of drugs on blood sugar, in order to improve therapeutic compliance (including main effect and side effects of drugs related or not to diabetes), adequate reaction to illness, fever, vomiting, measures to take while traveling</p> <p>2) Motivate your patient to adapt their lifestyle: balanced diet, smoking cessation, physical activity regular foot checks and wearing suitable footwear maintaining good oral and dental hygiene</p>	10.3 The RD2 program promotes patient empowerment and self-efficacy by encouraging patient participation, involvement, and sharing of experiences.	<p>10.4 Even if 4 diabetes education sessions get accessible to all the patients in the pre-trajectory, it would remain very knowledge oriented.</p> <p>Shouldn't pre-trajectory diabetes education be more nutrition and physical activity oriented given that these patients receive oral medication which require less education compared to injections?</p> <p>Guidelines advocate for intensive lifestyle education program in people with prediabetes with a clear emphasis on medical nutrition therapy^{9,11}. Group diabetes self-management education and support is also important³⁵.</p>

	<p>3) Provide your patient with social information (including driver's license)³².</p> <p>The approach appears very theory based and not really participatory and empowering. Patients' lack of involvement in lifestyle change activities is unlikely to empower them^{33,34}.</p> <p>Perhaps education should be more diet and physical activity oriented like in the Flemish region (the HALT2DIABETES program includes physical activity and diet sessions)²⁴. It is highly participatory and problem-solving oriented.</p>		
<p>11 Patients education Type 2 diabetes education sessions are mostly delivered in one-on-one sessions.</p>			
<p>11.1</p>	<p>11.2 In the pre-trajectory and care trajectory, it seems that healthcare professionals are more focusing on individual session and not much on group sessions³⁵.</p> <p>In the HALT2DIABETES Flemish program²⁴, dieticians are trained to the dynamics of group sessions by improvising group case studies in a theatre. In addition, other caregivers (general practitioners and pharmacists) are trained in screening and referral to increase participation in the programme.</p> <p>Barriers to group sessions can come from the patients</p>	<p>11.3 The CARE4DIABETES project will train healthcare providers to group sessions and increase their self-efficacy.</p> <p>To overcome those barriers, in the HALT2DIABETES Flemish program, sessions are based on two principles: differentiation and decentralization therefore sessions must be never too far, at different timing and online or in person. Another technic that they use to motivate the patient is to bring “a buddy”. It can also be helpful for people with literacy issue.</p>	<p>11.4</p>

	(motivation, difficulty to organize, feeling that the session will be less personalized) but also from healthcare providers (not sufficient space in their offices, not used to group dynamics, difficulty to organize).	With regard to space, group sessions could be organized in the offices of healthcare providers if sufficiently big or in the RLM, local health promotion centres (CLPS), Maison de quartier, or local non-profit organisation.	
12	Equity	and	sustainability
Additional efforts will be needed to reach vulnerable populations who need it most.			
12.1	12.2 Lifestyle education sessions are poorly attended by those most in need due to direct and indirect (i.e. transport) costs, language barrier ³⁶ , low level of education, literacy, health literacy, lack of technological skills, partly reimbursed diet sessions. This problem is called the double discrimination.	12.3 To be sustainable and equitable, RD2 must be adapted to vulnerable populations to make it accessible to as many people as possible. Like in the HALT2DABIETES, the program can be adapted to the level of language. They also give recommendations and guidelines on how dieticians should speak to the participants. They also adapt their workshops to different level of literacy (food diary versus taking pictures for instance). Bringing a familiar can also help for translation or lack of technological skills. The promotion of the program must be adapted to the target population, among other things, in terms of language, target locations for program promotion, health literacy, the price of food, culture. For instance, the maisons de quartier are good ways to promote the program to vulnerable groups.	12.4

13 Patient motivation			
The determinant factor.			
13.1	<p>13.2 A self-determination questionnaire to test the motivation of patients has been validated in healthcare settings and is already used in some hospitals ³⁷.</p> <p>An e-learning to facilitate the communication between GPs and dieticians has been recently developed ³⁸.</p>	<p>13.3 Patient motivation should be considered when lifestyle intervention is recommended ⁹.</p> <p>The self-determination questionnaire or a similar questionnaire should be applied to patients to ascertain their motivation to enter the program. RD2 also uses a motivation questionnaire before enrolling participants (Annex 1, Figure 2).</p> <p>GPs should be trained to place more emphasis on the complications of disease ³⁹ progression if left untreated and the utmost importance for patients to change their lifestyle as it is an essential part of the treatment ⁴⁰. This could increase patient participation, enrolment and follow-up in diabetes education sessions and dietitian sessions.</p>	13.4
14 Health providers project role			
Psychologists or educators/nurses in diabetes could take the role of the life coach.			
14.1 A potential alternative for patients to have the support of a psychologist would be to make a bridge between the program and the PSYNAM convention ⁴¹ . Within the convention, group sessions costs only 2.5 euros ⁴² .	14.2 There might be a lack of accredited psychologists.	14.3 The motivating role of the diabetes educators/nurses can be even more important if the first diabetes education session becomes mandatory in the new pre-trajectory.	14.4
Diabetes educators/nurses can have a motivating role.			

15 Type 2 diabetes international recommendations			
15.1	15.2 The recommendations do not necessarily recommend the cessation of certain drugs because they have beneficial effects at the cardio-renal level ⁴³	15.3	15.4

At local setting (RML LUXEMBOURG – MAISON DU DIABETE) – rural			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 The active role of Maison du diabète in the promotion of health			
<p>1.1 The Maison du diabète⁴⁴ has a proactive and preventive management of type 2 diabetes.</p> <p>They are used to group sessions and use recreational activities⁴⁵.</p> <p>They have organized 22 diet group workshops over the year 2022. Additionally they offer group sessions in diabetes education using a specific tool called “le train du diabète”⁴⁶.</p> <p>They organize screenings for diabetic rethinopathy⁴⁷.</p> <p>Chronicare⁴⁸, that is part of the Maison du diabète, trains healthcare providers in the fields of T2D, e-health and prevention.</p>	1.2	<p>1.3 In line with the CARE4DIABETES project, they focus on lifestyle intervention.</p> <p>Although they are actively involved in one-on-one lifestyle sessions, they also engage in group sessions.</p>	1.4

2 The Maison du diabète is an experienced organization.			
<p>2.1 The Maison du diabète is a long term trusted organization in the management of diabetes in the Luxembourg.</p> <p>The Maison du Diabète is the reference centre for general practitioners to send their new patients because they know that they will be taken care of by an educator and a nurse specialized in diabetes.</p> <p>They have an extensive network throughout the Luxembourg region and have multidisciplinary internal teams (dieticians, nurses/educators and local coordinator).</p> <p>The Maison du diabète site is the reference site in the Luxembourg region for health professionals linked to diabetes, in particular because it contains all the information on diabetes care pathways and a directory of the different health care providers of interest ^{49,50}.</p>	2.2	<p>2.3 RD2 program could be scaled up to the different regions after the pilot program thanks to their network and training centre Chronicare⁴⁸.</p>	2.4
3 A GDPR certified database of their patients.			
<p>3.1 The Maison du diabète has a certified GDPR database of their patient information.</p>	3.2	<p>3.3 This database is useful for communicating with the target audience (satisfaction survey, invitation to activities, events, etc.).</p>	3.4
4 The Maison du diabète is familiar with digital environments			

<p>4.1 Besides its website, the Maison du diabète is active on facebook ⁵¹.</p> <p>They actively participate in the registration of care providers in the Réseau Santé Wallon which allows care providers to have access to their clinical data ⁵².</p>	4.2	4.3	4.4
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At local setting (RML LIEGE AND LIEGE EAST) – urban			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 The RML has a low pre-trajectory uptake.			
1.1	1.2 They don't have a lot patients in the pre-trajectory mainly because GPs do not register patients in the pre-trajectory due to the reasons listed in <i>the national/regional context</i> 4.2.	1.3 The new terms of the pre-trajectory will relaunch its promotion and there will be more patients registrations.	1.4
2 The RML has an extensive network of multidisciplinary care providers.			
<p>2.1 The RML ⁵³ works in partnership with 10 medical centres and has a team of 40 diabetes educators.</p> <p>They also have a directory of diabetes educators⁵⁴, dietitians⁵⁵, diabetologists⁵⁶, podiatrists⁵⁷ and medical houses⁵⁸. They work with a dietitian who also works in the Luxembourg region (Emmanuelle Franco).</p> <p>They have a diabetologist in the RML.</p>	2.2	2.3	2.4

3 The RML has an active role in the promotion of health.			
<p>3.1 The RML organises group sessions regularly based on the needs of the patients. They are used to group sessions and use recreational activities.</p> <p>Not so long ago, they planned four sessions in relation with dietetics and four sessions in relation with diabetes education and needs identification (they use the Comet tool).</p> <p>The patients were motivated and attended to the sessions.</p> <p>They organize screenings for diabetic rethinopathy⁵⁹.</p> <p>They organize sessions of adapted physical activity.</p>	3.2	3.3	3.4
4 The RML has a patient database.			
4.1 The RML has collected patients' emails, so they can be contacted through this channel.	4.2	4.3	4.4
5 The RML is familiar with digital environments			
5.1 Besides its website, the RML has a Facebook page ⁶⁰ .	5.2	5.3	5.4

At local setting (RML CEGENO– FOSSES-LA-VILLE and surroundings) – rural			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 The RML has a medium size team but good collaborations.			

1.1 They have a team of 8 educators in diabetes. They also work with an excellent dietician.	1.2 They are worried about the new modalities of the pre-trajectory because the educators are already quite overwhelmed.	1.3	1.4
2 The RML team benefits from frequent trainings.			
2.1 The team frequently attends trainings and conferences to be up to date.	2.2	2.3	2.4
3 They have similar interest in some component program.			
3.1 They regularly organize recreational workshops with a dietician so they are used to group sessions. They wanted to start mindfulness session for the patients.	3.2	3.3 The RD2 proposes relaxation exercises which is closely related to mindfulness.	3.4

At local setting (RML AGRF – CHIMAY and surroundings) – rural			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 The RML has a small team but good collaborations.			
1.1 The RML ⁶¹ has 2 diabetes educators, one who works full time for 5 different RML and one who works 2 morning a week in an office that the RML provides her. Educators, GPs, dieticians and diabetologists work as independent but they have a good collaboration between each other.	1.2	1.3	1.4
2 The RML and multidisciplinary communication.			

2.1 Once a year they organize a multidisciplinary team meeting with at least one healthcare representative of the care trajectory.	2.2	2.3	2.4
3 The RML does not have patients in the pre-trajectory.			
3.1	3.2 The pre-trajectory is barely prescribed because GPs don't want to deal with the administrative burden of this trajectory and its yearly renewal.	3.3 The new terms of the pre-trajectory will relaunch its promotion and there will be more patients registrations.	3.4
4 The RML is not so involved in health promotion.			
4.1 They're just planning to run a type 2 diabetes screening campaign.	4.2	4.3	4.4

At local setting (RML UOAD – DINANT and surroundings) – rural			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 The RML has a small team but good collaborations.			
1.1 The RML ⁶² has 3 diabetes educators. One works at the RML. The RML have a very good relation with the local UOAD GP circle ⁶³ . They also work in partnership with the dieticians. They have a directory of diabetes educators, dieticians and podiatrists ⁶⁴ .	1.2	1.3	1.4
2 The RML has an active role in the promotion of health.			

<p>2.1 They organized 9 workshops this year.</p> <p>Dieticians organise workshops on different topics such as cooking, dietary information, water.</p> <p>They organize type 2 diabetes screenings on diabetes day.</p> <p>They organize screenings for diabetic rethinopathy.</p> <p>They have a partnership with Gym Sana for adapted physical activity²³.</p> <p>They are working on a new initiative to support people to stop smoking⁶⁵.</p> <p>They contact patients every year by email to incite them to go to the dietician or podiatrist.</p>	<p>2.2</p>	<p>2.3 They are developing an informative motivational letter to join to the email to increase patients motivation to go to the dietician or podiatrist.</p>	<p>2.4</p>
<p>3 The RML takes charge of the pre-trajectory.</p>			
<p>3.1 They were one of the first RML to add the pre-trajectory to their mission.</p>	<p>3.2</p>	<p>3.3.</p>	<p>3.4</p>
<p>4 The RML could make some improvement on their digital tool.</p>			
<p>4.1 Besides its website, the RML has a Facebook page ⁶⁶.</p>	<p>4.2 The website of the RML does not mention: the pre-trajectory, diabetic retinopathy screenings, dieticians workshops. It would need to be updated.</p>	<p>4.3</p>	<p>4.4</p>

At local setting (RML Grand Namur – NAMUR CENTRE and surroundings) – urban			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 The RML has good collaborations and a good organization.			
<p>1.1 The RML coordinator has been in charge of the RML from the start, so he knows all the tricks of the trade.</p> <p>The RML⁶⁷ works with motivated independent healthcare providers.</p> <p>The RML uses Medispring⁶⁷ software to manage the diaries of the multidisciplinary teams, collect information on patient data and session reminders by SMS.</p> <p>They have a directory of healthcare providers ⁶⁸.</p>	1.2	1.3	1.4
2 The RML has an active role in the promotion of health.			
<p>2.1 The RML organises diabetes education sessions at home and in various sites in the area. They have started to decentralize the sessions in order to increase patients' accessibility to them. Patients like to go to the sessions organized on site because it is a place where they can share their experience. This is also a time when diabetes educators can convince patients to attend diet sessions by explaining to them that diet sessions are not</p>	2.2	2.3	2.4

intended to lead to dietary restrictions. The RML also organises cooking workshops, health walk and nutrition and dietetic or diabetes education trivial pursuit ^{69,70} .			
3 The RML takes charge of the pre-trajectory.			
3.1 The RML integrates the pre-trajectory into its missions ⁷¹ .	3.2 According to figure 2 pre-trajectory uptake could be improved.	3.3 The new pre-trajectory modalities will boost its prescription and increase its adoption.	3.4
4 The RML has developed a good digital environment.			
4.1 The RML has a very well designed website divided in two part: one for the patients and one for the healthcare providers to provide each of them with the right information ⁶⁷ . The RML also has a Facebook page to promote its events, workshops and group sessions ⁷² .	4.2	4.3	4.4

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement *	Comments
Belgium Federal Cabinet	Tina Van Havere	4	The Belgian Federal Cabinet is the executive Belgian federal government. Tina Van Havere is an advisor at the cabinet.

Walloon Ministry of Health Cabinet	Yolande Husden Marina Libertiaux	4	The Walloon government in charge of the development and application of decrees related to health.
INAMI/RIZIV ² (The National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance)	Mike Daubie Pascal Meeus		The National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance (INAMI/RIZIV) with the Federal public service finance (SPF Finances) ³ organises and finances national health services.
SPF Santé Publique ⁷³ (The Federal Service of Public Health, Safety of the Food Chain and the Environment)	Laurence Doughan	2	The SPF Santé Publique is in charge, among other things, of the programs of the national food plan. By working with the government, they are aware of the challenges posed by type 2 diabetes. For this reason, they are following the progress of the project and assisting us in accessing certain representatives and health data.
AVIQ ⁴ (The Walloon Agency for a quality life)	Léna Frateur Caroline Frere	2	The AVIQ, the Walloon agency for a quality life, supports us in connecting with stakeholders and health structures of interest and the smooth running of the project.
Association Belge du Diabète ⁷⁴ (Non profit organisation)	Nicole Pirotte Valérie Heuvelmans	2	The Belgium Diabetes Association is the association of patients and patient representatives in the Walloon region, they actively participate in care policies related to diabetes.
Diabetes Liga ¹⁸ (Non profit organisation)	Luk Buyse Inge Everaert	2	The Diabetes Liga is the association of patients and patient representatives in the Flanders region, they actively participate in diabetes care policies. They are interested in the development of the project in order to be able to transfer it to Flanders. They work hand in hand with the Belgian Diabetes Association.
FAGW ⁷⁵	Guy Delrée	4	The Federation of Associations of General Practitioners of the Walloon Region could support us in the dissemination of the program to general practitioners, but its proximity to all the circles

			of independent local general practitioners is not certain. Local GP circles should also be informed.
FWPS ⁷⁶	Dounia Ouhadid	4	The Walloon Federation for Health Promotion can deliver specific trainings for healthcare professionals and facilitate our access to training tools through local health promotion centres (CLPS) ⁷⁷ .
Promo Santé & MG ⁷⁸	Gaëlle Fonteyne	4	Promo Santé & MG has resources/contacts to work on program accessibility for vulnerable populations. They also work with GPs and the Scientific Society of General Medicine (SSMG) ⁷⁹ who can be helpful in promoting the program to GPs to expand it in the future.
Chronicopole ⁸⁰	Damiela Viciencio	4	They are all part of the "chronic integrated care" pilot projects ²¹ launched in 2018. Currently, they are no longer in charge of setting up projects in the different regions, however, thanks to their 5-year expertise, they know the field resources and actors. It is likely that once Proxisanté is in force they play a role in governance at the meso level. They are useful to understand the existing dynamics within the different territories. Chronilux maintains close ties with the Maison du Diabète and could therefore help us promote the program to the various local stakeholders.
PACT Santé ⁸¹	Charlotte Degehansart	4	
Chronilux ⁸²	Céline Mostade	4	
Résinam ⁸³	Nicolas Mincier	4	
Rélian ⁸⁴	Julie Bechet	4	
RML Maison du Diabète ⁴⁴	Pierre-Christophe Stavaux	1*	For the reasons mentioned in each RML respective table, we have decided to include the RML Maison du diabète, the RML Liège and Liège Est, the RML Cegeno, the RML AGRF, the RML UOAD and the RML Grand Namur in the selection process as potential sites for the pilot program.
RML Liège et Liège Est ⁵³	Sabrina Gibilaro	1*	
RML Cegeno ⁸⁵	Isabelle Polis	1*	
RML AGRF ⁸⁶	Véronique Szöllösi	1*	
RML UOAD ⁶²	Séverine Delhaye / Delphine Delporte	1*	

RML Grand Namur ⁶⁷	Julien Laforge	1*	
RML Charleroi ⁸⁷	Yves Mengal	4	We decided not to select RML Charleroi as a potential site for the project because they did not show any interest.
RML Point Santé ⁸⁸	Axelle Spineux	4	The RML Point Santé is facing an internal restructuring. To ensure the smooth running of the program, it is preferable to set it up in an already well-organized structure, which is why we have decided not to retain it as a potential site.

* Only if they are the sites chosen for the pilot project, otherwise 4.

1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: 27/04/2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Charlotte Juton Sciansano, Stefanie Vandevijvere Sciansano, An-Sofie Vanherwegen Sciansano and Astrid Lavens Sciansano

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
1 The support of key actors involved in the implementation of the Proxisanté health reforms.	1

2 The program offers a game-changing vision in the management of T2D patients.	2 The recommendations in Belgium do not necessarily recommend the cessation of certain drugs because they have beneficial effects at the cardio-renal level.
3 A flexibility and adaptability in setting up the program.	3 The great variations in the missions of the RML according to the zones.
4 The program addresses the lack of intensive lifestyle intervention for T2D patients in the pre- and care trajectory.	4
5 The program supports GPs in intensive lifestyle changes for patients.	5
6 The program strengthens multidisciplinary teamwork and cross-functional communication.	6
7 The program promotes patient empowerment and self-efficacy.	7 Current practices are more knowledge-based in terms of diabetes education for patients.
8 The program encourages the sharing of patient experience.	8
9 The program offers dynamic positive and participatory group sessions for both healthcare providers and patients.	9 Current practices are more based on individual sessions.

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative = threats
1 A shared vision with that of the Walloon health promotion and prevention plan for the prevention of T2D and the promotion of healthy eating and physical activity in the general population.	1
2 A shared vision with that of Proxisanté for integrating health promotion practices in the first line of care and improving multidisciplinary teamwork and collaboration.	2
3 The promotion of the new pre-trajectory is likely to boost its prescription by general practitioners.	3
4 The expected increase in INAMI/RIZIV fees with respect to the nomenclature for diabetes educators will surely boost diabetes educators' motivation.	4 The shortage, overwork and lack of financial recognition of the diabetes educators decrease their motivation.
5	5 The uncertainty of the INAMI/RIZIV flat rate increase for group sessions in diabetes education may reduce the engagement of health care providers to being part of the program on the long term.
6 An increased accessibility to diabetes education sessions to all patients on oral antidiabetics in the new pre-trajectory.	6 The expected insufficient number of reimbursed lifestyle education sessions by the INAMI/RIZIV.

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is to:

- Strengthen health providers' multidisciplinary teamwork and cross-functional communication
- Reinforce early management of type 2 diabetes patients through an intensive program based on lifestyle changes.
- Increase social support and inclusion by encouraging patient involvement and experience sharing.
- Improve the health, well-being and quality of life of patients by enhancing patients empowerment and self-efficacy.
- Reduce costs associated with increased risk of disability, health-related retirement, and development of patient complications.

The scope of the C4D practice is to improve and promote health in Wallonia by reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and its associated risk factors through early management of patients with type 2 diabetes in effective lifestyle education programs delivered by collaborative multidisciplinary teams.

ANNEX 1

Figure 1: Reduction in drug declaration by the health insurer at 6, 12 and 24 months after the start of the program - comparison between patients following the R2D program (KDO) versus the control group

□ 24 months after start 53 % of participants used no medication or a lower medication level, n = 1,330

Figure 2: RD2 motivational questionnaire

Brief explanation of motivation and history

1 Briefly describe your motivation for participating in Reverse Diabetes2 Om:

2 How do you rate the following factors in your current lifestyle?
a scale of 1 - 10? 1= bad and 10= very good

Current diet	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
Daily movement	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
Quality of sleep	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
Quality of relaxation	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

3 To what extent do you agree with the following statements on a scale of 1 - 5?
1= not motivated and 5= very motivated

I am motivated to reverse my type 2 diabetes through lifestyle adjustments	1 2 3 4 5
Reversing my type 2 diabetes is more important to me than losing weight	1 2 3 4 5
I am willing to make adjustments to my current diet	1 2 3 4 5
I am willing to make exercise a part of my daily life	1 2 3 4 5
I am willing to make relaxation a part of my daily life	1 2 3 4 5

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Attachment II Bulgaria

REGIONAL HEALTH INSPECTORATE BLAGOEVGRAD, supported by MINISTRY OF HEALTH

BULGARIA

Authors: Mariya Tyufekchieva, Snezhana Popovska, Kristiyan Hristov, Bianka Ravnachka

Date: May 5th 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

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Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	Feb 6 2023; Mar 9 2023	Mariya Tyufekchieva	
II	Apr 10 2023	Mariya Tyufekchieva	
III	Apr 27 2023	Mariya Tyufekchieva	
IV	Apr 28 2023	Mariya Tyufekchieva	
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

Abbreviations:

RHI Blagoevgrad – Regional Health Inspectorate Blagoevgrad

MoH – Ministry of Health Bulgaria

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement date: Feb 6 2023, Mar 9 2023, April 13 2023

Meeting participants: Dr. Mariya Tyufekchieva, Snezhana Popovska, Kristiyan Hristov, Daniela Chiryiska, Dr. Petar Ivanov, Sylvia Georgieva, Bianka Ravnachka, Bilyana Miteva, Evgeni Anastasov

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Dr. Mariya Tyufekchieva	MoH Bulgaria	
Expert	Snezhana Popovska	MoH Bulgaria	
Expert	Kristiyan Hristov	MoH Bulgaria	
Expert	Snezhanka Dyankova	MoH Bulgaria	Substitute for Daniela Chiryiska, financial expert
Expert	Iliya Tasev	MoH Bulgaria	LEAR
Expert	Dr. Petar Ivanov	RHI Blagoevgrad	LEAR
Expert	Silviya Georgieva	RHI Blagoevgrad	Accountant, financial management, invited if advice needed

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Bianka Ravnachka	RHI Blagoevgrad	
Medical doctor	Dr. Ekaterina Mitova	RHI Blagoevgrad	Substitute for Dr. Shanina, indicated as a MD at the start of the project
Diabetes nurse	Borislava Angova	RHI Blagoevgrad	
Dietitian	Tzvetelina Hadjieva	RHI Blagoevgrad	Substitute for Dr. Kaloyan Kaloyanov, indicated as a MD at the start of the project
Coach	Stamenka Georgieva	RHI Blagoevgrad	

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meeting date: April 24 2023, April 25 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Dr. Mariya Tyufekchieva, Snezhana Popovska, Kristiyan Hristov

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team – Bianka Ravnachka, Silviya Georgieva, Borislava Angova, Evgeni Anastasov

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D practice in Bulgaria reflects the general objective of C4D practice: to improve and foster health in a current EU Member State by reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and related risk factors. This should happen on 2 levels simultaneously: the societal and personal one by stimulating effective lifestyle treatment and implementing various training programmes tailored patients' needs.

In addition, C4D practice can serve a valuable opportunity in Bulgarian context to reproduce successful practices of coordination between multidisciplinary regional expert team and central administrative structure both engaged in promotion of healthy lifestyle and raising awareness of Diabetes Type 2. By involving experts with various background we aim to strengthen the coordination between health professionals dealing with treatment of Diabetes type 2 and lifestyle practices that can further impact the course of the disease on individual level.

The scope of the C4D practice Bulgaria is:

- to propose design, to check its suitability and to assess its impact;
- program for patients with type 2 diabetes that is digitally supported to persuade them in the fruitfulness of healthy living;
- open new unexplored fields in Bulgarian context of possible determinants of the health of persons with diabetes type 2 such as physical activity, sleep and the decrease of stress;
- providing platform for interaction tete-a-tete between medical specialists and patients who are able to reunite theory and practice in regards to Diabetes type 2,
- to define and select the best approaches to re-educate diabetes specialists in regional and national context, that will help them to master digital tools as well as to rely on regular live contact with the selected patients

- the development of protocol and national plan for expansion of the best practices throughout the implementation of the project in order to secure sustainability on national level and to foster public dialogue on the update of national policies towards people living with diabetes

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date(-s): April 24 2023, April 25 2023, April 28 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Dr. Mariya Tyufekchieva, Snezhana Popovska, Kristiyan Hristov

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team – Bianka Ravnachka, Dr. Ekaterina Mitova Silviya Georgieva, Tzvetelina Hadjieva, Borislava Angova, Evgeni Anastasov,

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 National policy	Low budget of the national program	Developing national policies with the implementation of good practices in the field of diabetes	Increasing number of patients with type 2 diabetes at all levels of care and insufficient funding
2 Existing organisation with administrative capacity (National Program Council) – national coordinating structure – NCPHA and then RHI to implement the policy on local level	2	2	2
3 National expert council on endocrinology at the Minister of Health	3 Limited health personnel – insufficient number of endocrinologists, who are concentrated mainly in the regional cities (uneven distribution on the territory of the country). This impedes high quality of cares, prophylaxis and monitoring of treatment.	3 The inclusion of various experts from related medical fields (dietician, nurse) can reduce the work pressure among the doctors, who are specialists in diabetes.	3 The growth of C4D practice is highly dependent on changing attitudes and systemic changes in practice
4 The Law for Health Insurance – Diabetes Type 2 is enlisted in the list for subsidized services to reduce the financial burden for the	4 Health devices related to control of diabetes are at the expense of the patients	4 Providing low-threshold diabetes services among the uninsured	4

patients (the State pays for certain tests, medical exams and the concrete algorithm for diagnosing Diabetes Type 2			
5 Availability of diabetes education at primary (GPs, RNs, HPC) and secondary (hospitals - diabetes clinic) level of health care	5 Lack of concrete initiatives that are binded with the national policies (NCPHA experts should educate nutritionists and physical trainers, all supervised by endocrinologists)	5 increasing capacity to deliver education at all levels of care	5

At local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 The members of the multidisciplinary team have experience in international projects	1 high workload of team members	1 Positive adaptation to daily clinical practice	1
Most patients are treated by the same team for a long time and trust the healthcare team, which ensures a high degree of adherence to the project	2 degree of patient satisfaction with the project	2	2
3. Basic education for a healthy lifestyle is available through the preventive activities of the expert of RZI	3 The level of education of medical professionals and this is reflected in the approach to patient education	3 expanding education	3

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
National program board for the implementation of the National Program for the Prevention of Chronic Non-Communicable Diseases	known	informed	
Program board of the National Program for the Prevention of Chronic Non-Communicable Diseases - Blagoevgrad	known	informed	
Southwestern University "Neofit Rilski", department of social activities	known	informed	
Five medical facilities from Blagoevgrad region	known	briefly informed	
Regional structure of the Bulgarian Red Cross	known	briefly informed	
Municipality of Blagoevgrad	known	briefly informed	

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: April 25 2023, April 28 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Dr. Mariya Tyufekchieva, Snezhana Popovska, Kristiyan Hristov

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team – Bianka Ravnachka, Dr. Ekaterina Mitova Silviya Georgieva, Tzvetelina Hadjieva, Borislava Angova, Evgeni Anastasov,

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
1 Good collaboration with the Ministry of Health, Sofia National Medical Center, RZI in the Republic of Bulgaria, N. Rilski University of Applied Sciences, Faculty of Public Health, Health Care and Sports, Association of General Practitioners in Blagoevgrad Region, 5 MBALS in the district, CSMP and its subdivisions in the district, Directorate of "Social Assistance" and Regional structure of the Bulgarian Red Cross	1 Lack of personnel trained in a specific field of action Investing in treatment, not prevention, of chronic non-communicable diseases.
2 There is a coordination mechanism which, in case of a case, activates all these institutions.	2
3 Gained experience in the implementation of the National, Regional and Municipal Level.	3
4 Multidisciplinary team with good experience of working on national and international projects	4

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
1 A multidisciplinary intervention for treatment and lifestyle modification in patients with type 2 diabetes: - Acquisition of knowledge and skills that lead to the limitation of risk factors /smoking, alcohol abuse, adynamia, unhealthy diet/; - Improved lifestyle and quality of life; - Control of glycemic levels; - Reduction of drug therapy. The adoption of a long-term strategy for a targeted national policy for the prevention, early diagnosis and control of the disease Type 2 Diabetes.	1 Blagoevgrad region has hard-to-reach and remote settlements. A diversity of ethnic groups, religions and cultures is observed; - Gaining trust and motivating patients to join the project; - Ensuring the presence of patients; - Failure to meet patients' expectations; - Patient turnover;
2 Multiply the project as a portal for best practices to support the integration of evidence-based policies (and	2 Shortage of specialists in the field of human health protection;

learn about their applicability and scalability, and their evaluation over time).	
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The aim of the C4D practice in Bulgaria is to compensate for deficits in the training of health workers by building on the existing health education programs related to public health protection. Profiled diabetes control programs based on new learning technologies and future patient needs.

The scope of C4D practice in Bulgaria is

- increased quality of education of health workers, which in turn will lead to better access to services designed for patients with type 2 diabetes;
- to identify the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches to limit type 2 diabetes
- introduction and application of new technologies to ensure optimization of services for patients with type 2 diabetes;
- to use the potential of C4D to optimize type 2 diabetes policy;

Attachment III Finland

FINNISH DIABETES ASSOCIATION (FDA), supported by FINNISH INSTITUTE FOR HEALTH AND WELFARE (THL)

Authors: Sari Koski, Maija Kurki, Jaana Lindström, Katja Wikström, Päivi Valve, Jemina Kivelä

Date: April 30, 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

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Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	17.3.2023	THL/FDA	
II	31.3.2023	THL/FDA	
III	27.4.2023 / 28.4.2023	THL/FDA/Ekhva	
IV	27.4.2023 / 28.4.2023	THL/FDA/Ekhva	
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement date: 17.3.2023

Meeting participants: Jaana Lindström (THL), Sari Koski (Diabetes Association), Maija Kurki (Diabetes Association), Katja Wikström (THL), Päivi Valve (THL) and Jemina Kivelä (THL)

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	JK	THL	
Expert 1	PV	THL	
Expert 2	KW	THL	
Expert 3	JK	THL	
Expert 4	MK	FDA	
<i>Decision maker 1</i>	SK	FDA	
<i>Decision maker 2</i>	JL	THL	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	MK	FDA	
Medical doctor 1		Ekhva	Changes in the organisation, there is a doctor available, but changed from the initial info
Diabetes nurse 1	HL	FDA	
Diabetes nurse 2	TH	Ekhva	
Diabetes nurse 3	SK	Ekhva	
Dietitian 1	KA	FDA	
Coach 1	MK	FDA	
Other experts?			

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

1. What would you like to accomplish within the work of C4D?

New material and a new concept for lifestyle education of people with type 2 diabetes.

2. When C4D ends, what would you like to see as the result?

Finalised web-based lifestyle education as a part of education of people with type 2 diabetes implemented in Finnish health care system.

3. What would you like to see that would happen after C4D ends?

Finnish Diabetes Association continues the web-based lifestyle education as a part of their education platform for people with diabetes. New wellbeing services counties will also join in the cooperation, for example by routinely directing people with type 2 diabetes to join the educational course.

Consensus meeting date: 31.3.2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Jaana Lindström (THL), Sari Koski (Diabetes Association), Maija Kurki (Diabetes Association), Katja Wikström (THL), Päivi Valve (THL) and Jemina Kivelä (THL)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team Maija Kurki (Diabetes Association)

The aim of C4D practice:

The aim is to develop and test a new web-based lifestyle education concept and new materials to support adoption and maintenance of healthy lifestyles for people with type 2 diabetes. Finnish Diabetes Association will set up the web-based lifestyle education course to complement their current education platform for people with diabetes. The course will be tested in a pilot action which will be conducted in cooperation with one wellbeing services county. Two consecutive pilot-groups, 20 persons with diabetes in each group will be implemented, utilizing Plan-Do-Study-Act framework to identify and resolve encountered challenges that might hinder the larger-scale adoption of the practice. The implementation process as well as the patient-level outcomes will be evaluated, as well as the costs of the implementation.

The scope of the practice:

Health and wellbeing of people with type 2 diabetes will improve. The new web-based lifestyle education will be implemented and scaled-up in new wellbeing services counties. The service will be largely available and easily accessible for people with type 2 diabetes in Finland.

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date(-s): 27.4.2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Jaana Lindström (THL), Sari Koski (Diabetes Association), Maija Kurki (Diabetes Association), Katja Wikström (THL), Päivi Valve (THL), Sari Kaski EKHVA, Tiina Hujanen EKHVA,

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team Sari Koski (Diabetes Association), Maija Kurki (Diabetes Association), Päivi Valve (THL), Sari Kaski EKHVA, Tiina Hujanen EKHVA, Kirsikka Aittola (Diabetes Association)

At national level – in Finland			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 Many wellbeing counties have been developing lifestyle education for people with type 2 diabetes	1 Almost half of people with diabetes don't know whether they can have lifestyle education or not, and only about one fourth feel they receive enough lifestyle education	1 Importance of prevention of type 2 diabetes has been widely recognised in wellbeing counties	1 There are not enough resources to develop and broaden the lifestyle education in wellbeing counties
2 People with type 2 diabetes are willing to receive more nutritional education.	2 Less than one fifth of people with type 2 diabetes feels they receive nutritional education as much as they need. There are not enough dieticians working in the wellbeing counties	2 There are possibilities to evaluate the nutritional quality hopefully new methods will be used somehow	2 Wellbeing counties have no money to hire more dieticians
3 Diabetes nurses are well educated also in lifestyle education	3 Many diabetes nurses' positions have been transferred other positions	3 Diabetes nurses' importance to diabetes education is more credited	3 There are shortage of nurses in total and also in diabetes nurses

At local setting - in Ekhva			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative

1 Many people with diabetes experience that they have access to dietician	1 Still many are lacking, they don't know if they can have access to dietician	1 There were digital care possibilities during EKSOTE (previous organization) – are they still available?	1 Foreseen cutting of costs in the areas of social welfare and healthcare
2 Most people with diabetes have access to lifestyle counselling	2 One third would like to have more information about nutrition and exercise	2 Prevention is important in Ekhva - improving	2 Many patients are elderly – they do not have access to or capacity to use digital services
3 The diabetes nurses are able to give referrals to dieticians and coaches and physical activity counsellors at low threshold	3 Know-how of the person giving lifestyle counselling varies depending on the nurses' background – the patients' care is not equal!	3 There will definitely be users for the intervention if the best practice is sustainable, implemented and scaled-up.	3 Too much hype on digital services – we still need personal contacts when dealing with patients with diabetes
4 The diabetes nurses try to include lifestyle counselling in every meeting with the patient	4 There are too few dieticians and wellbeing coaches – patients need to wait long to the appointments	4	4
5 There is a dietician in EKHVA, and compared to the rest of the country there are more dieticians working in the wellbeing services county (but still too few)	5 There is lack of doctors and nurses in EKHVA - Diabetes nurses are not able to give enough intensive lifestyle counselling due to their heavy workload and also other nurses take care of people with diabetes than diabetes nurses	5	5
	6 There is a high turnover of the nurses in the wellbeing services county		
	7 Little chances for the nurses to get training in lifestyle change		
	8 People with diabetes and mental health challenges don't get the lifestyle counselling they need because their main care is not diabetes centred		

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
MH head of outpatient care in EKHVA		4	
AR head of wellbeing and prevention in EKHVA		4	
The board of FDA		4	
JV executive director of FDA		2	Consultation for legal issues, if necessary
RN head of communications of FDA		3	
TL, Advisory board member from Finland (UEF)		2	
AN, expert of health care services in THL		3	
SS, ministerial advisor in MoH		3	
US, professor of dietetics in UEF		3	
Directors of other welfare counties		4	Will be informed in dissemination and contacted in scale-up phase

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: 28.4.2023

Meeting participants: Multidisciplinary team Sari Koski (Diabetes Association), Maija Kurki (Diabetes Association), Päivi Valve (THL), Kirsikka Aittola (Diabetes Association), Jemina Kivelä (THL)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team (Name1 Surname1, Name2 Surname2,...)

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
1 a solid background and long traditions of lifestyle education for people with type 2 diabetes	1 tradition and routines for lifestyle counselling are strong, might diminish the ability to adopt new ways
2 the trainer team has a lot of know-how of type 2 diabetes pathophysiology, and lifestyle education	2 the model is delivered fully digitalised, it won't reach everyone
3 Platform already developed and in use for lifestyle courses	
4 The continuous glucose monitor provided to the participants will increase participants motivation and commitment	

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
1 possibility to scale up the model for the whole country	1 Lack of money in wellbeing county
2 Finnish Diabetes Association is already known and trusted by people with diabetes	2 Lack of nurses/doctors in wellbeing county
3 New ideas and way to work from the VL model will be adapted	3 Some concepts in the VL model are not in line with the evidence-based guidelines which we must follow; might be difficult to adapt VL model as a whole

The aim of C4D practice:

The aim is to develop and test a new web-based lifestyle education concept and new materials to support adoption and maintenance of healthy lifestyles for people with type 2 diabetes. Finnish Diabetes Association will set up the web-based lifestyle education course to complement their current education platform for people with diabetes. The course will be tested in a pilot action which will be conducted in cooperation with one wellbeing services county. Two consecutive pilot-groups, 20 persons with diabetes in each group will be implemented, utilizing

Plan-Do-Study-Act framework to identify and resolve encountered challenges that might hinder the larger-scale adoption of the practice. The implementation process as well as the patient-level outcomes will be evaluated, as well as the costs of the implementation.

The scope of the practice:

Health and wellbeing of people with type 2 diabetes will improve. The new web-based lifestyle education will be implemented and scaled-up in new wellbeing services counties. The service will be largely available and easily accessible for people with type 2 diabetes in Finland.

Attachment IV Greece

ALEXANDRA GENERAL HOSPITAL

Supported by 1st Regional Healthcare Authority of Attica

GREECE

Authors: Stavroula Paschou, Eleni Boutati, Theodora Psaltopoulou

Date: 30 April 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

Contact e-mail: c4d@hosp-alexandra.gr, s.a.paschou@gmail.com, eboutati@med.uoa.gr,
tpsaltop@hotmail.com

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	Feb 13 2023, Mar 17 2023	Theodora Psaltopoulou	
II	March 13 2023, March 17 2023, March 24 2023, March 31 2023	Stavroula Paschou	
III	March 20 2023, March 24 2023, April 17 2023	Theodora Psaltopoulou	
IV	April 24 2023	Stavroula Paschou	
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail	

Abbreviations:

Alexandra - Alexandra General Hospital

1st YPE - 1st Regional Healthcare Authority of Attica

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement dates: Feb 13 2023, Mar 17 2023

Meetings' participants: Stavroula Paschou, Kanella Kantreva, Kleio Makrygiannaki, Maria Agapiou, Foteini Tolika, Eleni Boutati, Theodora Psaltopoulou

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Theodora Psaltopoulou	Alexandra	
Expert	Stavroula Paschou	Alexandra	
Expert	Eleni Boutati	Alexandra	
Expert	Maria Agapiou	1st YPE	
Expert	Foteini Tolika	1st YPE	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Theodora Psaltopoulou	Alexandra	
Medical doctor	Stavroula Paschou	Alexandra	
Medical doctor	Katerina Stefanaki	Alexandra	
Medical doctor	Paraskevi Kazakou	Alexandra	
Junior medical doctor	Olympia Michalopoulou	Alexandra	
Dietitian	Vasiliki Marcasioti	Alexandra	
Diabetes nurse	Iro Kokalliari	Alexandra	
Administrative role	Kleio Makrygiannaki	Alexandra	

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meetings dates: March 13 2023, March 17 2023, March 24 2023, March 31 2023

Meetings' participants

C4D team members: Stavroula Paschou, Kleio Makrigiannaki, Foteini Tolika, Eleni Boutati, Theodora Psaltopoulou

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice:

The purpose of C4D practice Greece is to increase the capacity and quality of education at secondary healthcare level including new topics, new approaches and digital tools, with an aim to increase effective lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes. In addition, C4D serves as an unique opportunity to introduce to Greek context the approaches on how to design, pilot, monitor and evaluate educational programmes for patients in general, how to design and evaluate in a formative way digitally supported educational programmes with an aim to optimise the effectiveness based on the future patient needs and availability of the human resources, and to deliver the proposal for upgrading of the existing system for training of diabetes educators and medical doctors on coaching and the use of digital solutions.

The scope of the C4D practice Greece is

- to design, test and evaluate (using PDSA cycles),
- a digitally-enhanced educational program for patients with type 2 diabetes to support their healthy life choices, delivered at secondary level of care,
- that will be compatible to the organizational, professional and cultural context, existing terminology and symbols and building on the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches, and upgrading them with specific topics (physical activity, sleep and stress reduction),
- by fully embracing a co-creation approach and research methodologies in social sciences, including the most recent ones,
- with the optimal use of face-to-face interaction in combination with digital solutions
- and to identify the approaches to increase the skills of diabetes educators, medical doctors and other healthcare professionals in areas identified (such as coaching, use of digital tools, and related to physical activity, sleep and stress reduction as topics),
- and to use the potential of C4D to increase visibility of importance of education in type 2 diabetes at national level.

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

March 20 2023, March 24 2023 and April 17 2023 (communication with external participants by e-mails or telephone or video call)

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Stavroula Paschou, Kleio Makrigiannaki, Eleni Boutati, Theodora Psaltopoulou

External participants: representative of the Hellenic Endocrine Society, representative of National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, representatives of Greek diabetic patients associations, health care journalists

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
Greek state implementation plans for diabetes, yearly national diabetes conferences and high social media visibility	Fragmentation and regional differences, both in terms of at which point is the patient being appointed to education at the secondary level, as well as what kind of information is being provided to them (including differences in methods and approaches). HPs at the secondary level do not have a clear understanding if and what kind of preventive (e.g. education) and therapeutic activities were provided at the primary level. Similarly, GPs do not have a clear understanding what kind of education has been provided to persons with T2D that have been appointed to education via HCPs.	Digitalisation in healthcare	Increasing numbers of patients with type 2 diabetes at all levels of care, with different expectations from healthcare system, including digital services and support on one hand, and having more complex conditions including unfavourable socioeconomic conditions on the other. The interventions might actually broaden the gap in health across socioeconomic gradient if not designed well.
Increasing capacities at primary diabetes care and provision of education at all levels of diabetes care	Differences in education between primary and secondary care	Peer support is already developed in Greece	Decrease the number of healthcare professionals and other professionals working in healthcare, including those related to diabetes education.

Evolving process for type 2 diabetes education at primary care (family medicine practices, health promotion centres)	No systematic approach/platforms to support patients' education		
Existed telemedicine approaches for type 2 patients	No common e-health record		

At local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
Multidisciplinary team members, skilled in international projects	Extremely busy clinical setting, with unstable availability of multidisciplinary team members	Positive adaptation of everyday clinical practice	Potential obstacles arising outside the local setting
Basic healthy lifestyle education already available		Education with the use of digital platform	
Most of the patients are treated by the same team for a long time and they trust the healthcare team; if the team invites a patient to join a "project", they usually agree and join it with high expectations	There is a "post-COVID" effect and patients are not keen to visit hospital more than really necessary.		

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
Hellenic Endocrine Society	known	3	
Hellenic Diabetes Association	known	4	
Hellenic Diabetes Federation	known	4	
Patients with Diabetes Athens Vclub	known	4	
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	known	3	
Health journalists	known	4	

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: April 24 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Stavroula Paschou, Kleio Makrigiannaki, Eleni Boutati, Theodora Psaltopoulou

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative = weakness
Very close connection of C4D team members to scientific and patients diabetes associations, yearly national diabetes conferences and high social media visibility	Very busy clinical and research setting, with unstable availability of multidisciplinary team members
Very close connection of C4D team members to the evolving process for type 2 diabetes education at primary and secondary care	
Multidisciplinary team members are skilled in international projects	
Most of the patients are treated by the same team for a long time and they trust the healthcare team; if the team	

invites a patient to join a “project”, they usually agree and join it with high expectations	
Positive adaptation of everyday clinical practice	
Adequate experience in the use of digital platforms	

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
Greek state implementation plans for diabetes and increasing capacities at primary care and for provision of education at all levels of diabetes care	Fragmentation and regional differences, both in terms of at which point is the patient being appointed to education at the secondary level, as well as what kind of information is being provided to them. HPs at the secondary level do not have a clear understanding if and what kind of preventive (e.g. education) and therapeutic activities were provided at the primary level. Similarly, GPs do not have a clear understanding what kind of education has been provided to persons with T2D that have been appointed to education via HCPs.
Telemedicine approaches in type 2 diabetes in primary care	There is a need to build capacities for a continuous coaching approach and lifestyle support.
Availability of diabetes education at primary (GPs, RNs, HPC) and secondary (hospitals, diabetes centers) level of healthcare	An extensive development of new medicines and technologies (e.g. sensors) in diabetes management in recent years resulted in educators being focused on explaining their use, less on lifestyle change planning.
Longterm existence of diabetes education at secondary level, with extensive trainings, knowledge and skills of diabetes teams.	No systematic approach/platforms to support patients' education
Basic healthy lifestyle education already available at primary healthcare teams and health promotion centres	No common e-health record
Peer support is already developed in Greece	The level of education of HCPs at primary level might vary from team to team and this is reflected in the approach to education of the patients
	There is a “post-COVID” effect and patients are not keen to visit hospital more than really necessary.
	Increasing numbers of patients with type 2 diabetes at all levels of care, with different expectations from healthcare system.

	Decrease the number of healthcare professionals and other professionals working in healthcare, including those related to diabetes education.
	The scaling up of C4D practice is highly dependent on systemic changes (and sometimes even reforms), but the outcomes are unsure
	Current situation in the society and especially in health care sector is unsure
	Potential obstacles arising outside the country setting

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The purpose of C4D practice Greece is to increase the capacity and quality of education at secondary healthcare level including new topics, new approaches and digital tools, with an aim to increase the efficiency of the existing resources in delivering effective lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes. In addition, C4D serves as an unique opportunity to introduce to Greek context the approaches on how to design, pilot, monitor and evaluate educational programmes for patients in general, how to design and evaluate in a formative way digitally supported educational programmes with an aim to optimise the effectiveness based on the future patient needs and availability of the human resources, and to deliver the proposal for upgrading of the existing system for training of diabetes educators and medical doctors on coaching and the use of digital solutions.

The scope of the C4D practice Greece is

- to design, test and evaluate (using PDSA cycles),
- a digitally-enhanced educational program for patients with type 2 diabetes to support their healthy life choices, delivered at secondary level of care,
- that will be compatible to the organizational, professional and cultural context, existing terminology and symbols and building on the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches, and upgrading them with specific topics (physical activity, sleep and stress reduction),
- by fully embracing a co-creation approach and research methodologies in social sciences, including the most recent ones,
- with the optimal use of face-to-face interaction in combination with digital solution to increase the efficiency of the existent (human) resources,

- and to identify the approaches to increase the skills of diabetes educators, medical doctors and other healthcare professionals in areas identified (such as coaching, use of digital tools, and related to physical activity, sleep and stress reduction as topics),
- and to use the potential of C4D to increase visibility of importance of education in type 2 diabetes at national level.

Attachment V Hungary

NATIONAL PUBLIC HEALTH CENTRE OF HUNGARY

Hungary

Author: Noémi Borbély

Date: April 30 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

Contact e-mail: care4diabetes@nijz.si

jelka.zaletel@kclj.si, anja.brunec@nijz.si, denis.opresnik@nijz.si

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	2023.04.13.	Noémi Borbély	This was the date until we have agreed with all of the team members (separately).
II	2023.04.26.	Noémi Borbély	We had one personal meeting, where we discussed all of the questions. The questions were provided to the team members before the meeting so everyone could get acquainted with them and prepare with some possible answers.
III	2023.04.26.	Noémi Borbély	
IV	2023.04.26.	Noémi Borbély	
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement date: 2023.04.13.

Meeting participants: Péter Csizmadia, Zsófia Kimmel, Noémi Borbély, Katalin Tauszik, Roland Kosik, Marianna Lászlóffy dr., Izabella Henter

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Noémi Borbély	NPHC	
Expert 1	Zsófia Kimmel	NPHC	
Expert 2			
<i>Decision maker 1</i>	Péter Csizmadia	NPHC	
<i>Decision maker 2</i>			

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Noémi Borbély	NPHC	
Medical doctor1	Marianna Lászlóffy dr.	NPHC	
Diabetes nurse1	Roland Kosik	NPHC	
Dietitian1	Izabella Henter	external consultant	
Coach1	Katalin Tauszik	NPHC	

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meeting date: 2023.04.26.

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Zsófia Kimmel, Noémi Borbély

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team: Katalin Tauszik, Roland Kosik, Marianna Lászlóffy dr., Izabella Henter

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D practice is: raising awareness in the society, increasing the participants' health-consciousness, educating them and help them in achieving a better quality of life.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

The scope of the practice is: first of all to implement a pilot project that helps the participants to achieve a better quality of life. Secondly, we would like to execute such a project of which experiences can be used later, and through the dissemination we could decrease the number of people newly diagnosed with type 2 diabetes (T2D).

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date(-s): 2023.04.26.

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Zsófia Kimmel, Noémi Borbély

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team: Katalin Tauszik, Roland Kosik, Marianna Lászlóffy dr., Izabella Henter

External participants, providing the full overview at national, regional and local level -

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 100< health promotion offices (HPO) in the country. They can reach many people also at	1 People are not conscious concerning their body and their health behaviour.	1 We hope that the number of HPOs will increase.	1 The problem is that the situation of the HPOs is unstable so we can only hope that they will

schools and workplaces and as we see they really enthusiastic about their job. Many of them function within hospitals.			function in the future too. The government does not give them enough financial support.
2 There are competent professional bodies.	2 There are no dieticians in the primary health care so if someone needs a dietician he/she will definitely have to pay for that.	2	2
3 There are some well-known role models with T2D who can people look up to.	3 There ARE and there will always be people who share uncertain, unproven information about T2D and try to convince people or sell them something (usually their own product).	3	3 There are and there WILL always be people who share uncertain, unproven information about T2D and try to convince people or sell them something (usually their own product).
4 Many information can be found about T2D especially on the internet.	4 There are many information about T2D (good and bad information can be found on the internet as well)	4	4
5 More and more healthy choices are available for people with T2D in the shops.	5 However, maybe their financial situation is not good enough to buy healthy food.	5	5

At local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 As a national centre in the country we have many professional resources that we can use.	1 Participants' financial situation. (It can be true for the current and for the future situation as well.)	1	1
2 The attitude of the patients' family doctors can be supportive.	2 The attitude of the patients' family doctors can be resisting.	2	2

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
Hungarian Dietetic Association	-	2	The final step is ahead of us: it means, the head of the NPHC has to ask them officially to cooperate.
Hungarian Diabetes Association	-	3	The case is the same as above.
Professional Association	-	3	The case is the same as above.

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: 2023.04.26.

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Zsófia Kimmel, Noémi Borbély

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team: Katalin Tauszik, Roland Kosik, Marianna Lászlóffy dr., Izabella Henter

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
1 The team members have a big knowledge in their own profession and are all very experienced	1 Our financial and human capacity resources are restricted in a sense
2 The team members are determined in achieving permanent changes by the program among the participants and in the long term in the population as well	2
3 We have our own instruments (e.g. InBody machine, blood pressure monitors)	3

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
1 The NPHC is a reliable and reputable institution	1 People's motivation (to change)
2 At the NPHC there are a lot of experts from different fields (connected to health)	2 The "official" healthcare system has no communication (e.g. they don't educate people)
3 Hopefully all of the newest medications will be accessible for everyone (in the future)	3 There is a big hole between beliefs and real knowledge. People believe many things but they don't know many things.
4 Hopefully the health-consciousness of people will grow	4 Health literacy among people is quite low
5 Hopefully the education of professionals will be as good in the future as it is now (at least concerning healthcare)	5

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

We do not want to change our previous statements.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

We do not want to change our previous statements.

Attachment VI Italy

AOUP, ASL ROMA2 and FPG, supported by ISS

ITALY

Authors: Claudia Giacomozzi, Alberto Piaggese, Rocco Bulzomì, Dario Pitocco

Date: April 30 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

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jelka.zaletel@kclj.si, anja.brunec@nijz.si, denis.opresnik@nijz.si

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	March 29 2023	ISS	Based on preliminary meeting outcomes (September 8 2022)
II	April 14 2023	ISS	
III	April 19 2023	ISS	
IV	April 21 2023	ISS	Involving few potential stakeholders
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement date: March 29 2023

Meeting participants: Claudia Giacomozzi ISS, Alberto Piaggese AOUP, Elisabetta Iacopi AOUP, Sara Di Biase (associated to AOUP), Marco Mancuso (associated to ASLROMA2), Rosa Asprino (associated to ASLROMA2), Dario Pitocco FPG, Sara Monte (associated to FPG), Federica Conenna (associated to FPG)

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Claudia Giacomozzi	ISS	
Expert 1	Alberto Piaggese	AOUP	
Expert 2	Dario Pitocco	FPG	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Marco Mancuso	Associated to ASLROMA2	also in the role of Diabetes Expert Podiatrist
Diabetologist 1	Elisabetta Iacopi	AOUP	
Dietician1	Rosa Asprino	Associated to ASLROMA2	
Psychologist1	Sara Di Biase	Associated to AOUP	
Coach1	Sara Monte	Associated to FPG	
Coach2	Federica Conenna	Associated to FPG	
C4D pilot coordinator	Claudia Giacomozzi	ISS	also in the role of digital platform coordinator

Notes: this meeting had been preceded by some prework among ISS and the three AEs leaders, to share a common ground to design a potentially effective multidisciplinary team: online meetings, face2face meetings between ISS leader and each AE leader and administrative personnel, agreement notes, and so on. Agreement had been reached on the following point: the three AEs pilots will share the same multidisciplinary team, and the same digital platform (developed and hosted by ISS); the AEs share the common interest to involve participants with Type 2 Diabetes and lower limb complications; expert podiatrists are thus welcome in the

multidisciplinary team; apparently, there is no need to involve nurses, since any possible change in medication will be only managed by the reference diabetologists. Dr Bulzomì (ASLROMA2) could not attend the March 29 meeting but he was contacted and informed before and after the meeting.

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meeting date: April 14 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: (Claudia Giacomozzi, Alberto Piaggese, Rocco Bulzomì, Dario Pitocco)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team (Marco Mancuso, Rosa Asprino, Elisabetta Iacopi, Francesco Giangreco, Sara Di Biase, Sara Monte, Federica Conenna, Angelo Emilio Claro, Davide Mirra, Marta Barbalace)

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D practice is to reduce the burden of type 2 diabetes and of its complications in overweight or obese individuals and possibly reduce medication by: increasing motivation and daily activity, improving nutrition, quality of life and social interaction, reducing body weight.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

Patients' perspective: to improve the quality of life of individuals with Type 2 Diabetes also in the presence of (still manageable) complications, and to increase their awareness about the disease and the role of healthy lifestyles in reducing its burden.

Clinicians' perspective: to explore the potential role of healthier lifestyles adoption and maintenance in supporting the "reverse type 2 diabetes" paradigm; to implement a structured model of care based on previously conducted exploratory, individual attempts dealing with "consciousness of the disease and motivation to react" and with "new nutrition paradigms in diabetes"

Health System stakeholder: to explore a better management of type 2 diabetes through a new model of care relying on healthier lifestyles and digital health

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date(-s): April 19 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: (Claudia Giacomozzi, Alberto Piaggese, Rocco Bulzomì, Dario Pitocco)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team (Marco Mancuso, Rosa Asprino, Elisabetta Iacopi, Francesco Giangreco, Sara Di Biase, Sara Monte, Federica Conenna, Angelo Emilio Claro, Davide Mirra, Marta Barbalace)

External participants, providing the full overview at national, regional and local level (Flavia Pricci ISS, Mustazzolu Alessandro ISS, Piero Marchetti AOUP, Luisa Marina Mariani Italian MoH)

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 funds (grants and programmes) to promote digital health	1 health professionals specialized in healthy lifestyle promotion not included in healthcare systems	1 funds (grants and programmes) to sustain digitally-based initiative for non-communicable diseases prevention	1 poor investment in the public health service
2 national plan for chronic diseases associated with PNRR-Mission 6 initiatives	2 patients' inadequate digital skills and resources	2 integration of/coordination among regional and national e-health services	2
3 positive impact of e-health initiatives during Sars-Cov2 pandemic	3 patients' inadequate knowledge and awareness of the disease and its complications	3 integration of currently excluded health professions in the healthcare systems	3
4 raising interest towards health promotion	4 patients' inadequate motivation to relevant changes towards healthier lifestyles	4	4
5 raising interest to educate and train multidisciplinary teams towards integrated, healthier lifestyles promotion	5 patients' inadequate socio-economic conditions to support changes towards healthier lifestyles	5	5

At local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 Raising interest on exploring reversing type 2 diabetes	1 patients' inadequate socio-economic conditions to support changes towards healthier lifestyles	1 funds (grants and programmes) to assess reversibility of type 2 diabetes	1 poor investment in the public health service
2 plans for re-organization of territory healthcare	2 patients' inadequate motivation to relevant changes towards healthier lifestyles	2 re-organization of territory healthcare	2
3 positive impact of e-health local initiatives	3	3 integration of e-health initiatives in regional health systems	3
4 interest in motivating patients, families and caregivers towards healthier lifestyles	4	4	4
5 ISS expertise in digital health programmes	5	5	5

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
ISS, Head of Department		3	
ISS, Head of IT Service		1	
ISS, Head of Scientific Communication Service		4	
AOUP, Director of Diabetology Unit		1	
Italian MoH, Prevention Unit		3	
Regional Health Service			Waiting for contacts
Patients' associations			To be contacted afterwards
Scientific Societies			To be contacted afterwards

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: April 21 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: (Claudia Giacomozzi, Alberto Piaggese, Rocco Bulzomì, Dario Pitocco)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
1 ISS expertise in digital health programmes	1 patients' inadequate motivation to relevant changes towards healthier lifestyles
2 interest in motivating patients, families and caregivers towards healthier lifestyles	2 patients' inadequate digital skills and resources
3 raising interest to educate and train multidisciplinary teams towards integrated, healthier lifestyles promotion	3 patients' inadequate knowledge and awareness of the disease and its complications
4 interest on reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes and obesity	4
5 Raising interest on exploring reversing type 2 diabetes	5

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
1 positive impact of e-health local initiatives	1 poor investment in the public health service
2 plans for re-organization of territory healthcare	2 patients' inadequate socio-economic conditions to support changes towards healthier lifestyles

3 funds (grants and programmes) to assess reversibility of type 2 diabetes	3 patients' inadequate digital skills and resources
4 integration of currently excluded health professions in the healthcare systems	4
5 integration of/coordination among regional and national e-health services	5

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D practice is to reduce the burden of type 2 diabetes and of its complications in overweight or obese individuals and possibly reduce medication by: increasing motivation and daily activity, improving nutrition, quality of life and social interaction, reducing body weight.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

Patients' perspective: to improve the quality of life of individuals with Type 2 Diabetes also in the presence of (still manageable) complications, and to increase their awareness about the disease and the role of healthy lifestyles in reducing its burden.

Clinicians' perspective: to explore the potential role of healthier lifestyles adoption and maintenance in supporting the "reverse type 2 diabetes" paradigm; to implement a structured model of care based on previously conducted exploratory, individual attempts dealing with "consciousness of the disease and motivation to react" and with "new nutrition paradigms in diabetes"

Health System stakeholder: to explore a better management of type 2 diabetes through a new model of care relying on healthier lifestyles and digital health

CONSOLIDATED MULTIDISCIPLINARY TEAM AT THE DATE OF THIS DOCUMENT DELIVERY (changes may occur, which will be reported accordingly)

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Marco Mancuso	Associated to ASLROMA2	also in the role of Diabetes Expert Podiatrist
Diabetologist 1	Elisabetta Iacopi	AOUP	
Diabetologist 2	Francesco Giangreco	AOUP	
Dietician 1	Rosa Asprino	Associated to ASLROMA2	

Psychologist 1	Sara Di Biase	Associated to AOUP	
Psychologist 2	Angelo Emilio Claro	FPG	Specialized in psychiatry and psychotherapy
Coach 1	Sara Monte	Associated to FPG	
Coach 2	Federica Conenna	Associated to FPG	
CD4 platform consultant	Marta Barbalace	ISS	
CD4 platform developer	Davide Mirra	ISS	
C4D pilot coordinator	Claudia Giacomozzi	ISS	also in the role of digital platform coordinator
Expert 1	Alberto Piaggese	AOUP	
Expert 2	Rocco Bulzoni	ASLROMA2	
Expert 3	Dario Pitocco	FPG	

Attachment VII Malta

GOZO GENERAL HOSPITAL,

supported by MINISTRY FOR HEALTH

MALTA

Authors: Glorianne Busuttil, Mariella Borg Buontempo

Date: 29th May 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

Contact e-mail: care4diabetes@nijz.si

jelka.zaletel@kclj.si, anja.brunec@nijz.si, denis.opresnik@nijz.si

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	21.04.2023 – 23.05.2023	Glorianne Busuttil	
II	22.05.2023	Glorianne Busuttil	
III	24.05.2023	Glorianne Busuttil	
IV	26.05.2023	Glorianne Busuttil	
	May 29th 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

Abbreviations:

GGH: Gozo General Hospital, Malta

MDH: Mater Dei Hospital, Malta

PHC: Primary Health Care, Malta

AACC: Active Ageing and Community Care, Malta

HPDP: Health Promotion & Disease Prevention Directorate, Malta

MFH: Ministry for Health, Malta

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement date: 21st April, 28th April, 3rd May and 11th May 2023

Meeting participants: All participants as listed below

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Ms. Glorianne Busuttil	HPDP	Registered Nutritionist
Expert 1	Dr Mariella Borg Buontempo	HPDP	Senior Researcher
Expert 2	Prof. Stephen Fava	MDH	Head of Diabetes & Endocrine Centre
Expert 3	Dr Josephine Bigeni	GGH	Consultant Endocrinologist & Diabetologist
<i>Decision maker 1</i>	Dr Mario Caruana Grech Perry	MDH	Chief Scientific Officer, Dietitian
<i>Decision maker 2</i>	Ms Simone Cini	GGH	Head of Nursing & Clinic Operations
<i>Decision maker 3</i>	Ms Moira Grixti	MDH	Senior Practice Nurse in Diabetes
<i>Decision maker 4</i>	Dr Jason Copperstone	MDH	Principal Psychologist
<i>Decision maker 5</i>	Dr Laner Cassar	GGH	Head of Psychology Dept
IT Expert	Ms Denise Tabone Trapani	HPDP	ICT Executive

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Ms Glorianne Busuttil	HPDP	
Medical doctor1	Dr Josephine Bigeni	GGH	
Medical doctor 2	Dr Josette Rapa	GGH	
Diabetes nurse1	Ms Moira Grixti	MDH	
Diabetes nurse 2	Ms Dorianne Attard	GGH	
Dietitian 1	Ms Ilona Pulis	PHC	
Dietitian 2	Ms Caroline Borg	AACC	
Clinical Psychologist	Dr Laner Cassar	GGH	
Psychotherapist	Ms Marija Grech Debono	GGH	

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meeting date: May 24th 2023, May 26th 2023

C4D team members: Glorianne Busuttil, Mariella Borg Buontempo, Simone Cini, Moira Grixti

Multidisciplinary team: Josette Rapa, Ilona Pulis, Caroline Borg, Marija Grech Debono.

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D in Malta is to ameliorate the current practices in diabetes care as delivered in the local general hospitals, primary and community care in Malta. The pilot study will provide a more structured approach on diabetes care, with a programme that includes a multidisciplinary team of professionals that will in turn, highlight the need of a team of dedicated professionals to cater for such a growing population of Type 2 diabetics. C4D will also bring about updated knowledge on current practices in diabetes care in other European countries, with validated tools and practices. Thus, through the replication and adaptation of such practices, Malta will be able to deliver best practice for the wellbeing of the Maltese population. In addition, the digital platform, and other social media platforms, will provide updated and continuous support to the pilot participants. While hoping that this study will be sustainable in long term, Malta plans to replicate the study in the larger hospital in Malta and thereafter to roll out the project to include primary, secondary and community care.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

The scope of the C4D practice in Malta is based on the following;

- To develop a structured approach to the care of Type 2 diabetes
- To highlight the importance of a multidisciplinary team when caring for clients suffering from Type 2 diabetes
- To identify the gaps in current management of Type 2 diabetes and work on ways of how to ameliorate the services using the C4D project
- To identify the gaps in education for the MDT and increase their skills to provide a holistic approach
- To increase the efficiency of the existing resources on diabetes through the digital platform and social media platform.
- To work on providing further resources on diabetes care
- To develop an action plan to be able to scale it up and deliver it in Malta's general hospital and other clinics

- To use the C4D EU project to bring out the importance of optimal care of clients diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes from all aspects of care, both at personal and national level.
- To empower clients to self-manage their condition which in turn will help them in making informed choices on their health
- Together with the clients, to assess the individual’s specific education needs, work on common goals, work on a plan and its implementation and monitor its outcome.

The team met on various occasions and formulated the above. However, C4D Malta team is aware that these are not final and are subject to changes.

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date(-s): April 19th 2023, May 3rd, May 24th and May 26th 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Glorianne Busuttil, Mariella Borg Buontempo, Stephen Fava.

Multidisciplinary team: Josette Rapa, Moira Grixti, Ilona Pulis, Caroline Borg.

External participants, providing the full overview at national, regional and local level: Amanda Bugeja.

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 Diabetes is a national priority in Malta	1 Projections not all accomplished as it is a 4-year project and priorities changed due to Covid pandemic	1 Redesign of a new National Diabetes Strategy	1 Priorities might change
2 Diabetes tackled at both individual, societal, and family perspective. Approach is based on how the disease impacts the person as a whole	2 Cooperation is required from the public and unfortunately, not always present	2 Development of new ways on how to involve the public	2
3 Specialised care delivered by MDT to	3 Shortage of staff and increased workload and patient needs due to	3 Priorities being developed in new strategy	3 Human and financial resources may not be adequate

newly diagnosed diabetic patient	increasing obesity and older population		
4 Shared care programmes with multidisciplinary team and PHC	4 Shortage of Staff, increased workload, priorities change	4 Integrated Social marketing programme	4
5 Work on modifiable risk factors	5 Do not always refer clients to the professional providing specialised care or not aware of such services	5 Integrated approach to tackle chronic disease is the way forward	5

At local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 National Diabetes Yearly conference	1 Not all professionals invited to attend	1 Involve a wider cohort of professionals	1 May not attend due to workload and shortage of staff
2 Introduction of telemedicine during Covid pandemic	2 Public might not be that fluent in digital health and prefer face-to-face interaction	2 Extend the service to clients diagnosed in Type 2 diabetes	2 Education to the public required
3 Diabetes management course at university level available	3 Limit on the person who can enrol	3 Offer such programmes at CPD level	3 Does not necessarily mean a greater intake!
4 Centre of Excellence in Diabetes Care – under construction	4	4	4
5 Interest at large on healthy lifestyle, even amongst local councils	5 Delivery of services dependent on budget availability of local council	5 Becomes a Public Health Priority with Government providing further funding	5
6 Education material available	6 Material needs to be updated	6 Integrate them in a digital platform and made available this way	6 Digital platform under construction

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
Steering Group of the National Diabetes Strategy (2016-2020; 2023 -)	Known	Informed	
Maltese Diabetes Association	known	informed	
Malta Association of Public Health Medicine	known	informed	
Malta Health Network	known	informed	

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: May 26th 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Glorianne Busuttil, Mariella Borg Buontempo

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
1 C4D members - good relationship with the Steering Group of Diabetes Strategy for Malta	1

2 C4D members – Good relationship with Head of Diabetes and Endocrine Centre and coordinators of diabetes conference	2
3 Good relationship with developing body of telemedicine	3
4 Good relationship with Local Council Mayors and able to deliver further services related to diabetes of which being; weight management, smoking cessation, mental wellbeing and resilience and self-management programme of chronic conditions	4
5 Educational material available and able to work on further material to educate the public	5
6 MDT skilled at EU projects	
7 Supported by MDH, the main general hospital	

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
1 Availability of staff for further training	1 Shortage of staff and prioritisation of work might affect
2 Staff forming part of the Centre of Excellence in Diabetes Care	2 Workload of staff may affect rollout of C4D project
3 Availability of Diabetes Education programmes currently in place locally	3
4 Digitalisation and telemedicine on Diabetes education	4

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D project in Malta is to ameliorate the current practices in diabetes care as delivered in the local general hospitals, primary and community care in Malta. The pilot study will provide a more structured approach on diabetes care, with a programme that includes a multidisciplinary team of professionals that will in turn, highlight the need of a team of dedicated professionals to cater for such a growing population of Type 2 diabetics. C4D will also bring about updated knowledge on current practices in diabetes care in other European countries, with validated tools and practices. Thus, through the replication and adaptation of such practices, Malta will be able to deliver best practice for the wellbeing of the Maltese population. In addition, the digital platform, and other social media platforms, will provide updated and continuous support to the pilot participants. While hoping that this study will be sustainable in long term, Malta plans to

replicate the study in the larger hospital in Malta and thereafter to roll out the project to include primary, secondary and community care.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

The scope of the practice in Malta is based on the following;

- To develop a structured approach to the care of Type 2 diabetes
- To highlight the importance of a multidisciplinary team when caring for clients suffering from Type 2 diabetes
- To identify the gaps in current management of diabetes and work on ways of how to ameliorate the services using the C4D project
- To identify the gaps in education for the MDT and increase their skills to provide a holistic patient-centred approach
- To increase the efficiency of the existing resources on diabetes through the digital platform and social media platform.
- To work on developing further resources on diabetes care
- To develop an action plan to be able to scale it up and deliver it in Malta's general hospital and other clinics
- To use the C4D EU project to bring out the importance of optimal care of clients diagnosed with Type 2 care from all aspects of care, both at personal and national level.
- To empower clients to self-manage their condition which in turn will help them in making informed choices on their health
- Together with the clients, to assess the individual's specific education needs, work on common goals, work on a plan and its implementation and monitor its outcome.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Attachment VIII Poland

National Health Fund, supported by Medical University of Warsaw (MUW)
Poland

Authors: Agata Szymczak, Katarzyna Wiktorzak, Katarzyna Kułaga, Joanna Ostrowska

Date: April 30 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

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Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	03.04.2023	Agata Szymczak	
II	13.04.2023	Agata Szymczak	
III	17.04.2023	Agata Szymczak	
IV	19.04.2023	Agata Szymczak	
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement date: 15.03.2023

Meeting participants: Agata Szymczak, Katarzyna Klonowska, Anna Miszczak, Sylwia Wądrzyk-Bularz

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Agata Szymczak	National Health Fund	
Expert 1	Katarzyna Klonowska	National Health Fund	
<i>Decision maker 1</i>	Dariusz Dziełak	National Health Fund	
<i>Decision maker 2</i>	Anna Miszczak	National Health Fund	
<i>Decision maker 3</i>	Sylwia Wądrzyk- Bularz	National Health Fund	

The aim of this kick-off meeting was to present a projects' assumptions to decision makers at National Health Fund and to build up a multidisciplinary team within National Health Fund.

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Agata Szymczak	National Health Fund	
Expert 1	Katarzyna Wiktorzak	National Health Fund	
Expert 2	Katarzyna Kułaga	National Health Fund	
Expert 3	Iwona Poznerowicz	National Health Fund	
Expert 4	Rafał Kozłowski	National Health Fund	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	<i>To be decided</i>		
Diabetes nurse	Mariola Pietrzak, PhD	Medical University of Warsaw	
Diabetes nurse	Ewa Kobos, PhD	Medical University of Warsaw	
Dietitian	Joanna Ostrowska, PhD	Medical University of Warsaw	
Coach	Marzena Sekuła, PhD	Medical University of Warsaw	
Medical doctor	Anna Jeznach-Steinhagen, PhD	Medical University of Warsaw	

These are the preliminary multidisciplinary team members. Once the Primary Care Clinic (in which patients' recruiting process will take place) is finally chosen, new health care providers will be added to the team (e.g.: GP)

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meeting date: 13.04.2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: (Agata Szymczak, Katarzyna Wiktorzak, Katarzyna Kułaga, Iwona Poznerowicz)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team (dr Joanna Ostrowska)

The aim of C4D practice is to

- implement a good practice into the universal model of care in Poland in order to reverse treatment of type 2 diabetes by limiting pharmacotherapy in a safe and effective way through behavioral therapy,
- promote a lifestyle changes that can bring improved quality of life in people with type 2 diabetes
- reduce healthcare associated costs
- develop and disseminate a team/multidisciplinary/comprehensive relations with patients. This will be possible only when attention is being paid to the complexity of the type2 diabetes therapies — i.e. the need to involve many specialists who will support patients in taking an active role in managing their disease and build their motivation to undertake changes.
- Increase patients' wellbeing and quality of life

The scope of the practice is to

- develop an effective model of organisation of care for patients with type 2 diabetes that can be implemented in different healthcare units
- train the team of multidisciplinary specialists by experts from the Dutch organisation "Voeding Leef" who will conduct a pilot program in our country, evaluate its effects and will train other specialists in order to scale this practice
- prepare a recruitment strategy for C4Dpractice
- develop a repository of didactic materials for trainers
- develop a Knowledge Exchange Platform for Patients (maintaining effects for patients participating in the program, motivation to change for new patients, support groups)

- implement lifestyle interventions on the group of 40 patients with diabetes 2 (by achieving satisfactory metabolic compensation, which will allow for complete or partial abandonment of pharmacological treatment).
- translate and adapt to polish environment educational materials for patients for better self-management
- evaluate the pilot achievements
- prepare implementation report of pilot study
- present the conclusions of the pilot study carried out to the Polish Ministry of Health in order to possibly scale the described practice in our country

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date(-s): 13.04.2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: (Agata Szymczak, Katarzyna Wiktorzak, Katarzyna Kułaga, Iwona Poznerowicz)

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team (dr Joanna Ostrowska)

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
Existence of regional health policy programmes that include behavioural therapy for type 2 diabetes patients	Limited clinical setting with little availability of multidisciplinary teams unwilling to the new medial approaches	Dissemination of behavioural therapy-based care model in subsequent practices and strengthening/promoting good practices based on behavioural therapy	Limited range of practical training
Possibility to implement regional policy programmes by other local governments according to the same scheme- if they get a positive recommendation of Agency for Health	Lack of effective implementation of diabetic guidelines into the clinical practice	Implementation of universal model of care focused on behavioural therapy	Differences between different solutions/ Interventions — inability to compare

Technology Assessment and Tariffs			
Inclusion of type 2 diabetes patients' education in the coordinated care at primary level (medical team of GP, nurse, educator and dietician)	Regional outreach of Health Prevention Programme	Ability to scale proven and comparable solutions	The need to apply for programs by local governments instead of introducing a systemic solution
Increasing awareness among patients about importance of self-management of disease	The diabetic path is not systemic solution- optional implementation of coordinated care in primary healthcare units	The possibility of disseminating the model of coordinated care and ultimately covering this model of care for the whole population	
	No guarantee for changing the patient's lifestyle despite the support of specialists	Reduction of the use of medicines by patients and improving the health parameters of patients covered by the programme by reversing the care model	
	Dispersion of activities with only regional coverage- no systemic solutions		

At local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
multidisciplinary team already available at primary health units with adapted coordinated care approach	limited clinical setting with little availability of multidisciplinary teams unwilling to the new medical approaches	Positive adaptation of new paths into everyday clinical practice	Potential obstacles arising outside local setting
Support from NFZ and WUM's experts (diabetic, dietician experts included)		Education supported by the use of digital platform	
Basic healthy lifestyle education already available at primary healthcare level			

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
Ministry of Health/ Adam Niedzielski – Minister of Health	known	informed	
Polish Association of Diabetology/ prof. Leszek Czupryniak	known	consultation	
Association of Family Medicine/ Prof. Agnieszka Mastalerz- Migas	known	informed	
Federation of Education in Diabetology/ dr Ewa Kobos	known	full participation	
Regional consultant in the field of family nursing- dr Mariola Pietrzak	known	full participation	
AOTMiT- Agency for Health Technology Assessment and Tariffs	known	Briefly informed	
Section of Medical Dietetics POLSPEN/prof. Dorota Szostak-Węgierek	known	consultation	
Rector of Medical University of Warsaw – prof. Zbigniew Gacjong	known	briefly informed	
Dean of the Faculty of Health Sciences in Medical University of Warsaw – prof. Mariusz Gujski	known	informed	Informational meeting will take place soon

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: 19.04.2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: (Agata Szymczak, Katarzyna Wiktorzak, Katarzyna Kułaga, Iwona Poznerowicz, Rafał Kozłowski)

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
increase patient self-awareness of treatment, behavioural habits in diabetes life	the approach focuses on self-discipline and patient engagement
availability of educational materials for all patients	small sample of patients in the pilot phase – unrepresentative
achieving better quality of life for type 2 diabetes	the need to adapt the IT system in the project
access to the programme that has been validated and is ready for use	

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
increasing the importance of patients self -management	low involvement rates of patients, multidisciplinary teams, GPs
reducing the cost of diabetes treatment	unwillingness to modify the medical procedures
increased access to comprehensive diabetes care	unwillingness to modify eating, physical activity habits, systematic use of medicines
	insufficient cooperation between primary healthcare and outpatient specialized care
	no guarantee of obtaining financial savings for the health sector

The aim of C4D practice is to

- implement a good practice into the universal model of care in Poland in order to reverse treatment of type 2 diabetes by limiting pharmacotherapy in a safe and effective way through behavioural therapy,
- promote a lifestyle changes that can bring improved quality of life in people with type 2 diabetes
- reduce healthcare associated costs
- develop and disseminate a team/multidisciplinary/comprehensive relations with patients. This will be possible only when attention is being paid to the complexity of the type2 diabetes therapies — i.e. the need to involve many specialists who will support patients in taking an active role in managing their disease and build their motivation to undertake changes.
- Increase patients' wellbeing and quality of life

The scope of the practice is to

- develop an effective model of organisation of care for patients with type 2 diabetes that can be implemented in different healthcare units
- train the team of multidisciplinary specialists by experts from the Dutch organisation "Voeding Leef" who will conduct a pilot program in our country, evaluate its effects and will train other specialists in order to scale this practice
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- translate and adapt to polish environment educational materials for patients for better self-management
- evaluate the pilot achievements
- prepare implementation report of pilot study
- present the conclusions of the pilot study carried out to the Polish Ministry of Health in order to possibly scale the described practice in our country.

Attachment IX Portugal

Directorate General of Health - DGS

Portugal

Authors: Rogério Ribeiro, Joana Fonseca, José Does, Cristina Portugal, Ana Viegas, Ana Jesus, João Raposo, Inês Teixeira Duarte, Eugénia Pedro, Laura Martins, Lia Ferreira, Sónia do Vale

Date: April 30 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

Contact e-mail: care4diabetes@nijz.si

jelka.zaletel@kclj.si, anja.brunec@nijz.si, denis.opresnik@nijz.si

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	12th April 2023	Sónia do Vale (DGS)	
II	19th April 2023	Sónia do Vale (DGS)	
III	19th April 2023	Sónia do Vale (DGS)	
IV	19th April 2023	Sónia do Vale (DGS)	
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

Abbreviations:

DGS - Directorate General of Health

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting date: 12/04/2023

Meeting participants: Sónia do Vale, Cristina Portugal, José Dores, Eugénia Pedro, Joana Fonseca, Rogério Ribeiro, João Raposo, Ana Viegas, Lia Ferreira

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Sónia do Vale	DGS	
Expert 1	Rogério Ribeiro	APDP	
Expert 2	João Raposo	APDP	
Expert 3	José Dores	DGS	
Expert 4	Eugénia Pedro	DGS	
Expert 5	Ana Viegas	ARS Algarve	
Expert 6	Lia Ferreira	CHU Santo António	

Multidisciplinary teams:

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	João Filipe Raposo / Rogério Ribeiro	APDP	
Medical doctor1	João Filipe Raposo / Rita Nortadas	APDP	
Diabetes nurse1	Dulce do Ó	APDP	
Dietitian1	Lisandra Ribeiro	APDP	
Psychologist1	Ana Lúcia Covinhas	APDP	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Ana Filipa Viegas / Ana Isabel Jesus	UCSP Mar - ACeS Algarve III Sotavento	
Medical doctor1	Ana Isabel Jesus	USF Balsa - ACeS Algarve III Sotavento	
Diabetes nurse1	Dulcineia Guerra	UCC Talábriga - ACeS Algarve III Sotavento	

Dietitian1	Laura Martins	URAP ACeS Algarve III Sotavento	
Psychologist1	Rosália Fonseca	URAP ACeS Algarve III Sotavento	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	José Dorés	Unidade Local de Saúde do Baixo Alentejo	
Medical doctor1	Luís Coentro	Unidade Local de Saúde do Baixo Alentejo	
Diabetes nurse1	José Dorés	Unidade Local de Saúde do Baixo Alentejo	
Dietitian1	Bárbara Valadas	Unidade Local de Saúde do Baixo Alentejo	
Psychologist1	Inês Costa Neves	Unidade Local de Saúde do Baixo Alentejo	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Helena Cardoso / Lia Ferreira	Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Santo António	
Medical doctor1	Lia Ferreira	Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Santo António	
Medical doctor2	Isabel Palma	Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Santo António	
Diabetes nurse1	Sara Pinto	Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Santo António	
Dietitian1	Mariana Fraga	Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Santo António	

Psychologist1	Inês Carvalho	Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Santo António	
Psychologist2	Sara Viveiros	Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Santo António	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Eugénia Pedro	ACeS do Estuário do Tejo	
Medical doctor1	Maria Manuel Marques	ACeS do Estuário do Tejo	
Diabetes nurse1	Eugénia Pedro	ACeS do Estuário do Tejo	
Dietitian1	Joana Fonseca	DGS	
Dietitian2	Inês Teixeira Duarte	DGS	
Psychologist1	Filipa Santos	ACeS do Estuário do Tejo	

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meeting date: 19/04/2023

Meeting participants:

C4D team members: Cristina Portugal, Rogério Ribeiro, Ana Jesus, José Dores, Joana Fonseca, Sónia do Vale, Inês Teixeira Duarte, Eugénia Pedro, Ana Viegas, Laura Martins

Multidisciplinary team: Ana Jesus, José Dores, Joana Fonseca, Inês Teixeira Duarte, Eugénia Pedro, Ana Viegas, Laura Martins

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D practice is to improve the clinical outcomes and quality of life of people with type 2 diabetes through the establishment and evaluation of a safe and structured European Good Practice.

Scope of the C4D practice is to empower people with type 2 diabetes to adapt and adopt lifestyle measures, and to provide training to the healthcare teams in motivational and coaching approaches, in primary, hospital and patient association care units, to improve self-management support and care delivery.

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date: 19/04/2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Cristina Portugal, Rogério Ribeiro, Ana Jesus, José Dores, Joana Fonseca, Sónia do Vale, Inês Teixeira Duarte, Eugénia Pedro, Ana Viegas, Laura Martins

Multidisciplinary team: Ana Jesus, José Dores, Joana Fonseca, Inês Teixeira Duarte, Eugénia Pedro, Ana Viegas, Laura Martins

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 Specialised human resources	1 Scarcity of psychologists, nutritionists and exercise physiologists across the NHS	1 Adapt dietary guidelines	1 Lack of financial resources

2 Partnerships with Municipalities	2 Low data portability	2 Adapt motivation assessment	2 Lack of human resources on NHS
3 Participation of patient representatives	3 Fragmented care and limitation in consultation time	3 Adopt online platform	3 On-going major organizational changes
4 Diabetes Functional Coordinating Units	4 Low health literacy	4 Add quality of life assessment	4 Low formal commitment on community lifestyle programs
5 Built knowledge with “Diabetes em Movimento” and “Juntos é mais fácil” (lifestyle programs)	5 Limited training for doctors and nurses in coaching and motivational approaches	5 Add social support	5

At local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
5	5	5	5

In Portugal there is no major difference between local and national levels so the analysis is very similar.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
Diabetes Association Patient	APDP, FPAD	1 (APDP), 3 (FPAD)	
Academic institutions	University hospitals	4	
Primary care health units	Diabetes Functional Coordinating Units	3	
Regional Authorities Health	Regional Diabetes Coordinators	3	

Scientific societies	SPD, SPEDM, SPMI, SPMGF	3	
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*1= full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2= consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3= informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: 19/04/2023

Meeting participants:

C4D team members: Cristina Portugal, Rogério Ribeiro, Ana Jesus, José Dorés, Joana Fonseca, Sónia de Vale, Inês Teixeira Duarte, Eugénia Pedro, Ana Viegas, Laura Martins

Multidisciplinary team: Ana Jesus, José Dorés, Joana Fonseca, Inês Teixeira Duarte, Eugénia Pedro, Ana Viegas, Laura Martins

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative = weakness
1 – Existence of multidisciplinary teams	1 – Lack of human resources
2 – Teams with training on diabetes	2 – Work overload of the human resources
3 – Experience in previous lifestyle education projects	3 – Financial sustainability of the project
4 – Participation of multidisciplinary teams from all over the country	
5 - Participation of multidisciplinary teams from all levels of care (primary care, hospital care, and patient association)	

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative = threats
1 – A National Program for Diabetes	1 - Financial sustainability of the project

2 – Uniformized national health registers	2 – Bureaucratic restrains
3 – The existence of national campaigns for the promotion of healthy lifestyles	3 – Lack of health literacy / lack of nutritional literacy
4 – More than 850 thousand people registered with the diagnosis of diabetes	4 – Lack of digital literacy
5 – Expansion and replication (bench marking) of the project available	5 – Low maintenance of the participants in other lifestyles programs
6 – Community engagement and ownership	

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The aim of C4D practice is to improve the clinical outcomes and quality of life of people with type 2 diabetes through the establishment and evaluation of a safe and structured European Good Practice.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

Scope of the C4D practice is to empower people with type 2 diabetes to adapt and adopt lifestyle measures, and to provide training to the healthcare teams in motivational and coaching approaches, in primary, hospital and patient association care units, to improve self-management support and care delivery.

Attachment X Slovakia

NAME OF C4D PARTNER WITH PILOT IMPLEMENTATION, supported by NAME OF C4D COMPETENT MoH

Slovakia

Authors: Hana Wijntjes, Natália Ballová, Mária Hlásna, Soňa Senderáková

Date: April 30 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

Contact e-mail: care4diabetes@nijz.si

jelka.zaletel@kclj.si, anja.brunec@nijz.si, denis.opresnik@nijz.si

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	27.3.2023	Natália Ballová	
II	10.4.2023	Natália Ballová	
III	20.4.2023	Mária Hlásna	
IV	26.4.2023	Natália Ballová	
	April 30 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement date: 27.3.2023

Meeting participants: Hana Wijntjes, Natália Ballová, Mária Hlásna

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Natália Ballová	MoH SR	
Expert 1	Hana Wijntjes	MoH SR	
Expert 2			
<i>Decision maker 1</i>			
<i>Decision maker 2</i>			
Project manager	Mária Hlásna	MoH SR	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	TBD		
Medical doctor1	TBD		
Diabetes nurse1	TBD		
Dietitian1	TBD		
Coach1	TBD		

1. What would you like to accomplish within the work of C4D?

Implementation of pilot for 2 groups of patients should result in:

- Improvement of their health conditions
- Gathering of the patients and experts feedback on programme
- Gaining new skills for experts

2. When C4D ends, what would you like to see as the result?

- Measurable evidence of programme which could be reused
- Spreading of the basic knowledge about the programme for other patients with diabetes and wide spectrum of experts in the field

3. What would you like to see that would happen after C4D ends?

- Promotion of the programme among public
- Extension of the programme for other patients
- Increase of our engagement (as Slovakia / MoH SR) in other diabetes related programmes or projects

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meeting date: 10.4.2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Hana Wijntjes, Natália Ballová, Mária Hlásna

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team – Not defined yet

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

To improve general health conditions of population in Slovakia with focus on diabetes type 2 prevention and treatment, by reducing related risk factors and improving health of patients (healthier blood glucose levels with potential lower medication consumption) through effective lifestyle treatment and implemented programme.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

Scope in number of participants: 40 patients in 2 groups in Pilot programme

Scope of activities:

- Transfer of the identified best practice “Reverse Diabetes2 Now experience” from VL and implementation in Slovak conditions which includes activities such as:
 - Training of Experts
 - Training of patients
 - Implementation of effective lifestyle treatment for patients
 - Monitoring and reporting
 - Building of Evidence based on outputs and measurement

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date(-s): 20.4.2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Hana Wijntjes, Natália Ballová, Mária Hlásna, Soňa Senderáková

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team – Not defined yet

External participants, providing the full overview at national, regional and local level – No external participants

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1 Existing chain of regional health consultancy offices (36)	1 Low attendance and popularity in regional health consultancy offices	1 Available EU funding	1 Low workforce
2 Existion	2 lack of national plan to beat diabetes	2	2
3	3 National Health Promotion program does not mention DM	3	3
4	4 Not enough funding	4	4

At local setting – not applicable in Slovak setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
5	5	5	5

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
MoH SR	Hana Wijntjes	1	Senior Expert
MoH SR	Natália Ballová	1	Project manager
MoH SR	Mária Hlásna	1	Project manager
St. Elizabeth University of Health and Social Work in Bratislava	Marianna Mrázová	1	Senior Expert – Programme Coordinator
Public Health Authorities		2	
Central State and Administration Bodies		4	
Local Administration Bodies		4	
Regional Authorities (8 regions)		4	
Municipalities		4	
Medical and Public Health schools		4	
Research and Educational Institutions		4	
Healthcare Providers		4	
Health Insurance Groups		4	
Social Insurance Group		4	

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: 26.4.2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Hana Wijntjes, Natália Ballová, Mária Hlásna, Soňa Senderáková

At decision of the organiser: Multidisciplinary team – not defined yet

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4
5	5

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
1 NCDs are currently one the most important topics in Slovakia and therefore we see the chance that diabetes and lifestyle education topic will increase in importance	1 Turbulent political situation in Slovakia
2 Dedicated increased financial support in new state budget for next year based on evidence from the C4D project.	2 Replacement of team members due to external circumstances
3 Increased knowledge among patients and healthcare providers could lead to more engagement in projects such as C4D.	3 Shortage of healthcare workers due to demographic situation, educational gap and insufficient remuneration.
4 C4D evidence could lead to increased research in the field, investments in medical devices or development of further frameworks.	4

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

Objective is the same.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

Scope is the same.

Attachment XI Slovenia

GENERAL HOSPITAL NOVO MESTO,
supported by NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF PUBLIC HEALTH
SLOVENIA

Authors: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec, Jana Klavs, Milivoj Piletič, Jelka Zaletel

Date: April 21 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

Contact e-mail: care4diabetes@nijz.si

jelka.zaletel@kclj.si, anja.brunec@nijz.si, denis.opresnik@nijz.si

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	Feb 10 2023, Mar 14 2023	Denis Oprešnik	
II	March 10 2023, March 14 2023, March 21 2023, March 28 2023	Denis Oprešnik	
III	March 16 2023, March 21 2023, April 13 2023	Denis Oprešnik	
IV	April 20 2023	Denis Oprešnik	
	April 21 2023	Delivered to e-mail care4diabetes@nijz.si	

Abbreviations:

NIJZ – National institute of Public Health Slovenia

SBNM - General hospital Novo mesto

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement dates: Feb 10 2023, Mar 14 2023 (second diabetes education expert)

Meetings' participants: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec, Jana Klavs, Milivoj Piletič, Jelka Zaletel

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Denis Oprešnik	NIJZ	
Expert	Jana Klavs	NIJZ	
Expert	Milivoj Piletič	SBNM	
Expert	Andreja Semolič Valič	NIJZ	
Expert	Anja Brunec	NIJZ	
Expert	Jelka Zaletel	NIJZ	
Expert	Claudia Adamič	NIJZ	Financial management, invited if advice needed on this topic

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
<i>C4D practice coordinator</i>	<i>To be decided</i>	SBNM	
Medical doctor	Milivoj Piletič	SBNM	
Diabetes nurse	Andreja Žnidaršič	SBNM	
Dietitian	Irena Hren	SBNM	During planning, monitoring, evaluation
Diabetes nurse	Tjaša Janjoš	SBNM	
Diabetes nurse	Bernarda Bobič	SBNM	

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meetings dates: March 10 2023, March 14 2023, March 21 2023, March 28 2023

Meetings' participants

C4D team members: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec, Jana Klavs, Milivoj Piletič, Jelka Zaletel

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice:

The purpose of C4D practice Slovenia is to increase the capacity and quality of education at secondary healthcare level including new topics, new approaches and digital tools, with an aim to increase the efficiency of the existing resources in delivering effective lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes. In addition, C4D serves as an unique opportunity to introduce to Slovenian context the approaches on how to design, pilot, monitor and evaluate educational programmes for patients in general, how to design and evaluate in a formative way digitally supported educational programmes with an aim to optimise the effectiveness based on the future patient needs and availability of the human resources, and to deliver the proposal for upgrading of the existing system for training of diabetes educators and medical doctors on coaching and the use of digital solutions.

Scope of the C4D practice:

The scope of the C4D practice Slovenia is

- to design, test and evaluate (using PDSA cycles),
- a digitally-enhanced educational program for patients with type 2 diabetes to support their healthy life choices, delivered at secondary level of care,
- that will be compatible to the organizational, professional and cultural context, existing terminology and symbols and building on the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches, and upgrading them with specific topics (physical activity, sleep and stress reduction),
- by fully embracing a co-creation approach and research methodologies in social sciences, including the most recent ones,
- with the optimal use of face-to-face interaction in combination with digital solution to increase the efficiency of the existent (human) resources,
- and to identify the approaches to increase the skills of diabetes educators, medical doctors and other healthcare professionals in areas identified (such as coaching, use of digital tools, and related to physical activity, sleep and stress reduction as topics),

- including development of action plan for scaling-up the educational program at national level including the permanent platform, and that will include the identified gaps related to diabetes education (competencies, approaches, topics, organisation) at micro (individual patient-HCP interaction), meso (healthcare organisation including healthcare teams) and macro level (healthcare system),
- and to use the potential of C4D to increase visibility of importance of education in type 2 diabetes at national level.

A comment: C4D team's opinion is that they are ambitious, feasible and are leading to sustainability and scale-up. In addition to the individual work via e-mail, we had 4 meetings to agree on the results, so it was an iterative process and C4D team is aware, that the decisions are not yet final.

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Meeting date No.1: March 16 2023 (national level), March 21 2023 and April 13 2023 (C4D level, by e-mail exchange)

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec, Jana Klavs, Milivoj Piletič, Jelka Zaletel

External participants – members of Steering Group of National Diabetes Plan 2020-2030 Mojca Gobec, Ministry of Health, Jožica Poličnik, Ministry of Health, Zdenka Tičar, Ministry of Health, Rade Brinovec Pribaković, NIJZ, Alojz Plesničar, Health Insurance Institute Slovenia, Metka Zaletel, NIJZ, Draženka Pongrac Barlovič, National association of diabetologists, Barbara Jemec Zalar, Medical Faculty, Dept. For family medicine, Mojca Urbančič, University Eye Hospital, University Medical Centre Ljubljana, Mojca Lunder, Dept. for diabetes and endocrinology, University medical Centre Ljubljana, Nataša Bratina, Dept. for diabetes and endocrinology, University Children Hospital Ljubljana, Taja Čokl, NIJZ, and Jelka Zaletel and Jana Klavs (also members of C4D team)

and external experts with national and system overview in type 2 education with focus to lifestyle intervention Sanja Vrbovšek National institute of Public Health, Davorina Petek, Marija Petek Šter and Matic Mihevc (all Medical Faculty, Dept. For family medicine)

Meeting date No.2: March 21 2023, April 13 2023 (e-mail exchange) (local setting)

C4D team members: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec, Jana Klavs, Milivoj Piletič, Jelka Zaletel

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
National diabetes plan 2020-2030 as a strategic guidance with 2yearly implementation plans, with functional Steering Group, yearly national diabetes conferences and high social media visibility	Fragmentation and regional differences, both in terms of at which point is the patient being appointed to education at the secondary level (e.g. at diagnosis, complications etc.) as well as what kind of information is being provided to them (including differences in methods and approaches). HPs at the secondary level do not have a clear understanding if and what kind of preventive (e.g. education) and therapeutic activities were provided at the primary level. Similarly, GPs do not have a clear understanding what kind of education has been provided to persons with T2D that have been appointed to education via HCPs.	Digitalisation in healthcare one of the cornerstones of health reform; in place a process to improve and extend the functionalities of GDPR-protected repository of patient data	Increasing numbers of patients with type 2 diabetes at all levels of care, with different expectations from healthcare system, including digital services and support on one hand, and having more complex conditions including unfavourable socioeconomic conditions on the other. The interventions might actually broaden the gap in health across socioeconomic gradient if not designed well.
National payer provides payment for increasing capacities at primary care and for provision of education at all levels of care	At primary care, education is mainly delivered and financed in a structured way (courses in health promotion centres with opportunities for individual education); at secondary level, the financing is different and does not support structured education and the payment of digital/non face to face visits is not clear.	Peer support (via experienced persons with T2D -'lay consultants') is being under development (Ljubljana primary care unit)	Decrease the number of healthcare professionals and other professionals working in healthcare, including those related to diabetes education.
Existence of GDPR-protected repository of patient data (with very limited functionalities) (CRPP)	There is a need to build capacities for a continuous coaching approach and lifestyle support. Education is frequently perceived (by persons with T2D and sometimes by HCPs) as	Telemedicine is in development: there are initiatives to develop standardised and unified online educational materials (videos) accessible nationwide.	The scaling up of C4D practice is highly dependent on systemic changes (and sometimes even reforms), but the outcomes are unsure

	acquiring a certain set of information (e.g. “dieting”)		
Proactive national association of nurses in diabetes education developing education at all levels of care with explicit support from MoH, including recommendations, approaches and tools,	An extensive development of new medicines and technologies (e.g. sensors) in diabetes management in recent years resulted in educators being focused on explaining their use, less on lifestyle change planning.	At MoH there is project on Health literacy to be concluded in 2023, a Strategy for Health literacy will follow; clinical pathway (also for diabetes, including gaps) was analysed within this project and what kind of information would be useful for a person with a condition traveling through the system.	
Visibility and availability of website of national association of nurses designed to support diabetes education	The numbers of RNs diabetes educators at secondary level is being reduced, while education itself became broader and more nuanced. Unclear availability and potential roles of other HPs, dietitians, psychologists, coaches, physiotherapists.	Terminology and philosophy of 19th century (speaking about services, patients, levels, specialities etc.) should be overcome and this is one of the opportunities. Language shapes reality (L. Wittgenstein). Let’s think about the level of individual person who does not care where he receives help...	
Evolving process for type 2 diabetes education at primary care (family medicine practices, health promotion centres) under the leadership of NIJZ	No systematic approach/platforms to support patients’ education		
Well studied telemedicine approaches in type 2 diabetes in primary care (and in pregnancy as a model of approach)	No common e health record		
Availability of diabetes education at primary (GPs, RNs, HPC) and secondary (hospitals –			

diabetes clinic) level of healthcare			
Adherence to (certain types of) educational programs very high			
Longterm existence of diabetes education at secondary level, with extensive trainings, knowledge and skills of diabetes teams.			

At local setting			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
Multidisciplinary team members, skilled in international projects	Extremely busy clinical setting, with unstable availability of multidisciplinary team members	Positive adaptation of everyday clinical practice	Potential obstacles arising outside the local setting
Support from NIJZ and national diabetes experts included in NIJZ team	Unclear payment for digital services	We are revitalizing regular meetings with the teams from primary sector to discuss certain topics and mainly to agree upon future collaboration and upon the way how to exchange patient data.	Current situation in the society and especially in health care sector is unsure
Basic healthy lifestyle education already available at primary healthcare teams and health promotion centres	The level of education of HCPs at primary level might vary from team to team and this is reflected in the approach to education of the patients	Education with the use of digital platform.	
Most of the patients are treated by the same team for a long time and they trust the healthcare team; if the team invites a patient to join a “project” , they usually agree and join it with high expectations	There is a “post-COVID” effect and patients are not keen to visit hospital more than really necessary.		

KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
Steering group of the National Diabetes Plan 2020-2030	known	informed	Includes among others representatives of Ministry of Health, national health insurance, national institute of public health, national patients' association, national association of family medicine specialists
National association of diabetes nurse educators	known	informed	
National association of diabetologists	known	briefly informed	
Top management in the Hospital	known	briefly informed	
Patient diabetes association Novo mesto	known	briefly informed	
National institute of public health – regional office	known	briefly informed	
Health promotion centre (Health centre Novo mesto)	known	briefly informed	

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Meeting date: April 20 2023

Meeting participants

C4D team members: Denis Oprešnik, Anja Brunec, Jana Klavs, Milivoj Piletič, Jelka Zaletel

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
Very close connection of C4D team members to National diabetes plan 2020-2030 as a strategic guidance with 2yearly implementation plans, with functional Steering Group, yearly national diabetes conferences and high social media visibility	Extremely busy clinical setting, with unstable availability of multidisciplinary team members
Very close connection of C4D team members to the proactive national association of nurses in diabetes education developing education at all levels of care with explicit support from MoH, including recommendations, approaches and tools, including a platform	
Very close connection of C4D team members to build upon the Visibility and availability of website of national association of nurses designed to support diabetes education	
Very close connection of C4D team members to the evolving process for type 2 diabetes education at primary care (family medicine practices, health promotion centres) under the leadership of NIJZ	
Multidisciplinary team members are skilled in international projects	
Support from NIJZ and national diabetes experts included in NIJZ team	
Most of the patients are treated by the same team for a long time and they trust the healthcare team; if the team invites a patient to join a “project”, they usually agree and join it with high expectations	
Positive adaptation of everyday clinical practice	
We are revitalizing regular meetings with the teams from primary sector to discuss certain topics and mainly to agree upon future collaboration and upon the way how to exchange patient data.	
Education with the use of digital platform.	

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative =threats
National payer provides payment for increasing capacities at primary care and for provision of education at all levels of care	Fragmentation and regional differences, both in terms of at which point is the patient being appointed to education at the secondary level (e.g. at diagnosis, complications etc.) as well as what kind of information is being provided to them (including differences in methods and approaches). HPs at the secondary level do not have a clear understanding if and what kind of preventive (e.g. education) and therapeutic activities were provided at the primary level. Similarly, GPs do not have a clear understanding what kind of education has been provided to persons with T2D that have been appointed to education via HCPs.
Existence of GDPR-protected repository of patient data (with very limited functionalities) (CRPP)	At primary care, education is mainly delivered and financed in a structured way (courses in health promotion centres with opportunities for individual education); at secondary level, the financing is different and does not support structured education and the payment of digital/non face to face visits is not clear.
Well studied telemedicine approaches in type 2 diabetes in primary care (and in pregnancy as a model of approach)	There is a need to build capacities for a continuous coaching approach and lifestyle support. Education is frequently perceived (by persons with T2D and sometimes by HCPs) as acquiring a certain set of information (e.g. “dieting”)
Availability of diabetes education at primary (GPs, RNs, HPC) and secondary (hospitals – diabetes clinic) level of healthcare	An extensive development of new medicines and technologies (e.g. sensors) in diabetes management in recent years resulted in educators being focused on explaining their use, less on lifestyle change planning.
Adherence to (certain types of) educational programs very high	The numbers of RNs diabetes educators at secondary level is being reduced, while education itself became broader and more nuanced. Unclear availability and potential roles of other HPs, dietitians, psychologists, coaches, physiotherapists.
Longterm existence of diabetes education at secondary level, with extensive trainings, knowledge and skills of diabetes teams.	No systematic approach/platforms to support patients’ education
Basic healthy lifestyle education already available at primary healthcare teams and health promotion centres	No common e health record

<p>Digitalisation in healthcare one of the cornerstones of health reform; in place a process to improve and extend the functionalities of GDPR-protected repository of patient data</p>	<p>Unclear payment for digital services</p>
<p>Peer support (via experienced persons with T2D -'lay consultants') is being under development (Ljubljana primary care unit)</p>	<p>The level of education of HCPs at primary level might vary from team to team and this is reflected in the approach to education of the patients</p>
<p>Telemedicine is in development: there are initiatives to develop standardised and unified online educational materials (videos) accessible nationwide.</p>	<p>There is a "post-COVID" effect and patients are not keen to visit hospital more than really necessary.</p>
<p>At MoH there is project on Health literacy to be concluded in 2023, a Strategy for Health literacy will follow; clinical pathway (also for diabetes, including gaps) was analysed within this project and what kind of information would be useful for a person with a condition traveling through the system.</p>	<p>Increasing numbers of patients with type 2 diabetes at all levels of care, with different expectations from healthcare system, including digital services and support on one hand, and having more complex conditions including unfavourable socioeconomic conditions on the other. The interventions might actually broaden the gap in health across socioeconomic gradient if not designed well.</p>
<p>Terminology and philosophy of 19th century (speaking about services, patients, levels, specialities etc.) should be overcome and this is one of the opportunities. Language shapes reality (L. Wittgenstein). Let's think about the level of individual person who does not care where he receives help...</p>	<p>Decrease the number of healthcare professionals and other professionals working in healthcare, including those related to diabetes education.</p>
	<p>The scaling up of C4D practice is highly dependent on systemic changes (and sometimes even reforms), but the outcomes are unsure</p>
	<p>Current situation in the society and especially in health care sector is unsure</p>
	<p>Potential obstacles arising outside the local setting</p>

Having all this in mind, we re-evaluated if the purpose/aim/general objective and the scope as defined in Step II need to be adapted. They should be ambitious, feasible and sustainable.

Purpose/aim/general objective of C4D practice is:

The purpose of C4D practice Slovenia is to increase the capacity and quality of education at secondary healthcare level including new topics, new approaches and digital tools, with an aim

to increase the efficiency of the existing resources in delivering effective lifestyle education in type 2 diabetes. In addition, C4D serves as an unique opportunity to introduce to Slovenian context the approaches on how to design, pilot, monitor and evaluate educational programmes for patients in general, how to design and evaluate in a formative way digitally supported educational programmes with an aim to optimise the effectiveness based on the future patient needs and availability of the human resources, and to deliver the proposal for upgrading of the existing system for training of diabetes educators and medical doctors on coaching and the use of digital solutions.

Scope of the C4D practice is:

The scope of the C4D practice Slovenia is

- to design, test and evaluate (using PDSA cycles),
- a digitally-enhanced educational program for patients with type 2 diabetes to support their healthy life choices, delivered at secondary level of care,
- that will be compatible to the organizational, professional and cultural context, existing terminology and symbols and building on the strengths of the existing national level recommendations, tools and approaches, and upgrading them with specific topics (physical activity, sleep and stress reduction),
- by fully embracing a co-creation approach and research methodologies in social sciences, including the most recent ones,
- with the optimal use of face-to-face interaction in combination with digital solution to increase the efficiency of the existent (human) resources,
- and to identify the approaches to increase the skills of diabetes educators, medical doctors and other healthcare professionals in areas identified (such as coaching, use of digital tools, and related to physical activity, sleep and stress reduction as topics),
- including development of action plan for scaling-up the educational program at national level including the **permanent digital platform (i.e. <https://e-diabetes.si/>)**, and that will include the identified gaps related to diabetes education (competencies, approaches, topics, organisation) at micro (individual patient-HCP interaction), meso (healthcare organisation including healthcare teams) and macro level (healthcare system),
- and to use the potential of C4D to increase visibility of importance of education in type 2 diabetes at national level.

Attachment XII Spain

Beneficiary Entity: SPAIN

CSPA.FICYT.SESPA: Marta M. Pisano González, Inés Rey Hidalgo, Isabel Diez Valcarce, Cristina Fernández García.

SCS.IDIVAL. Luis Alberto Vázquez Salví, Paloma González Álvarez, Natalia Montoya.

FUNDESALUD.JUNTAEX. Carla Venturi Monteagudo, Bernardino Morillo Merino, Yolanda Tomé Pérez, Elisabeth García Alonso.

SERGAS: Blanca Cimadevila Álvarez, Alfonso Alonso Fachado, Silvia Suárez Luque, Carolina Muñoz Ibáñez, Paula Urones Cuesta.

SAS.FPS: Eduardo Mayoral, María Asunción Martínez Brocca. Rafael Rodríguez Acuña.

GAIAP: Lucía Lasilla, Rosa Magallón, Cruz Bartolomé, María Millán, Isabel Monreal

Date: April 30, 2023

Developed within Task 5.1, by NIJZ team: Jelka Zaletel, Anja Brunec, Denis Oprešnik

Based on the approach and experiences from JA CHRODIS, JA CHRODIS PLUS and JADECARE including the implementation strategy, developed by Institute for Health Services Research - Kronikgune, Basque Country, Spain

Contact e-mail: care4diabetes@nijz.si

jelka.zaletel@kclj.si, anja.brunec@nijz.si, denis.opresnik@nijz.si

Steps	Date of the completion	Organizer	Comments
I	27.02.2023	Marta M. Pisano González Isabel Diez Valcarce	Spanish Consortium
	10.03.2023	Marta M. Pisano González Isabel Diez Valcarce	CSPA/SESPA/FICYT
	16.03.2023	Rosa Magallón	GAIAP
	17.03.2023	Paloma González	SCS.IDIVAL. After the Spanish videoconference coordinated by the Asturian partners, the Cantabrian team decided to have a meeting to start with the step one of this report in order to define the team and the roles.
	18.04.2023	Blanca Cimadevilla	SERGAS
	27.03.2023	María Asunción Martínez Brocca	SAS.FPS
II	17.03. 2023	Marta M. Pisano González Isabel Diez Valcarce	Spanish Consortium
	24.03.2023 07.04.2023	Bernardino Morillo Merino	FUNDESALUD. JUNTAEX Work on Step I, Step II
	29.03.2023	Marta M. Pisano González Isabel Diez Valcarce	CSPA/SESPA/FICYT
	05.04.2023	Natalia Montoya	SCS.IDIVAL. After the Spanish videoconference coordinated by the Asturian partners, the Cantabrian team decided to have a meeting to start with the step one of this report in order to define the team and the roles.
	17.04.2023	Lucía Lasilla	GAIAP
	18.04.2023	Blanca Cimadevilla	SERGAS
	11.04.2023	María Asunción Martínez Brocca	SAS.FPS

III	14.04.2023	Marta M. Pisano González Isabel Diez Valcarce	Spanish Consortium
	10.04.2023	Marta M. Pisano González Isabel Diez Valcarce	CSPA/SESPA/FICYT
	13.04.2023	Bernardino Morillo Merino	JUNTAEX
	17.04.2023	Lucía Lasilla	GAIAP
	18.04.2023	María Asunción Martínez Brocca	SAS.FPS
	20.04.2023	Natalia Montoya	SCS.IDIVAL Cantabrian team shared their opinions on the topic proposed in Step III and defined their stakeholders.
	25.04.2023	Blanca Cimadevilla	SERGAS
IV	28.04.2023	Marta M. Pisano González Isabel Diez Valcarce	Spanish Consortium
	26.04.2023	Natalia Montoya	SCS.IDIVAL Cantabrian team meets for the last Step and the global revision of the document.
	17.04.2023 22.04.2023 26.04.2023	Bernardino Morillo Merino	FUNDESALUD.JUNTAEX Phone calls and video-meetings with stakeholders. Document preparation and translation.
	17.04.2023	Lucía Lasilla	GAIAP
	25.04.2023	Blanca Cimadevilla	SERGAS
	25.04.2023	María Asunción Martínez Brocca	SAS.FPS
	27.04.2023	Marta M. Pisano González	CSPA/SESPA/FICYT

	Isabel Diez Valcarce	
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Abbreviations:

CSCJA- Consejería de Salud y Consumo Junta de Andalucía

CSPA- Consejería de salud del Principado de Asturias

FICYT- Fundación para el Fomento en Asturias de la Investigación Científica Aplicada y la Tecnología.

FPS- Fundación Progreso y Salud

FUNDESALUD- Fundación para la Formación e Investigación de los Profesionales de la Salud en Extremadura

GAIAP- Grupo Aragonés de Investigación en Atención Primaria

IDIVAL- Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria Valdecilla

JUNTAEX- Junta de Extremadura

SAS- Servicio Andaluz de Salud

SCS- Servicio Cántabro de Salud

SERGAS- Servicio Gallego da Saude

SESPA- Servicio de Salud del Principado de Asturias

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STEP I: C4D TEAM

Meeting/agreement dates: Feb 27, 2023, March 10 2023, March 16 2023, March 17 2023, March 18 2023, March 27 2023.

C4D Spain teams members: Marta M. Pisano González, Inés Rey Hidalgo, Isabel Diez Valcarce, Cristina Fernandez García, Luis Alberto Vázquez Salví, Paloma Gonzalez Álvarez, Natalia Montoya, Carla Venturi Monteagudo, Bernardino Morillo Merino, Yolanda Tomé Pérez, Elisabeth García Alonso, Blanca Cimadevila Álvarez, Alfonso Alonso Fachado, Silvia Suárez Luque, Carolina Muñoz Ibañez, Paula Urones Cuesta, Eduardo Mayoral, Maria Asunción Martínez Brocca, Rafael Rodríguez Acuña, Lucía Lasilla, Rosa Magallón, Cruz Bartolomé, María Millán, Isabel Monreal and Nuria Prieto Santos.

Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
Organiser	Marta M. Pisano González	CSPA	Scientific Coordinator C4D
Organiser	Bernardino Morillo Merino	FUNDESALUD	Project technician
Organiser	Rosa Magallón Botaya	GAIAP	
Organiser	Paloma Gonzalez	IDIVAL	As project manager of IDIVAL, Paloma was in charge of the organization of the meetings and the minutes, it is expected to incorporate a new person that will play this role of organiser
Organiser	Maria Asunción Martínez Brocca	SAS	
Organiser	Blanca Cimadevila Álvarez	SERGAS	Head of Assistance Integration Service
Decision maker	Nuria Prieto Santos	Spanish Ministry of Health	General Subdirectorate for Quality of Care. Ministry of Health.
Decision maker	Carmen Lama Herrera	CSCJA	
Decision maker	Maria Josefa Fernández Cañedo.	CSPA	General Directorate of care, humanization and social and health care.

Decision maker	Jonathan Gómez Raja	FUNDESALUD	Science Coordinator European Projects
Decision maker	Galo Peralta	IDIVAL	Managing director of the biomedical research institute.
Decision maker	Jose Luis Vicente	JUNTAEX	Directorate General JUNTAEX
Decision maker	Castañar García Gomez	SCS	Medical Doctor specialist in diabetes and medical associate director in the main hospital of SCS
Decision maker	Alfonso Alonso Fachado	SERGAS	Deputy Director General of Care Management and Innovation
Decision maker	Silvia Suarez Luque	SERGAS	Public Health Directorate. Deputy Director General of Development Programs of healthy lifestyles
Senior Advisor	Ana M Carrizo	CSCJA	
Expert	Maria Jesús Rodríguez Nachón	CSPA	
Expert	Inés Rey Hidalgo	FICYT	Coordinator
Expert	Elisabeth García	FUNDESALUD	Phycologist
Expert	Carla Venturi Monteagudo	FUNDESALUD	Doctor
Expert	Isabel Monreal Aliaga	GAIAP	
Expert	Lucía Lasilla Fernández	GAIAP	Family and Community Medical Doctor.
Expert	Yolanda Tomé Pérez	JUNTAEX	Diabetes Nurse
Expert	Marcos Cobaleda Velasco	JUNTAEX	Secretary of Research commission JUNTAEX
Expert	Eduardo Mayoral Sánchez	SAS	
Expert	Luis Alberto Vazquez Salví	SCS	As Medical Doctor specialist in diabetes and principal investigator of

			this project, Luis will act as expert
Expert	Abraham Delgado Diego	SCS	Technician in the healthcare unit in the SCS and is expert in chronicity.
Expert	Pedro Muñoz	SCS	Medical Doctor specialist in diabetes.
Expert	Maria Gonzalez Villa	SCS	Medical Doctor endocrinology service.
Expert	Cristina Fernández García	SESPA	Nurse and Psychologist.
Expert	María Antonia Herrero Jabonero	SESPA	Nurse at the General Directorate of Care responsible of Humanization.
Expert	Isabel Diez Valcarce	SESPA	Coordinator
Expert	Carolina Muñoz Ibañez	SERGAS	Public Health Directorate. Head of the Healthy Lifestyles and Health Education Service
Expert	Paula Urones Cuesta	SERGAS	Coordinator
Project manager	Natalia Montoya	IDIVAL	Experience as project manager in various projects related to diabetes.
Project Manager	Rafael Rodríguez-Acuña	FPS	

Multidisciplinary team, that will run C4D practice (some of them may also be part of C4D team and include them above)			
Role	Name Surname	Institution	Comments
C4D practice coordinator	Bernardino Morillo Merino	FUNDESALUD	15 years coordinating EU projects
C4D practice coordinator	Cruz Bartolome	GAIAP	Medical doctor expert in research.
C4D practice coordinator	Eduardo Mayoral Sánchez	SAS	Medical doctor expert in diabetes.

C4D practice coordinator	Natalia Montoya Calzada	SCS	
C4D practice coordinator	Paula Urones Cuesta	SERGAS	
C4D practice coordinator	Isabel Diez Valcarce	SESPA	
Medical doctor	Carla Venturi Monteagudo	FUNDESALUD	Experienced in research.
Medical doctor	Lucía Lasilla Fernández	GAIAP	
Medical doctor	María V. Iborra Oquendo	SAS	
Medical doctor	Josefa Mayoral Sánchez	SAS	
Pharmacist	Carlos Fernández Oropesa	SAS	
Medical doctor	Maria González Villa	SCS	Medical doctor with experience in clinical trials.
Medical doctor	Luis Alberto Vazquez Salvi	SCS	
Medical doctor	Teresa Martínez Ramonde	SERGAS	Head of endocrinology service.
Medical doctor	Jose María Nieto	SESPA	
Coach	Elisabeth García Alonso	FUNDESALUD	Psychologist.
Coach	Isabel Monreal	GAIAP	
Coach	Rosa Ayesa	IDIVAL	Psychologist, head of the mental diseases research group.
Coach	Mario Alberto Rivas Carro	SERGAS	University professor of Mental Health.
Dietitian	Fabiola Cruz	IDIVAL	Dietitian in the endocrinology service.
Dietitian	Iria Gonzalez Fraga	SERGAS	Dietitian.
Dietitian	Yolanda Tomé Pérez	JUNTAEX	Specialist diabetes nurse.
Diabetes Nurse	Lourdes Aizpeolea San Miguel	SCS	Nurse in the endocrinology service.
Diabetes nurse	José Andrés Peña Álvarez	SERGAS	Diabetes nurse educator.
Diabetes Nurse/dietitian	TBD	SAS	At least 3 primary care nurses (from the “Sevilla” and “Granada

			<p>Nordeste” Health Districts).</p> <p>2-3 Diabetes Advanced Primary Nurse (from the “Sevilla” and “Granada Nordeste” Health Districts).</p> <p>At least 2 Health Promotion Technician (from the “Sevilla” and “Granada Nordeste” Health Districts).</p>
Diabetes Nurse/dietitian	Esther González N	SESPA	
Diabetes Nurse/dietitian	Sara López Álvarez	SESPA	Nurse at Primary care center
Diabetes Nurse/dietitian	Sara Padrino Ojea	SESPA	Family and community Nurse
Diabetes Nurse/dietitian	María Ablanedo Mingot	SESPA	Nurse at endocrine department, experienced in diabetes
Diabetes Nurse/dietitian	Manuela Parrondo Fernández	SESPA	Nurse teaching department
Diabetes Nurse/dietitian	Alejandro Álvarez Álvarez	SESPA	Family and community Nurse
Diabetes Nurse/dietitian	Raquel Méndez	SESPA	Nurse at endocrine department, experienced in diabetes

STEP II: C4D TEAM'S SCOPE

Consensus meetings dates: March 17 2023, March 24 2023, March 29 2023, April 5 2023, April 7 2023, April 11 2023, April 17 2023, April 18 2023.

C4D Spain teams members: Marta M. Pisano González, Inés Rey Hidalgo, Isabel Diez Valcarce, Cristina Fernandez García, Luis Alberto Vázquez Salví, Paloma Gonzalez Álvarez, Natalia Montoya, Carla Venturi Monteagudo, Bernardino Morillo Merino, Yolanda Tomé Pérez, Elisabeth García Alonso, Blanca Cimadevila Álvarez, Alfonso Alonso Fachado, Silvia Suárez Luque, Carolina Muñoz Ibañez, Paula Urones Cuesta, Eduardo Mayoral, Maria Asunción Martínez Brocca, Rafael Rodríguez Acuña, Lucía Lasilla, Rosa Magallón, Cruz Bartolomé, María Millán, Isabel Monreal and Nuria Prieto Santos.

The Spanish consortium agrees regarding the Steep II questions:

** What would you like to accomplish within the work of C4D?

The Spanish consortium is to design a T2D pilot lifestyle intervention strategy, which would be based on therapeutic education and led by primary care nurses. The aim is to test this strategy in several primary care centers to collect data to support its subsequent scaling up as the first stage of a progressive deployment in the National Healthcare System.

We will work on how to create a new T2D alternative treatment protocol and to improve communication between the public and private health sector in diabetes treatments.

T2D patients demand greater involvement of healthcare professionals and the design of practical activities to identify the needs and priorities of patients with T2D.

It is also address by the Spanish consortium how to highlight changing lifestyle habits contributes to the management of chronic diseases in general and T2D particularly, supporting the development of their decision-making skills and promoting the prevention of complications in T2D.

In addition, the facilitating support of new educational technology and the online T2D community platform will improve communication, cooperative interaction among T2D participants and fluent dialogue with professionals. It also includes the learning process assessment, evaluating how behavioral changes and new attitudes towards T2D appear and to identify where to adapt, adopt, adjust or abandon according to the pilot's experiences.

The Spanish consortium pursues to enhance the collaboration of multidisciplinary professionals as a complementary team, promoting the development of a scientific research network to support this approach effectiveness, contributing to its sustainability as part of the established health system in place.

Finally, we will encourage collaborative interactive projects including T2D associations and different stakeholders to engage them with this project.

** When C4D ends, what would you like to see as the result?

After the T2D intervention program development it is expected that its participants will follow the proposed treatment and activities to improve their condition self-management, particularly related to diet and physical activity, reducing the use of their medication too. Participants would understand that their treatment success depends overall on their determining diabetes factors proper management.

Besides, it is intended to obtain a broad and comprehensive framework on the learning process and self-care awareness, to create a new solid evidence-based treatment, and to promote self-care and the adherence to therapeutic self-management.

The visibility and recognition of the multidisciplinary team and the widespread of the program among the population and professionals will extend to more people with T2D throughout the country and this new professional's approach will grow.

** What would you like to see that would happen after C4D ends?

The Spanish consortium would extend the practice and scale it up adapting to other conditions and proving its effectiveness in new different scenarios, as a solid T2D Best Practice. A stable maintenance of physiologic parameters (glycemic index, body weight, plasma lipids, blood pressure) in T2D through systematic promotion of healthy lifestyles is feasible and affordable by the Health System with the corresponding reduction of T2D patients in the respective region and in the country. That will contribute to the expansion of C4D protocol along regional and national Health Care System.

A general change of mentality would occur, from the political commitment, at national and local jurisdictions, to align themselves in the strategy of promotion of healthy habits perspective, self-management individual care with regulations that would enhance and facilitate this approach. Not another road to nowhere after three years of C4D Joint Action.

Based on the exhaustive data analysis, scientific value and support to the figures would prove efficient this method, preventing avoidable costs and improving patients' conditions at the same time.

STEP III: CONTEXT REVIEW AND KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Consensus meetings dates: April 10 2023, April 13 2023, April 14 2023, April 17 2023, April 18 2023, April 20 2023, April 25 2023.

C4D Spain teams members: Marta M. Pisano González, Inés Rey Hidalgo, Isabel Diez Valcarce, Cristina Fernandez García, Luis Alberto Vázquez Salví, Paloma Gonzalez Álvarez, Natalia Montoya, Carla Venturi Monteagudo, Bernardino Morillo Merino, Yolanda Tomé Pérez, Elisabeth García Alonso, Blanca Cimadevila Álvarez, Alfonso Alonso Fachado, Silvia Suárez Luque, Carolina Muñoz Ibañez, Paula Urones Cuesta, Eduardo Mayoral, Maria Asunción Martínez Brocca, Rafael Rodríguez Acuña, Lucía Lasilla, Rosa Magallón, Cruz Bartolomé, María Millán, Isabel Monreal and Nuria Prieto Santos.

External participants, Paloma Pacho, Medical Director of teams in Area IV (Oviedo) of Asturias, Ana Gemma García Alvarez Nursing Director of Area VII (Mieres) of Asturias, Mieres Sur Area VII Health Center, Moreda Area VII Health Center, Maria José Liboreiro Suarez Nursing Director of Area VIII (Langreo) of Asturias, Elena Miguel Rodríguez Continuity of Care Coordinator of Area VIII (Langreo) of Asturias, Beatriz Braña Marcos Deputy Director of Nursing Area V (Gijón) of Asturias, Jose María Nieto Area Medical Director VI (Arriondas) of Asturias, Pedro Abad Internist Area VI, Raquel Fernandez Nursing Director of Area I (Jarrio) of Asturias, Bárbara Gonzalez, Medical Director of Area II (Cangas del Narcea) of Asturias, Yolanda Menendez Carbayo Nursing Director of Area II (Cangas del Narcea) of Asturias, Iñigo De Diego Marín Economic and Professional Director in Sanitary Area VIII, Cabueñes Metabolic Unit, Gijón. Amalia Fernández Vázquez Director of the Valle del Nalón hospital in Area VIII, Rocío Allande Coordinator of Assistance Management of the Central Services of the Health Service of the Principality of Asturias, Alejandra Fueyo Director of Health Care and Evaluation of the Health Service of the Principality of Asturias, Elena Garzo Economic-Financial and Infrastructure Director of the Health Service of the Principality of Asturias, Castañar García Gomez - Cantabrian Health Service, Abraham Delgado - Cantabrian Health Service, Lourdes Aizpeolea - Cantabrian Health Service, María González Villa - Cantabrian Health Service, Rosa Ayesa- IDIVAL, Antonio Lavado Castillo president of the Federation of Associations of People with Diabetes in Extremadura, (FADEX), Vicente Caballero Pajares president of the Extremadura Diabetes Society (SEDI), Verónica Martín Galán Managing Director of Fundesalud, David Peñalver Talavera president of the Sociedad Extremeña de Endocrinología y Nutrición, María Gil Marchena president of the Sociedad Extremeña de Enfermería Familiar y Comunitaria (SEFyCEX), Jose Manuel García Romero president of FEGADI (Federación Galega de Asociacions de Diabéticos), Teresa Martínez Ramonde- SERGAS, José Andrés Peña Álvarez- SERGAS , Iria González Fraga- SERGAS, Mario Alberto Rivas Carro- SERGAS , María Victoria Iborra Oquendo (SAS).

At national/regional level			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
<p>NATIONAL HEALTH SYSTEM</p> <p>Participation of the Spanish National Ministry of Health will evaluate the development and conclusions of the activity at the central level.</p> <p>Universal health system in place and running</p> <p>Public health care system with a broad portfolio of services including diabetes education.</p> <p>Electronic Health record and regular T2D programmed visits in place.</p> <p>Integrated Diabetes Plan in place. It includes an integrated T2D care process.</p>	<p>Decentralization of the health system at national level.</p> <p>Different administrative local health systems to coordinate.</p> <p>Incomplete and non-homogeneous implementation of therapeutic education in primary healthcare.</p> <p>Healthcare burden:</p> <p>Not enough time per patient, including time to teach T2D patients.</p>	<p>Universal health assistance.</p> <p>European project engaging several countries: when positive results, new supportive strategies.</p> <p>Same evaluation methodology will provide common understanding at country level.</p> <p>Increased prestige of the healthcare system.</p> <p>Reduction of the economic cost: on medication and treatment of complications.</p> <p>Equity T2D approach among European Countries.</p> <p>Impact on regional, national and international health policies.</p>	<p>Prospective to have less professionals available as ratio patients per medical professionals increase while decreasing the time to take proper care of the patient.</p> <p>Uncertainty about the possibility of generalizing education due to lack of funding and/or human resources.</p> <p>Increasing rates of aging according to demographic projections, which implies a greater number of comorbidities, and therefore of T2D.</p>
<p>SYSTEM-PATIENTS PROFESIONALS INTERACTION-</p> <p>Strong commitment of healthcare professionals to patients.</p> <p>Follow up of T2D patients at health centers.</p> <p>Close relationship with the patient.</p> <p>Multidisciplinary team motivated and ready to work T2D learning proactively.</p>	<p>Inadequate Primary Care relationship professionals-patients.</p> <p>T2D paternalistic management attitude still coexist.</p> <p>Tendency to introduce medical treatment at early stages as first option.</p> <p>Over-prescription: excessive medicalization T2D</p> <p>Unequal approach/T2D coach and training depending on the professional responsible.</p>	<p>Lifestyle Key Performance Indicators included as part of medical records.</p> <p>Liaison nurses and social workers are regular members of the multidisciplinary teams.</p> <p>Social workers engaged in training and follow up of T2D.</p> <p>Emphasis on prevention in educational programs.</p> <p>The prospect of group techniques over individual ones as more efficient therapeutic education.</p>	<p>Resistance to change educational strategies among professionals.</p> <p>Insufficient professionals' number (rural areas, regular absences, on-call duty...).</p> <p>Resistance of professionals towards the change of educational strategies.</p> <p>Early prescription of drugs, difficult to erase.</p> <p>Reduction in pharmaceutical research</p>

<p>Knowledge exchange between health and non-health personnel.</p> <p>Expert diabetes nurse who can train on an individual level.</p> <p>Regular optional training in place (General Planning Directorate)</p> <p>Updated information through new communication channels.</p> <p>Possibility of taking courses to improve knowledge of diabetes</p> <p>Phone and video chat healthcare.</p> <p>E-learning and technology applied to learning</p>	<p>Regardless stage of T2D same message sent.</p> <p>No clarity on the individualized prescription of knowledge for change in lifestyles.</p> <p>Not having a diabetes nurse or doctor as a reference in all health centres.</p> <p>Lack of specific profiles for those positions.</p> <p>No dietitian or coach available in most cases.</p> <p>No psychological support in place for T2D.</p> <p>Poor culture on group health education.</p> <p>Lack of protocolized infrastructure.</p> <p>Deficient lifestyle change treatment follow-up.</p> <p>Poor number of liaison nurses (the one relating to Hospital and Primary Care systems).</p> <p>Poor participation of social workers (patients at risk of exclusion).</p> <p>Scarce number of human resources available for education for the number of patients (nurse educators and dietitians).</p> <p>Healthcare professional burned out because overloaded</p> <p>Total or partial absence of continuity of care report between different levels of care.</p> <p>Resistance to change (of health professionals/ person with diabetes)</p> <p>Lack of knowledge about the impact of healthy lifestyles on disease control (the most</p>	<p>Greater empowerment of the patients and self-control of T2D.</p> <p>Patients will be more involved if they can see the positive results of the interventions (body weight loss; lower glucose, plasma lipids and blood pressure; reduction in the need of drugs...) for themselves.</p> <p>Increased awareness and involvement of patients in their disease.</p> <p>Being able to adapt new learning technologies to the reality.</p> <p>Structured individual and group diabetes education programs.</p> <p>Continuity of care report in place and regular writing report extended.</p>	<p>on anti-diabetic treatments.</p>
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	<p>effective treatment for diabetes).</p> <p>No standardized training for healthcare professionals in motivation and psychological management of the patient</p> <p>Lack of regular self-care training for professionals.</p> <p>Lack of advanced practice nursing training in diabetes.</p> <p>Lack of regular standard training in diabetes among health professionals.</p>		
<p>PATIENTS</p> <p>Increased social awareness of the importance of acquiring healthy lifestyles as a measure to prevent the onset of diseases.</p> <p>Individual patient advice.</p> <p>Planning structure care plans.</p>	<p>Ageing population with greater difficulty in acquiring new lifestyle habits and healthy behaviours.</p> <p>T2D population increasing numbers, unaware responsible for their own process.</p> <p>There are no regulatory standards that prevent obesogenic environments.</p> <p>Unhealthy lifestyle from earlier ages.</p> <p>T2D treatment based on pharmacological treatment.</p> <p>T2D autonomy and control loss inducing disengagement and treatment dependency.</p> <p>No structured or specific T2D training: fix and limited sessions not adjusting to individual needs as a chronic process of the disease.</p> <p>Patient resistance to change</p> <p>Advice easy to forget if not immediate acquisition of new habits.</p> <p>Poor training focuses on patients 'digital capacity building.</p>	<p>Individual and group structured diabetic educational programs.</p> <p>T2D population aware and mature to work on their own progress and control.</p> <p>T2D generates their own reflection, own learning.</p> <p>T2D goals are settle by themselves taking control and responsibility of their own process.</p> <p>Specific T2D telemedicine access.</p> <p>New health education platforms and tools that improve disease perception and can be implemented in similar pathologies.</p> <p>More people will be able to use internet devices properly that can help to take care of their own health.</p> <p>Being able to adapt new learning technologies to the reality.</p>	<p>High prevalence of people with obesity and T2D with tendency to increase over time.</p> <p>Applying lifestyle change regulations effectively is complex without the collaboration of the patient.</p> <p>T2D change resistance to improve their quality of life.</p> <p>Possibility of obsessive thoughts in relation to lifestyle.</p> <p>Digital divide.</p> <p>Patient resistance to education due to associated psychosocial problems.</p>

At local setting (IT COMPILES DIFFERENT REALITIES FROM DIFFERENT REGIONS IN SPAIN ADDED TO TABLE ABOVE)			
Current situation		Future	
Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative
<p>Protocols in place. There is a Comprehensive Diabetes Plan in the Region. Integrated management of personal health records (linking of various sources of information through the single health record number). A single and universal personal health record.</p> <p>Accumulated experience in the management by Integrated Care Process (including 'Healthcare for people with diabetes'). Some small regions allow a close patient-nurse educator relationship.</p>	<p>Professionals' agenda overloaded. Professionals fatigue. Few nurses involved in diabetes education. Low interest on focusing on the mental health. Not having a diabetes nurse or doctor as a reference in the health centers. Not the same education for everyone. The education level of diabetes depends on the health professionals that are taking care of that patient. No dietitian available. No exercise coach available. Lack of time and resources. Resistance to change on the part of professionals and patients</p>	<p>Promotion of Community Activities as a wellness driver. Proven cases will stimulate participation. Entrusted teams, system and community get recognition. Bonds reinforced between institutions to incorporate aspects of the activity into educational strategies. Inclusion of C4D in common daily practice. C4D could support dialogue, collaboration and better coordination of institutions in the field of diabetes education. Population pyramid less aged than the average regional population (particular case).</p>	<p>Uncertainty about the possibility of continued funding for education improvements. The sustainability of public healthcare system is under pressure due to the increase of the population aging and its chronic condition. Changes in the political situation and organizational models. Institutional engagement required for sustainability of the project. Multiple research projects must be ensured.</p>
<p>Highly experienced, knowledgeable local team with access to patients. Improved patient-physician relationship.</p>		<p>Involvement and recognition of the work and its results, integrating it into the daily practice of diabetes professionals.</p>	<p>Mind-sets evolution required. Excessive patient responsibility. Need to adapt the program to the patient and his or her limitations.</p>
<p>There are voluntary training courses currently run by the Planning DG. Possibility of taking courses at SERGAS to</p>	<p>Language barrier from original practice. Resistance to change on the part of professionals and patients.</p>	<p>Evidence based approach. T2D participate in C4D in the way that best suits their needs giving flexibility and adapting to individual needs.</p>	<p>Lack of time for teamwork.</p>

<p>improve knowledge of diabetes.</p> <p>High prestige of medical institutions in clinical research, particularly in diabetes.</p> <p>The population is receptive to collaborate in health research projects.</p>	<p>Aged & scattered population mostly in rural areas.</p> <p>Geographic areas with adverse socioeconomic status.</p> <p>Digital divide.</p>	<p>Decreased pressure on patient care due to patient autonomy.</p>	
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KEY STAKEHOLDERS

Key stakeholders and their level of involvement			
Institution/personal name	Contact, if known	Level of involvement*	Comments
Nuria Prieto Santos	nprieto@sanidad.gob.es	full participation	General Subdirectorate for Quality of Care. Spanish Ministry of Health.
Maria Josefa Fernández Cañedo	Maríajosefa.fernandezcanedo@asturias.org	full participation	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Rocío Allande	Rocio.allande@sespa.es	full participation	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Association of Diabetics Principality of Asturias (ASDIPAS).	info@asdipas.org	consultation	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Diabetes Advisory Council of the Principality of Asturias (CADPA).	Joseantoniomarinvaldes@asturias.org	Full participation	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
President of the International Society of Bioethics.	Isolina.riano@sespa.es bioetica@sibi.org	consultation	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Head of the Endocrinology and Nutrition Service of the HUCA. Central University Hospital of Asturias.	edelmiro.menendez@sespa.es	consultation	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Patient Schools , belonging to the Asturias School of Care.	Escueladecuidados@asturias.org	informed	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT

Asturias Society of Family and Community Medicine (SaMFyC).	samfyc.asturias@samfyc.org	informed	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Asturias Association of Community Nursing (SEAPA).	Presidencia@seapa.es	informed	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Members of the Asturias Diabetes PCAI (Key Interdisciplinary Care Program).	dgcuidados@asturias.org	consultation	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Older people University (PUMUO).	dir.extension@uniovi.es	informed	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Foundation for Biosanitary Research and Innovation of the Principality of Asturias (FINBA).	info@finba.es	Full participation	CSPA.SESPA.FICYT
Castañar García Gómez	mdelcastanar.garcia@scsalud.es	full participation	CSC.IDIVAL
Pedro Muñoz	pedro.munoz@scsalud.es	full participation	CSC.IDIVAL
Abraham Delgado - Sub-directorate of Care, Training and Care Continuity.	abraham.delgado@scsalud.es	full participation	CSC.IDIVAL
Cantabria Diabetes Association.	diabetescantabria@gmail.com	briefly informed	CSC.IDIVAL
Iñaki Lapuente – Managing Director of Primary Health of Cantabria.	inaki.lapuente@scsalud.es	briefly informed	CSC.IDIVAL
Reinhard Wallmann – General Director of Public Health.	dgsalud@cantabria.es	briefly informed	CSC.IDIVAL
Cantabria School of Health.	info@escuelacantabradesalud.es	informed	CSC.IDIVAL
Cantabria Health Service.	buzgen.dg@scsalud.es	briefly informed	CSC.IDIVAL

Cantabria Regional Ministry of Health.	consejosanitario@scsalud.es	briefly informed	CSC.IDIVAL
Aureliano Ruiz Salmón	diabetescantabria@gmail.com	consultation	CSC.IDIVAL
UNATE – Cantabria Permanent University.	unate@unate.es	briefly informed	CSC.IDIVAL
Spanish Society of Endocrinology and Nutrition.	secretaria@seen.es	briefly informed	CSC.IDIVAL
Diabetes Spanish Society.	secretaria@sediabetes.org	briefly informed	CSC.IDIVAL
Spanish Obesity Society.	secretaria@seco.org	briefly informed	CSC.IDIVAL
Federation of Associations of People with Diabetes of Extremadura (FADEX).	Antonio Lavado Castillo	consultation	JUNTAEX. FUNDESALUD Patients piloting in the region. Communication support.
Extremadura Diabetes Society (SEDI).	Vicente Caballero Pajares	consultation	JUNTAEX. FUNDESALUD Communication and political support.
FundeSalud.	Verónica Martín Galán	full participation	JUNTAEX. FUNDESALUD Training and piloting support. Third party in the project.
Extremadura Society of Endocrinology and Nutrition.	David Peñalver Talavera	informed	JUNTAEX. FUNDESALUD
Extremadura Society of Family and Community Nursing.	María Gil Marchena	informed	JUNTAEX. FUNDESALUD
Galician Federation of Diabetic Associations (FEGADI).	Jose Manuel García Romero	Consultation	SERGAS
Asociation of patients with diabetes of Aragón.		Briefly informed	GAIAP

<p>Zaragoza Medical Profesional Association.</p>		Briefly informed	GAIAP
<p>Regional Ministry of Health and Consumers Affairs of Andalusia:</p> <p>Chief of the Health Promotion and Local Health Action Service.</p> <p>General Directorate for Public Health and Pharmaceutical Organisation.</p> <p>The Andalusian Strategy for the Promotion of a Healthy Life.</p> <p>The Andalusian Comprehensive Care Strategy.</p>	<p>María Dolores Fernández</p> <p>Deputy Director of Pharmaceutical Management, Strategies, Prevention and Health Promotion.</p> <p>Pablo García Cubillana (Head of the strategy)</p> <p>Nieves Lafuente Robles</p>	consultation	SAS.FPS
<p>Andalusian Health Service:</p> <p>General Directorate for Healthcare and Health Outcomes.</p> <p>Deputy-Director of Information Technologies.</p> <p>Deputy-Director of Information Management</p> <p>Coordination of Information Systems</p> <p>Sevilla” and “Granada Nordeste” Health Districts.</p>	<p>Responsible of primary healthcare.</p> <p>Deputy Director</p> <p>Deputy Director.</p> <p>Chief of Service.</p> <p>People responsible of healthcare (mainly family physicians and primary care nurses).</p>	consultation	SAS.FPS

Specialised Healthcare Training of the SAS: Teaching units in: Primary Care Nursing; Family Physicians; Endocrinology and Nutrition	Heads of the Teaching Commissions	informed	SAS.FPS
Regional Ministry of Educational Development and Vocational Training of Andalusia	Responsible with competencies in the field of health promotion among students	informed	SAS.FPS
Federation of Associations of Diabetics of Andalusia , member of the Spanish Federation of Diabetics.	President of the association.	informed	SAS.FPS
Healthcare services of the municipalities .	Responsible for the health promotion programs.	informed	SAS.FPS
Patient Schools , belonging to the Andalusian School of Public Health.	Responsible for the Patient School on diabetes.	informed	SAS.FPS
Scientific societies: Andalusian Society of Family and Community Medicine (SAMFyC). Andalusian Association of Community Nursing (ASANEC). Andalusian Society of Endocrinology, Diabetes and Nutrition (SAEDYN).	Responsibles	Briefly informed	SAS.FPS

*1=full participation; the stakeholder is directly included to the C4D team; include the person retrospectively to the C4D team list

2=consultation; the stakeholder is actively consulted during the process and their opinions are discussed within C4D team

3=informed; the stakeholder is fully informed on decisions and decision-making process

4=briefly informed; the stakeholder is briefly informed at usual contacts or during usually C4D communication and dissemination activities at national, regional and local level.

STEP IV: RE-DEFINITION OF THE SCOPE

Consensus meetings dates: April 17 2023, April 17 2023, April 22 2023, April 25 2023, April 25 2023, April 26 2023, April 26 2023, April 27 2023, April 28 2023.

C4D Spain teams members: Marta M. Pisano González, Inés Rey Hidalgo, Isabel Diez Valcarce, Cristina Fernandez García, Luis Alberto Vázquez Salví, Paloma Gonzalez Álvarez, Natalia Montoya, Carla Venturi Monteagudo, Bernardino Morillo Merino, Yolanda Tomé Pérez, Elisabeth García Alonso, Blanca Cimadevila Álvarez, Alfonso Alonso Fachado, Silvia Suárez Luque, Carolina Muñoz Ibañez, Paula Urones Cuesta, Eduardo Mayoral, Maria Asunción Martínez Brocca, Rafael Rodríguez Acuña, Lucía Lasilla, Rosa Magallón, Cruz Bartolomé, María Millán, Isabel Monreal and Nuria Prieto Santos.

Within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team	
Positive = strengths	Negative =weakness
Promotes outdoors activity.	Low interest on focusing on T2D mental health.
Close relationship with the patient.	Not having enough time.
Universal health assistance.	Not having specific training T2D patients.
Follow up of the patients at Primary Care health centres.	T2D tendency to forget the advice as time pass by.
Availability of nurses' appointments if the patient has doubts or needs help.	Tendency to focus the treatment only on pills.
More people will be able to use internet devices properly that can help to take care of their own health.	Not the same education for everyone. The education level of diabetes depends on the health professionals that are taking care of that patient.
Multidisciplinary with specific functions.	Possibility of discrepancies regarding the method.
High preparation for e-teaching.	No incentives or rewards except the intrinsic one.
Protocolized, structured and validated training.	Time (missing) and no compensation in time / days off / release of schedule, etc.
Some regions are small and manageable easier than others.	Lack of accreditation and recognition of nurses specialized in diabetes.
Close relationship between health personnel and patient.	Absence of the figure of nutritionist/dietician within the health system.

Local team with extensive experience and knowledge of patients with T2D.	Lack of specialized personnel in motivation and psychological aspects.
Highly experienced diabetes nurse educators.	Ageing population with greater difficulty in acquiring new lifestyle habits and healthy behaviours.
Population in particular areas are supportive in health research projects.	Few nurse educators in diabetes. No dietitian or exercise coach available.

Not within the power of C4D team and multidisciplinary team, or is in the future	
Positive = opportunities	Negative = threats
<p>Extrapolate education style to other areas.</p> <p>Development of new health education platforms and tools.</p>	Abandonment of the program/involvement due to extension in time.
Impact more people and these in turn, in others, exponential effect.	Non-recognition (or uncertainty) as a research member.
Increasing social awareness in the education of healthy habits.	Political policies that may affect the project's strategy in the future.
<p>Existence of a corporative and integrated Information System with a shared electronic health record available throughout most public health care system.</p> <p>Existence of a Health Population Data Base as information source with population stratification capacity in some regions.</p> <p>Existence of a Care Model for complex chronic patients in some regions.</p>	Lack of funding in the long term.
Improved patient-physician relationship.	Lack of patient motivation or involvement in the long term.
<p>Patient healthcare based on multidisciplinary teams.</p> <p>Primary care teams which are used to teamwork/ working together. Encourage teamwork.</p>	Patient resistance to change and part of professionals too.
Improvement in the dialogue, collaboration and better coordination of the institutions at local, regional and national level in the field of diabetes education.	Lack of time and/or resources to offer personalized care to each patient.
Patient-centred healthcare at primary level, with highly trained and specialized professionals.	The number of old people is increasing.

<p>Universal T2D coverage of the public health care system. The care is prioritized in the healthcare system, having its own Plan/Strategy and aligning with the rest of the strategies.</p>	<p>The tendency is that there will be less family doctor available in the future, decreasing the time to take proper care of the patient.</p>
<p>Type 2 diabetes is, not only a national challenge and priority, but also an international one (i.e. for the EU, WHO, among others).</p>	<p>Not having a diabetes nurse or doctor as a reference in the health centers. The intervention won't reach all population because of lack of motivation or not use of technologies. Lack of free time and budget to do the intervention.</p>

Having all this in mind, we re-evaluated if the purpose/aim/general objective and the scope as defined in Step II need to be adapted. They should be ambitious, feasible and sustainable.

The purpose Spanish Consortium has related to C4D are the development of the participants quality of life because of their better understanding of T2D, empowering them to a greater control of their glucose levels and glycemetic control.

Their individual awareness, to learn how to make healthier choices will reduce their medication needs and comorbidities improving selfcare. They will receive psychological support to reinforce their motivation and progress.

Patients and professionals' bonds will be reinforced with more connection with health professionals.

The scope of the practice for the Spanish Consortium is to establish an effective and sustainable intervention that will be replicable and transfer inside the health system to expand to more T2D.

It is intended to get involved all stakeholders, from individual patients to their associations, health care staff and other policy makers related to T2D so as to ensure a favourable result in the long-term maintenance of lifestyle changes and motivation.

We count on the implementation of psychological support for all patients in the public health system as part of their regular T2D follow up.

Quality health care services expansion and accessibility will be facilitated with the new resource's availability for face-to-face and online program development, counting on the production of educational programs for patients and health care professionals, including new technologies and medical devices arising a network for the exchange of information for patients and professionals.